

THE SPACE COURT FOUNDATION STUDENT SPACE LAW JOURNAL

The GDPR in Space: Mapping Jurisdiction and Navigating Trust
(Maartje van Bellen)

Modernizing the Outer Space Treaty: Article IX and the Legal Governance of Kinetic Anti-satellite Activities
(Yug Raman Srivastava)

Environmental Governance in Orbit: Navigating EIA and ESG Pressures in the Newspace Industry
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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The SCF Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ) is a bi-annual, peer-reviewed publication dedicated to fostering academic excellence among students and early-career professionals in the field of space law and policy. Launched in June 2024 by the Space Court Foundation, it is the first journal exclusively for student-authored scholarship in this specialised discipline.

Aim: To offer an accessible yet exceptionally rigorous forum in which current and recent space-law students can cultivate, publish and refine scholarship of the same calibre demanded by the world's leading academic journals. By welcoming contributions from those without advanced law degrees (LLM or higher), the SCF SSLJ fills a critical gap left by traditional space-law periodicals, which seldom consider submissions from undergraduates or early-stage postgraduates, while nonetheless adhering to the highest standards of peer review and editorial excellence.

Scope: The Journal welcomes original contributions on international, regional and national dimensions of space law and policy, including but not limited to:

- Comparative analyses of national space legislation and regulatory frameworks
- Legal protection of Earth's and outer-space environments (including D&QS preservation)
- Space-traffic management (STM) and space-situational awareness (SSA)
- Satellite spectrum allocation and frequency management
- Emerging issues in space sustainability, cybersecurity and the militarisation of space
- Regulatory and ethical considerations for AI and automated decision-making in space activities
- Policy developments relating to commercial, environmental and public-interest uses of outer space

All submissions undergo double-blind peer review in accordance with the most exacting professional standards. Moreover, as part of our internship programme, SCF interns may submit abstracts and, if accepted, are paired with a dedicated mentor who guides them through the drafting and structuring of a professional manuscript, while ensuring they retain full academic ownership of their ideas and prose.

Further information about the SCF SSLJ can be found on [our website](#).

SPACE COURT LAW LIBRARY MASTHEAD

Work on the Space Court Law Library brings together scholars and students from around the world to collaborate on a range of research projects. Together, these projects will form a comprehensive and accessible online space law reference library. It will ultimately be home to the most complete repository of primary source legal documents related to national and international space law, both private and public.

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FOREWORD

Welcome to the April 2026 issue of the Space Court Foundation Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ).

In an era of unprecedented growth in space activities – driven by both state and private actors – the need for fresh perspectives and innovative legal analysis has never been greater. The SCF SSLJ was founded to meet that need: an open, dedicated platform where law students and early-career space law professionals can participate in scholarly discourse at the highest level. By removing traditional barriers to publication and providing structured editorial mentorship, we aim to cultivate emerging writing talent, stimulate debate, and advance the rule of law in space.

This issue comprises eight articles and brings together contributions addressing a broad range of pressing and rapidly evolving topics in space law. The authors engage with several key challenges in contemporary outer space governance, including the application of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), anti-satellite activities, and the extension of environmental governance principles to the space domain.

Further contributions examine commercial space mining, the intersection of art and outer space, and questions of state responsibility in the context of armed conflict. The issue also explores the proposed EU Space Act and its potential role in orbital traffic management, as well as the position and influence of mid-sized nations in global space governance.

We are deeply grateful to our authors and peer reviewers for their dedication and hard work, and to the entire editorial team for their unwavering commitment to the standards of academic integrity and clarity that define the SCF SSLJ. We hope that as you explore these articles, you will share our enthusiasm for the quality of thinking on display from the next generation of space lawyers.

— Yana Yakushina and Jonathan Kaley-Isley, Managing Editors, April 2026

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THE GDPR IN SPACE: MAPPING JURISDICTION AND NAVIGATING TRUST

MAARTJE VAN BELLEN¹

ABSTRACT

This article examines the applicability of Article 3 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to space-based personal data collection conducted via Earth observation satellites. Moreover, it measures these findings against public trust perceptions and privacy attitudes. The research adopts a multi-methodological approach, combining a legal doctrinal analysis with psychological theory. Furthermore, it conducts semi-structured interviews with several subject-matter experts. The legal analysis highlights the GDPR's potential but ambiguous extraterritorial reach in regulating these instances. In parallel, the psychological dimension reveals low public trust in space-based observation satellites, compounded by technical complexities and a growing sense of dependence. In order to integrate the two dimensions and create constructive suggestions, this article applies Malcolm Sparrow's risk framework. This reveals that, despite legal uncertainty, the risks associated with satellite-based personal data collection by observation satellites necessitate regulatory oversight, positioning supervisory authorities in a key role for addressing societal harms that extend beyond formal legal responsibilities.

“I often see privacy set against innovation or law enforcement efforts. But privacy is also a form of security, equally important as protection from crime.”

– Monique Verdier, Deputy Chair of the Dutch DPA²

KEYWORDS: GDPR, Extraterritorial Scope, Space-based Satellite Surveillance, Trust Perceptions, Risk Management.

¹ University of Amsterdam; maartj39@gmail.com

² Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal data breaches have become global risks rather than isolated incidents, affecting millions of people.³ A personal data breach is an event involving unauthorised access, disclosure, or misuse of personally identifiable information by someone without proper authorization or for an improper purpose.⁴ Traditionally, personal data breaches have occurred via Earth-based systems, such as subsea fibre-optic cables or wireless networks.⁵ With the growing dependence on outer space satellites for the transmission and storage of data, there is a notable shift in the risk landscape. In the contemporary era, space-based personal data breaches appear increasingly inevitable.⁶

Within this evolving context, a critical legal question arises concerning the applicability of the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR) to personal data processed beyond the Earth's surface. As complex technological capabilities expand into outer space, the need for explicit legal safeguards becomes more pressing.⁷ Moreover, it is essential to approach this matter not solely from a legal perspective but to adopt a broader socio-psychological lens that considers the wider implications. That is because the societal impact of space-based personal data processing extends beyond what legal frameworks can address alone. Moreover, public perceptions determine not only how society views these privacy issues but also how such matters ought to be addressed. Therefore, this article explores the potential applicability of the GDPR to personal data collection by space-based observation satellites and critically examines how this aligns with public trust perceptions in personal data protection in space.

Satellites have become an indispensable part of daily life, supporting a wide range of critical functions across modern society.⁸ The world grows increasingly dependent on satellites and space-based systems for surveillance, infrastructure, communication, and numerous other essential functions. Therefore, understanding their role in relation to privacy concerns is crucial for ensuring ethical governance, public trust, and the protection of individual rights in an era of expanding technological dependence.⁹ There are fundamentally different types of satellites, each with distinct technical properties. While some are capable of storing data over extended periods, others are limited to real-time data transmission.¹⁰ Accordingly, this study narrows its analytical scope to observation satellites.¹¹

³ Leyden, J., Swinhoe, D., & Hill, M. (2024, September 12). *The 18 biggest data breaches of the 21st century*. CSO Online. <https://www.csoonline.com/article/3257425/the-18-biggest-data-breaches-of-the-21st-century.html>.

⁴ Kyriazoglou, J. (2024, October 25). *Information security and breach definitions and obligations*. Apress. 1–14. https://doi.org/10.1007/979-8-8688-0870-8_1.

⁵ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA). (2020, December 14). *ENISA threat landscape for 5G networks report*. <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-report-for-5g-networks>.

⁶ Peeters, W. (2022). *Cyberattacks on satellites: An underestimated political threat*. LSE IDEAS, London School of Economics and Political Science. <https://www.lse.ac.uk/ideas/projects/space-policy/publications/Cyberattacks-on-Satellites>.

⁷ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

⁸ Huang, H., Guo, S., and Wang, K. (2018). Envisioned Wireless Big Data Storage for Low-Earth-Orbit Satellite-Based Cloud. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 25(1). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2018.1700178>.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Sergieieva, K. (2025, March 22). *Types of satellites: Different orbits & real-world uses*. EOS Data Analytics. <https://eos.com/blog/types-of-satellites/>.

¹¹ The technical rationale for this focus follows in the literature review.

The GDPR represents one of the most significant advancements in personal data policy.¹² However, its enforcement regarding space-based personal data collection is sometimes contested due to ambiguous outer space jurisdiction.¹³ A recent report highlights that the extraterritorial enforcement of the GDPR remains uncertain when entities operate outside EU territory without an establishment, representative, or assets within the Union.¹⁴ Although various legal frameworks may be relevant for addressing personal data collection or processing in outer space, this article concentrates on the GDPR, given both its foundational role in European data protection, its global informal influence, and the necessity of maintaining a focused scope.¹⁵

The legal and psychological dimensions of this research are profoundly interconnected. Legal frameworks outline rules for personal data protection, yet their societal influence and necessity arise from perceptions of people.¹⁶ Following this, the academic relevance of this study lies in its dual contribution: it provides a doctrinal legal analysis exploring the potential applicability of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites, and also examines how it corresponds with European citizens' perception of the protection of their personal data in space. This dual approach creates a novel and meaningful combination.

Towards the end of the article, the analysis weighs these two dimensions against each other: the legal reality versus public perceptions and concerns. This leads to an evaluative and normative conclusion, showing that the GDPR, as current legal protection, is not entirely sufficient. However, it should be, given citizens' concerns and their low trust in existing data governance frameworks. As a suggestion, this article introduces the national supervisory authority as a key factor in overseeing compliance and addressing emerging risks.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This article answers a central research question, which it explores through two sub-questions. It adopts a dual methodological approach: a legal doctrinal analysis of the GDPR to space-based observatory satellites, and theoretical research into public trust and attitudes regarding personal data protection in observatory space technologies. Additionally, the research included four interviews with subject-matter experts to substantiate the findings.

- I) The central research question of this study states: How does a possible application of Article 3 of the GDPR to personal data at space-based observation satellites intersect with the trust attitudes of European citizens regarding personal data protection in space?
- II) The first sub-question of this study pertains to the legal dimension, stating: To what extent does the extraterritorial scope of Article 3 of the GDPR apply to personal data collected by Earth observation satellites operated by entities falling within its jurisdictional scope?
- III) The second sub-question examines the psychological dimension: How do individuals' attitudes regarding trust in space-based technologies influence their perceptions of personal data protection in space?

¹² Hoofnagle, C. J., van der Sloot, B., & Zuiderveen Borgesius, F. (2019). The European Union general data protection regulation: What it is and what it means. *Information & Communications Technology Law*, 28(1), 65–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2019.1573501>.

¹³ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

¹⁴ Kastlová, H. (2024, April 17). Report on extraterritorial enforcement of GDPR. European Data Protection Board.

¹⁵ Mishova, A. (2024, October 28). *Global data protection regulation: How GDPR sets the international standard*. GDPR Local. <https://gdprlocal.com/global-data-protection-regulation-how-gdpr-sets-the-international-standard/>.

¹⁶ Pickens, J. (2005). Attitudes and perceptions. In N. Borkowski (Ed.), *Organizational behavior in health care* (pp. 43–75). Jones & Bartlett Publishers.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Two primary gaps can be identified in the literature concerning relevant legal and psychological scholarship. First, the unprecedented applicability of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites. Second, the limited integration of relevant psychological insights, particularly those concerning trust attitudes and privacy perceptions, within legal analyses of space-based personal data collection.

3.1. *The Limits of the GDPR applied to Outer Space*

3.1.1. *The GDPR*

The GDPR,¹⁷ adopted by the European Union (EU) in 2016 and enforced on May 25, 2018, represents one of the most significant advancements in personal data policy.¹⁸ The GDPR is specifically aimed at safeguarding the personal data and privacy rights of individuals within the EU and the European Economic Area (EEA) and extends its scope beyond EU territory by requiring non-EU entities processing the personal data of individuals in the Union to comply.¹⁹ The regulation inter alia establishes a detailed, comprehensive framework of rules on specifically the collection, processing, and storing of data, applying to companies, governments, and organizations.²⁰

3.1.2. *Extraterritorial Scope*

While no legal framework explicitly governs space-based data collection, the GDPR is frequently referenced for this in legal and academic discussions due to its broad extraterritorial scope.²¹ The relevance stems largely from Article 3(2), which extends the regulation's applicability to data controllers and processors not established in the EU if they process personal data of individuals located within the EU.²² In the context of space-based technologies, this may extend to satellite systems operated from outside the EU that collect personal data pertaining to EU citizens.

3.1.3. *Application to Outer Space*

Existing literature largely agrees that the GDPR potentially extends to personal data at space-based satellites. However, its applicability has neither been explicitly articulated within current regulatory texts nor applied in practice.²³ Moreover, given that satellites operate in outer space, their characteristics differ fundamentally from terrestrial data processing to which the GDPR typically applies. Martin Zoltick and Jenny Colgate highlight the pressing need for the development of an international treaty or an updated regulatory framework that delineates jurisdictional authority over actors involved in

¹⁷ The GDPR replaced the 1995 Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC).

¹⁸ Hoofnagle, C. J., van der Sloot, B., & Zuiderveen Borgesius, F. (2019). The European Union general data protection regulation: What it is and what it means. *Information & Communications Technology Law*, 28(1), 65–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2019.1573501>.

¹⁹ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Bu-Pasha, S., & Kuusniemi, H. (2021). Data protection and space: What challenges will the General Data Protection Regulation face when dealing with space-based data? *Journal of Data Protection & Privacy*, 4(1), 52–58. https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/12271/Osuva_Bu-Pasha_Kuusniemi_2021.pdf.

²² Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

²³ Bu-Pasha, S., & Kuusniemi, H. (2021). Data protection and space: What challenges will the General Data Protection Regulation face when dealing with space-based data? *Journal of Data Protection & Privacy*, 4(1), 52–58. https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/12271/Osuva_Bu-Pasha_Kuusniemi_2021.pdf.

the collection of personal data beyond national territories, such as in outer space.²⁴ Such a framework would be essential to determine which legal entity, whether national, regional, or international, has the right to govern, investigate, or adjudicate activities involving personal data collection in space.²⁵

In contrast to the aforementioned authors, Laura Keogh highlights that the GDPR remains the primary data protection framework within the EU.²⁶ She emphasises that it should continue to be regarded as the most relevant personal data protection framework in the context of the evolving space sector.²⁷ Her perspectives align with the broader scholarly view that prioritises the need for clearer interpretations and extensions of the GDPR's existing provisions to space-related activities, rather than advocating for the creation of entirely new legal frameworks.²⁸

Thus, scholars generally maintain that the GDPR is already applicable to space-related data processing, although its application in this context remains largely untested in practice. However, questions remain regarding the allocation of jurisdiction over actors involved in personal data processing beyond national territories. Accordingly, this research conducts a holistic analysis of how the existing regulatory framework may operate in relation to space-based technologies.

3.2. *Types of Satellites Considered*

Roopashree Sharma explains that there are different types of satellites involved in data processing or collecting.²⁹ Among these are observation, communication, and navigation satellites. These categories differ in function and data handling capacity.³⁰ While examining the full spectrum of satellite types could be valuable, this article specifically focuses on observation satellites. This decision is grounded in technical relevance: observation satellites are distinct in that they typically store personal data for prolonged durations, whereas other types either transmit it in real time or are not intended to retain it.³¹

Riccardo Patriarca et al. argue that the extended data retention associated with observation satellites increases the risk of personal data breaches.³² This concern is grounded in the satellite's capacity to store sensitive information related to individuals. Examples of sensitive data concerning observation satellites include high-resolution imagery, as well as other forms of Earth observation data that can capture identifiable human activity.³³

3.3. *Psychological Perspectives: Trust Attitudes and Perceptions*

The psychological dimension of this explores individuals' trust and perceptions of space-based technologies and their attitudes regarding the protection of their personal data. Psychological lenses concerning these specific matters remain largely underexplored in relation to space-based personal data collection. To address this gap, this section engages with established psychological research.

²⁴ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Keogh, L. (2023). EU data protection considerations for the space sector. In P. J. Blount & M.

Hofmann (Eds.), *Space law in a networked world* (pp. 230–255). Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004527270_011.

²⁷ Ibid, p. 251.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Sharma, R. (2024, September 4). *Types of satellites and their applications*. Jagran Josh.

<https://www.jagranjosh.com/general-knowledge/types-of-satellites-and-their-applications-1725441333-1>.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Patriarca, R., Costantino, F., & Di Gravio, G. (2019). Risk, safety, reliability and satellites: Chronicles of a fragmented research field. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 6(3), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssse.2019.08.002>.

³³ Ibid.

Although research on trust attitudes in the context of space observation satellites remains scarce, there is a study by McAmis et al. that examines how American citizens perceive the capabilities and implications of commercial satellite imagery.³⁴ Through interview data, participants express discomfort or a lack of understanding regarding observatory satellite data practices, especially in light of privacy.³⁵ Moreover, participants highlight the importance of regulation in this domain.³⁶ The authors note that these perceptions are particularly relevant given the increasing accuracy of satellite imagery.³⁷

A key takeaway from the study is the widespread concerns among citizens regarding observation satellites, as well as the stressed importance of incorporating constructs such as trust and perceived risk into conceptualisations of regulatory frameworks.³⁸ However, it is important to note that this research was conducted solely in the United States. Further research across diverse contexts is needed to enhance the generalisability of these findings and to extend insights to European citizens. On the other hand, given the global nature of satellite observation technologies, these findings can hold tentative relevance for European citizens as well.

To continue, a meta-analysis by Leschanowsky et al. examines how individuals perceive privacy, security, and trust in artificial intelligence (AI) systems. These include, for example, chatbots and voice assistants.³⁹ The study reveals that numerous individuals express concern regarding the collection, storage, and potential misuse of their personal data.⁴⁰ Specifically, users' concerns regarding privacy and potential data misuse play a critical role in shaping their trust, particularly in environments where personal data is handled by systems that are technologically complex or lack transparency.⁴¹

There are notable parallels regarding trust, privacy, and perceived data security in the context of space-based data collection and AI mechanisms. Namely, similar to satellite technologies, AI systems employ complex and technical methods for collecting data.⁴² Consequently, existing literature suggests that both technologies generate comparable public concerns related to trust, surveillance, and feelings of diminished control.⁴³ Therefore, the low levels of perceived trust, privacy, and data security observed in other technological domains appear similarly applicable to space-based systems, including observation satellites.⁴⁴ This is further reinforced by the growing integration of AI in space-based observation satellites, which increasingly rely on AI to process, analyse, and interpret the vast amounts of data they collect.⁴⁵ In fact, observation satellites and AI are becoming increasingly interdependent, with AI

³⁴ McAmis, R., Sim, M., Bennett, M., & Kohno, T. (2024). Over fences and into yards: Privacy Threats and concerns of commercial satellites. *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2024(1), 379–396. <https://doi.org/10.56553/popets-2024-0022>.

³⁵ Ibid, 384–385

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid, 389–390

³⁹ Leschanowsky, A., Rech, S., Popp, B., & Bäckström, T. (2024). Evaluating privacy, security, and trust perceptions in conversational AI: A systematic review. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 159(2), Article 108344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2024.108344>.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid, 18.

⁴² Zuboff, S. (2019). *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. PublicAffairs.

⁴³ Ibid; Lyons, S. (2023). Satellite surveillance and the orbital unconscious. *New Media & Society*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448231187352>.

⁴⁴ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. PublicAffairs.

⁴⁵ Lachner, C., Mann, Z. Á., & Dustdar, S. (2021). Towards understanding the adaptation space of AI-assisted data protection for video analytics at the edge. In *Proceedings of the 2021 IEEE 41st International Conference on*

functioning as an essential component of satellite operations, making it difficult to consider the two in isolation from one another.⁴⁶

In addition to this, the lack of public trust, specifically in observation satellites, is suggested by broader distrust in satellite technologies and outer space systems in general.⁴⁷ Since observation satellites are central to personal data collection, the general distrust in satellite technologies directly applies to them. Literature highlights that this distrust stems from a fundamental lack of transparency and the inability of current legal frameworks to keep pace with the autonomous and large-scale nature of surveillance, particularly when facilitated by complex, AI-driven technologies in space.⁴⁸

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1. *Legal Positivism and Its Modern Application*

The legal dimension of this study is grounded in the theory of legal positivism, which conceives that the validity of law stems from legislation, formal procedures, and court decisions, rather than satisfying politics or social configurations.⁴⁹ Consequently, a legal positivist perspective is appropriate for examining the GDPR, which represents a codified, rules-based approach to data protection governance. While classical legal positivism avoids normative assessments, this article additionally engages with a modern conceptualization of legal positivism that, in addition, examines normative considerations as integral to the interpretation and practical application of legal provisions.⁵⁰ This approach facilitates a more nuanced analysis.⁵¹

4.2. *The Sparrow Framework*

Furthermore, this article adopts Malcolm Sparrow's safety-management framework to support the exploration of the overarching research question by examining the balance between legal and psychological dimensions. Sparrow's conceptualisation visualises the relationship between legal and harmful phenomena through a Venn diagram.⁵² Essentially, the left side of the model represents matters that are addressed through existing legal mechanisms and enforcement structures. In contrast, the right side pertains to risks that are not formally governed by law but nonetheless pose significant harm to

Distributed Computing Systems Workshops (ICDCSW) (pp. 7–12). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCSW53096.2021.00009>.

⁴⁶ Ghiglione, M., & Serra, V. (2022). Opportunities and challenges of AI on satellite processing units. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF '22)* (221–224). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3528416.3530985>; Yazici, T., Martin, A.-S., Wood, S., Kucher, L., Almenar, R., Zielinski, L. Y., Wedenig, S.-M., & Tricco, G. (2025). *Balancing innovation and responsibility: International recommendations for AI regulation in space*. *Acta Astronautica*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.04.063>.

⁴⁷ McKenna, A. T., Gaudion, A. C., & Evans, J. L. (2020). The role of satellites and smart devices: Data surprises and security, privacy, and regulatory challenges. *University of Pennsylvania Journal of International Law*, 42(2), 289–342.

⁴⁸ Gerlich, M. (2024). Public anxieties about AI: Implications for corporate strategy and societal impact. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(11), 288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14110288>.

⁴⁹ Himma, K. E. (2019). Legal positivism. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2019 Edition). Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2019/entries/legal-positivism/>.

⁵⁰ Simma, B., & Paulus, A. L. (1999). The responsibility of individuals for human rights abuses in internal conflicts: A positivist view. *American Journal of International Law*, 93(2), 302–316. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2997991>

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² While the Venn diagram is discussed in *The Character of Harms*, the actual visual representation does not appear in the book itself but is included in a presentation Sparrow gave at the Twelfth Annual Symposium of the Performance and Planning Exchange on May 27, 2008. The presentation is available at: http://www.ppx.ca/download/symposiums/2008/keynote/2008_pp_Sparrow_e.pdf.

society.⁵³ The core idea of this model is to visualise how certain harms, though argued to lie outside the legal framework, may still warrant regulatory attention if they fall within the scope of the right side.⁵⁴ In doing so, the model challenges the traditional line between what is legally regulated and what is socially or ethically concerning.

Figure 1 (Sparrow,

2008)

The closely associated theories developed by Malcolm Sparrow are often described as bridging the gap between legal governance and the social dimension of harm prevention.⁵⁵ When Sparrow's model is applied to the analysis presented later in this article, it serves as an analytical tool to contextualise the findings, directly pertaining to the overarching research question. Consequently, when falling in the right category, it is imperative that regulatory authorities, in each national context, do not confine their approach solely to existing legal frameworks but also consider broader forms of oversight governance where necessary.⁵⁶

5. METHODOLOGY

This article employs a multi-methodological approach, combining legal doctrinal analysis with psychological theoretical research and qualitative empirical inquiry.⁵⁷ To answer the first sub-research question, a doctrinal analysis is conducted, serving as the central methodological component of this study. It specifically focuses on the extraterritorial scope of Article 3 of the GDPR and is structured according to the IRAC method. This method provides a systematic framework for identifying the legal issue, stating the relevant rule, applying it to the specific context, and formulating a conclusion.⁵⁸

⁵³ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Engells, T. E. (2010, May). The character of harms: Operational challenges in control. *Security Management*. <https://www.asisonline.org/security-management-magazine/articles/2010/05/the-character-of-harms-operational-challenges-in-control/>.

⁵⁶ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁵⁷ Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Pearson Education.

⁵⁸ Neumann, R. K., Jr., & Tiscione, K. K. (2009). *Legal reasoning and legal writing* (7th ed.). Wolters Kluwer Law & Business.

The doctrinal analysis systematically researches the content of Article 3 of the GDPR, together with other relevant legal provisions and accompanying recitals.⁵⁹ Given the highly contemporary nature of satellite-based data processing, relevant case law remains limited. As a result, this study additionally relies on academic commentary, scholarly literature, and other soft law tools to supplement the gaps that exist within the currently available materials.

Moreover, the analysis examines *the Google Spain case*.⁶⁰ This ruling substantially influenced contemporary interpretations of the GDPR's extraterritorial scope. Particularly in the context of space-based personal data processing, this case's relevance lies in comparable challenges related to jurisdiction and enforceability.

Furthermore, the analysis considers interpretative guidance issued by influential bodies, including the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), which is a crucial institution for interpreting and overseeing the implementation of EU data protection law. The integration of all the elements aforementioned establishes the foundation for addressing the legal dimension of this analysis.

Following this, the Sparrow model is applied to the findings from the prior sections. This helps reveal that the balance between legal applicability and socio-psychological perceptions is either reinforced or undermined by the latter. Thus, this section synthesises and weighs all findings against each other, providing an integrated reflection that suggests future recommendations. It includes recommendations for legal interpretation, as well as alternative measures to be taken when the applicability of the GDPR to space proves insufficient.

Lastly, this study employs semi-structured interviews as a methodological tool to gather more in-depth insights from different experts. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, are valuable for capturing nuanced perceptions, especially in evolving and technically complicated fields.⁶¹ Therefore, to gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter, four interviews were conducted with diverse specialists.

Each of the four interviewees brings a distinct and complementary perspective to the topic at hand. Monique Verdier, the Deputy Chair of Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens (AP), being the Dutch Data Protection Authority (DPA), offers insights from a regulatory and oversight standpoint. Barbara Kathmann, Member of the Dutch Parliament and a member of the Parliamentary Committee on Digital Affairs, provides a legislative and policy-oriented view. Bart Schermer, Professor of Privacy and Cybercrime at Leiden University, brings academic and theoretical expertise. Lastly, Michiel Steltman, former Director of the Dutch Digital Infrastructure Foundation (DINL), adds a perspective grounded in the practical realities of digital infrastructure and technological implementation. Only Dutch experts were interviewed. Nevertheless, all four interviewees may be considered representative of broader EU perspectives, given

⁵⁹ Bhagyamma, G. (2023). *A comparative analysis of doctrinal and non-doctrinal legal research*. *ILE Journal of Governance and Policy Review*, 1(1), p.88.

⁶⁰ Case C-131/12, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD) and Mario Costeja González*, 2014 ECLI:EU:C:2014:317

⁶¹ Luger, E., & Sellen, A. (2016). "Like having a really bad PA": The gulf between user expectation and experience of conversational agents. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 5286–5297). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858288>; Cowan, B. R., Pantidi, N., Coyle, D., Morrissey, K., Clarke, P., Al-Shehri, S., Earley, D., & Bandeira, N. (2017). "What can I help you with?": Infrequent users' experiences of intelligent personal assistants. *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services (MobileHCI'17 '17)*, Article 43, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3098279.3098539>; Binns, R., Veale, M., Van Kleek, M., & Shadbolt, N. (2018). "It's reducing a human being to a percentage": Perceptions of justice in algorithmic decisions. *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '18)*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173951>.

their professional engagement within the Dutch regulatory and legal landscape, which is embedded in the EU framework.

6. DOCTRINAL ANALYSIS

6.1. Framing the Legal Issue

The legal issue is whether Article 3 of the GDPR applies to personal data collected by space-based Earth-observation satellites operated by entities within its jurisdiction. It examines whether personal data breaches involving the transmission or leakage of such data to third parties fall within the extraterritorial scope of the Regulation.

To further contextualise potential risks, the interviewees offer complementary insights. Michiel Steltman emphasises that when personal data falls into the wrong hands, it can give rise to unforeseen risks.⁶² Bart Schermer adds that the rise of AI fundamentally shifts the privacy landscape, as even anonymised data may be re-identified and linked back to individuals.⁶³ Monique Verdier underscores the severity of misuse by referencing real-world consequences, including identity fraud, and, in extreme cases, suicides resulting from reputational damage.⁶⁴ Such harms may stem from the misuse of personal data types, including geolocation patterns or behavioural profiles derived from satellite imagery, particularly when these are enhanced through AI-driven analysis and used to infer identity, monitor movement, or draw sensitive conclusions about individuals. These potential harms underscore the need to examine whether, and to what extent, the GDPR covers such risks.

6.2. Examining Article 3 GDPR: Territorial Scope

The following sections examine the relevant legal provisions and definitions of the GDPR articles, relevant case law, interpretative guidance from the EDPB, and an analysis of the relevant recitals. As a directly applicable EU regulation, the GDPR takes precedence over conflicting national laws, thereby holding a prominent position within the European legal order as a binding instrument of primary legislation.⁶⁵ In general, Article 3 outlines the geographic and jurisdictional conditions under which the GDPR is applicable. Article 3(3) is not addressed in this analysis, as the primary relevance for the discussion lies in provisions 3(1) and 3(2).

6.2.1. Article 3(1): Establishment in the Union

Article 3(1) GDPR states: “The regulation applies to the processing of personal data in the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the Union, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the Union or not.⁶⁶” The provision thus formulates that entities within the EU remain subject to GDPR obligations. This applies even when their data processing activities are carried out beyond EU territory, regulating its applicability extraterritorially.⁶⁷

⁶² Author interview with Michiel Steltman (Former Director of the Dutch Digital Infrastructure Foundation), 19 May 2025.

⁶³ Author interview with Bart Schermer (Privacy and Cybercrime Professor at Leiden University), 19 May 2025.

⁶⁴ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁶⁵ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union., 2012 O.J. C (326)/47. Art. 288.

⁶⁶ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁶⁷ Gil González, E., & de Hert, P. (2019). Understanding the legal provisions that allow processing and profiling of personal data - An analysis of GDPR provisions and principles. *ERA Forum*, 19(4), 597–621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12027-018-0546-z>.

6.2.2. Article 3(2): Targeting or Monitoring in the Union

Article 3(2) GDPR broadens the territorial scope. It states: “This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not established in the Union, where the processing activities are related to: (a) the offering of goods or services, irrespective of whether a payment of the data subject is required, to such data subjects in the Union; or (b) the monitoring of their behaviour as far as their behaviour takes place within the Union.⁶⁸” In other words, this provision prioritises the impact on EU data subjects, preventing parties from evading its protections based on location.⁶⁹

6.2.3. Article 4: Definitions

Article 4 of the GDPR provides key terminological clarifications to gain insight into definitions within these provisions. The most relevant definitions for assessing the applicability to space-based observation satellites are Article 4(1), 4(7), and 4(8). Article 4(1) defines *personal data*. It states: “personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.⁷⁰”

Furthermore, Article 4(7) defines a *controller*: “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.” Lastly, Article 4(8) defines a *processor*: “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.” As clarified in Article 29 Working Party Opinion 3,⁷¹ determining whether an entity qualifies as a controller or processor under EU data protection law is essential for assessing the applicability of the GDPR. These definitions further enable the GDPR to be applied, insofar as the processing involves personal data that can be linked to individuals located within the EU.⁷² While the articles and definitions offer foundational insights, it remains essential to consult supplementary sources to develop a more comprehensive understanding.

6.2.4. Google Spain Case

The case *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos* is a key judgment that offers valuable insights into the territorial scope of the GDPR that can be relevant for assessing its applicability to space-based satellites.⁷³ The case is about Mr Costeja González, who sought the removal of sensitive personal information linked to his name from Google’s search results. Although Google’s headquarters were located in the United States, the Court held that the company was still subject

⁶⁸ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁶⁹ Höglund, W. (2018). *The extraterritorial reach of the GDPR: Exporting data protection law*. Umeå University Publications.

⁷⁰ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁷¹ Refers to EU advisory body that issued influential guidance on data protection prior to the GDPR, only cited in this article where no updated interpretation exists.

⁷² Mondschein, C. F., & Monda, C. (2018). *The EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in a research context* (Chapter 5). In P. Kubben, M. Dumontier, & A. Dekker (Eds.), *Fundamentals of clinical data science*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99771-8_5.

⁷³ Case C-131/12, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD) and Mario Costeja González*, 2014 ECLI:EU:C:2014:317.

to EU data protection law and required it to remove the information.⁷⁴ The CJEU had to decide on the interpretation of “establishment” in Article 3(1).⁷⁵ According to them, the term “establishment” must be interpreted broadly, given that entities based outside the EU can still fall under the GDPR’s territorial scope if they direct their activities toward EU individuals.⁷⁶

In contrast, in AG Niilo Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion, he highlighted the importance of a narrow interpretation of the term “establishment”⁷⁷. He argued that the mere presence of a subsidiary within the EU does not suffice to bring a non-EU company, such as Google Inc., within the territorial scope of EU data protection law.⁷⁸ Therefore, he articulated a limitation on the broad interpretation of the extraterritorial scope of the GDPR, which gained considerable support. Although the CJEU ruled differently on the case, AG Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion remains doctrinally interesting. While not legally binding, AG Opinions carry persuasive authority and are often cited for their detailed legal reasoning and interpretative frameworks.⁷⁹ Jääskinen’s insistence on a narrow reading of “establishment” underscores potential limits on the GDPR’s extraterritorial scope.

6.2.5. EDPB’s Guidelines 3/2018

The EDPB issues non-binding soft law recommendations but holds significant interpretative authority. The EDPB Guidelines 3/2018 describe when the GDPR applies outside the EU, in light of Article 3(1) and 3(2).⁸⁰ In essence, it emphasises that the applicability of the GDPR is primarily determined by the location and legal rights of the data subject.

The EDPB elaborates that “establishment” in Article 3(1) is to be interpreted in a broad sense.⁸¹ They emphasise that the determining factor for GDPR applicability is the existence of operational links, rather than the physical location of processing infrastructure. They state: “The decisive factor is whether the processing is carried out in the context of the activities of the EU establishment.”⁸² This is particularly relevant given that once the criterion for “establishment” is fulfilled, a controller or processor must respect data subject rights as per the articles of the GDPR.

Regarding Article 3(2), the EDPB affirms that the targeting criterion applies when a non-EU entity monitors the behaviour of individuals in the EU.⁸³ The deciding factor is the data subject’s presence in the EU at the time of processing, irrespective of nationality. This furthermore ensures that data subjects in the EU are protected from invasive data practices, even when carried out by entities based outside the EU.⁸⁴

6.2.6. Recital 15: Technology Neutrality

Recital 15 offers additional interpretative insight into the scope and application of the relevant provisions, particularly by emphasising the notion of technology neutrality. Recital 15(1) states: “In order to prevent

⁷⁴ Ibid.

⁷⁵ Ibid.

⁷⁶ Ibid; Frantziou, E. (2014). Further developments in the right to be forgotten: The European Court of Justice's judgment in Case C-131/12, *Google Spain, SL, Google Inc. v Agencia*.

Española de Protección de Datos. *Human Rights Law Review*, 14(4), 761–777. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hrlr/ngu033>.

⁷⁷ Jääskinen, N. (2013). Opinion of Advocate General Jääskinen, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v Agencia Española de Protección de Datos*, Case C-131/12, ECLI:EU:C:2014:317.

⁷⁸ Ibid, para 63.

⁷⁹ Mañko, R. (2019). *Role of Advocates General at the CJEU* (EPRS Briefing PE 642.237). European Parliamentary Research Service. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2019\)642237](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2019)642237).

⁸⁰ EDPB, 2018.

⁸¹ EDPB, 2018, p. 5.

⁸² EDPB, 2018, p. 8.

⁸³ EDPB, 2018, pp.13-15.

⁸⁴ EDPB, 2018.

creating a serious risk of circumvention, the protection of natural persons should be technologically neutral and should not depend on the techniques used”⁸⁵. Thus, the type of technology is secondary to the concern of ensuring the protection of individuals’ personal data. The focus lies on the impact on the data subject, rather than the specific tools or systems through which the processing occurs.⁸⁶

6.3. *Assessing the Applicability*

An initial examination of the content of Articles 3(1) and 3(2) suggests that the GDPR may extend to space-based satellite-derived personal data concerning identifiable individuals within the EU. This is irrespective of the satellite’s physical location in outer space. However, additional analysis is required to determine the full extent of this applicability.

When interpreted in the context of space-based observation satellites, the definitions set out in Articles 4(1), 4(7), and 4(8) can be applied to collected personal data. For example, geolocation patterns or behavioural profiles generated through satellite imagery, especially when enhanced by AI technologies, may fall within the scope of “personal data” under Article 4(1), insofar as they relate to an identified or identifiable natural person. Furthermore, “controllers,” as defined in Article 4(7) of the GDPR, may include satellite operators that determine the purposes and means of processing satellite-derived personal data, such as Maxar Technologies or Airbus Defence and Space. “Processors,” as defined in Article 4(8), can refer to third parties, certain actors on Earth or in space that handle the data on behalf of the controller. These may include image analytics firms or government contractors such as Planet Labs PBC or Maxar Intelligence.⁸⁷

The examined case law confirms that the notion of extraterritoriality should be interpreted broadly, potentially allowing for its application to space-based satellites. However, such an extension may remain somewhat ambiguous. This uncertainty is underscored by AG Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion, in which he advocated for a narrower interpretation of the territorial scope. If a limitation on the interpretation of establishment is already suggested by AG Jääskinen in the terrestrial context, extending the concept to outer space appears even less self-evident. As previously noted, although this opinion lacks binding legal force, it carries significant academic weight and contributes to the interpretative discourse on the scope of the GDPR.

Furthermore, given that the EDPB emphasises that “monitoring” includes observation beyond online tracking, it potentially covers Earth observation technologies. Thus, the Guidelines appear to affirm that the GDPR applies extraterritorially to observation satellites where data subjects are in the EU, or the processing is linked to an EU-based individual. Additionally, the notion of technological neutrality per Recital 15 of the GDPR implies that space-based technologies should also fall within the regulation’s scope; the focus lies on the protection of personal data, irrespective of the means or tools used to process, including space-based observation satellites.⁸⁸

Lastly, it is noteworthy that neither the text of the GDPR nor its recitals makes any explicit reference to satellites or outer space.⁸⁹ This omission makes it difficult to assert with certainty that the GDPR applies to space-based contexts. Especially, as stated in the literature review, given that satellites operate in outer

⁸⁵ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ FlyPix AI. (2025, April 12). Leading satellite image processing companies delivering precision. <https://flypix.ai>

⁸⁸ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

space, their characteristics differ fundamentally from terrestrial data processing. As a result, one can argue that a degree of ambiguity remains, and further clarification from relevant interpretative bodies is needed to determine whether the GDPR may be legitimately applied.

Thus, from a legal positivistic perspective, the text and purpose of the GDPR, especially Articles 3(1), 3(2), 4(1), 4(7) and 4(8), supported by relevant case law, EDPS Guidelines, and Recital 15, suggest that its territorial scope could extend to space-based personal data in observation satellites from EU individuals or people that are in the EU. However, this interpretation is not without legal uncertainty. The absence of explicit references in any of the material to satellites or outer space, coupled with competing views from AG Jääskinen's opinion and other scholars, indicates that such an extension is plausible but currently constitutes a far-reaching interpretation. Moreover, this interpretation is yet to be applied in practice, further contributing to its legal uncertainty. Ultimately, this article contends that further legal clarification, particularly from authoritative bodies such as the EDPB, is essential to solidify the GDPR's applicability to space-based observation satellites.

However, from a normative perspective, considering the concerns surrounding public distrust and fear highlighted in the psychological sections, as well as the emphasis in Recital 15 on ensuring broad and technologically neutral protection, this article argues that the GDPR ought to be interpreted as extending to space-based observation satellites. That is furthermore because, as prior sections state, for European citizens, the GDPR constitutes the most comprehensive privacy framework currently in place, and the importance of safeguarding against associated risks is considerable.

7. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DIMENSION

The doctrinal analysis reveals that the GDPR does not provide undeniable certainty when it comes to the protection of individuals' personal data in the context of outer-space observation satellites. Consequently, the interest of the socio-psychological dimension increases. There remains an open issue as to whether a meaningful balance exists between legal protection and societal concern. However, the literature review of this article demonstrates that individuals express significant discomfort and concerns regarding space-based satellite surveillance and personal data misuse. The interview data complement these findings. For instance, Monique Verdier highlights the overwhelming public reaction to the DPA's call to object to META's use of personal data for AI training, indicating widespread unease and a lack of clarity.⁹⁰ Interestingly, Barbara Kathmann also notes this as an example of a growing unease in public perception.⁹¹ Bart Schermer describes how he sees that individuals often accept tracking, not out of genuine consent but due to limited alternatives, reinforcing a sense of coercion.⁹² In conclusion, there is a clear imbalance: while public concern is high, the law itself remains inadequate.

8. INTEGRATING DIMENSIONS: LEGAL GAPS AND PERCEIVED HARM

8.1. A Disconnect Between Law and Attitudes

The disparity between the legal reality and public concern underscores the urgent need for robust regulatory frameworks to ensure adequate protection of personal data in outer space. The following sections aim to explore ways to restore balance between the two dimensions, while emphasizing that legal clarification is, first and foremost, desirable. When returning to the core of why public trust is low and why regulatory safeguards are necessary, the underlying concern lies in the concepts of potential harm.

⁹⁰ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁹¹ Author interview with Barbara Kathmann (Member of the Dutch Parliament for PVDA/GroenLinks and Member of the Parliamentary Committee on Digital Affairs), 16 June 2025.

⁹² Author interview with Bart Schermer (Privacy and Cybercrime Professor at Leiden University), 19 May 2025.

Legal frameworks aim to regulate and prevent harm, whilst simultaneously, low perceptions of trust often circulate potential harm. Accordingly, the following sections investigate whether an alternative approach to safeguarding against such risks may be warranted. To that end, this study applies the Sparrow diagram to identify which entities, besides GDPR-regulated actors, bear responsibility for mitigating risk and harm, and to reframe the legal and psychological findings in a more integrated perspective. This synthesis ultimately supports the formulation of a conclusion to the overarching research question.

8.2. *Applying the Malcolm Sparrow Framework*

This article employs Malcolm Sparrow's diagram and accompanying theoretical framework as an evaluative perspective to further synthesise the legal and psychological dimensions of the research.⁹³ This allows for an analysis that extends beyond the boundaries of legally governed harm to consider broader societal risks. This study argues that Sparrow's dual perspective is particularly relevant to space-based observation satellites, given their distinctive regulatory challenges and psychological characteristics that do not easily align with traditional legal boundaries. As stated before, the doctrinal analysis of Article 3 of the GDPR demonstrates that while the regulation may extend extraterritorially, its application to satellite-based data collection remains legally uncertain. When applied, personal data in space may lie at the margins, or even outside, the formal legal domain, being the left side of Sparrow's diagram.⁹⁴ However, the risks evidently reside within the sphere of societal harm and are thereby situated on the right side. Consequently, even if the protection of personal data regarding observation satellites does not fall within the domain of established legal regulation, it becomes all the more essential to address the risks, situated on the right side. Precisely because these risks lie beyond the reach of existing legal frameworks, they may warrant even greater regulatory or oversight attention.⁹⁵

Furthermore, Sparrow emphasises the critical role of national supervisory authorities, particularly in addressing risks that fall within the right sphere.⁹⁶ Moreover, he explains that even if these stakeholders are not always legally obligated, they nonetheless carry ethical and practical responsibilities in responding to the risks that emerge. A complementary illustration of this idea is that the Deputy Chair of the Dutch DPA elaborates that she thinks that supervisory bodies have the essential responsibility to not only monitor adherence to certain rules but also to identify and respond to evolving societal risk, especially in areas where legal frameworks may still be underdeveloped.⁹⁷ This statement aligns with the position advanced by Aute Kasdorp, who builds upon Sparrow's framework and argues that, when risks fall within the right side of Sparrow's model, it is ultimately up to the supervisory authority to determine the role it wishes to assume in response.⁹⁸ This indicates that it may not only be desirable in cases of risk, but foremost legally permissible for authoritative bodies to apply their regulatory mandates to other emerging risks.

To situate the foregoing within an exhaustive context, in light of ambiguity regarding the GDPR's applicability, risks to personal data fall inarguably on the right side of Sparrow's model; that is, outside the domain of formal legal regulation. This, in turn, necessitates regulatory attention. Accordingly, it underscores the significance of supervision beyond strictly defined responsibilities laid down in the

⁹³ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁹⁴ Sparrow, M. K. (2008, May 27). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control* [Keynote presentation]. Twelfth Annual Symposium of the Performance and Planning Exchange, Ottawa, Canada. http://www.ppx.ca/download/symposiums/2008/keynote/2008_pp_Sparrow_e.pdf.

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁹⁸ Kasdorp, E.-A. (2022). *Between Scylla and Charybdis: Regulators' supervisory practice in the face of harmful but legal regulatee conduct* [Doctoral dissertation, Erasmus University Rotterdam]. 51–62. <https://reader.ogc.nl/fceec8e51-657d-4280-b033-a42964c2ef9b.epub/>.

GDPR, especially for national supervisory authorities entrusted with wider regulatory and oversight responsibilities.

9. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE TRAJECTORY

Trust in the GDPR as a legal framework in itself is a distinct and valuable topic, but one that would broaden the scope of this article beyond its intended focus. Nevertheless, it remains closely connected to the issues discussed above. Combining these insights may offer valuable perspectives for future research.

In conclusion, this article demonstrates that the protection of personal data in the context of outer space observation satellites holds substantial societal relevance and warrants serious regulatory attention. To explore this theme, the study employs a multi-methodological approach that integrates legal doctrinal analysis, psychological theoretical research, and qualitative empirical inquiry with experts. Its interdisciplinary framework highlights how the potential applicability of Article 3 of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites intersects with public trust perceptions among European citizens, thereby generating a novel and integrative insight not previously explored.

The legal analysis reveals that the text and intent of the GDPR suggest potential applicability to the personal data collected by these satellites. However, the distinctive legal context of outer space, the absence of explicit references to space-based technologies, and the fact that this interpretation has not yet been tested in practice may give rise to certain jurisdictional and interpretative ambiguities. Thus, while plausible, the application of Article 3 of the GDPR to personal data in the context of space-based observation satellites would benefit from further legal clarification by authoritative legal bodies. From a normative perspective, this article argues that outer-space observation satellites should fall under the scope of the GDPR, especially in light of the risks and the regulation's regulatory influence. From a psychological perspective, public perceptions reflect low levels of trust in space-based satellite technologies and the protection of personal data, influenced by concerns over surveillance and a lack of transparency. Therefore, the importance of robust legal safeguards increases.

The application of the Sparrow framework facilitates further integration of the legal and psychological dimensions. It highlights that even if the risks associated with personal data regarding observation satellites fall outside the scope of current legal frameworks, they still warrant regulatory attention. This emphasises supervisory authorities as crucial actors in addressing these societal harms, even in legally uncertain domains. The interdisciplinary character of this study is essential for creating an exhaustive overview, as the societal impact of personal data in space-based observation satellites extends beyond what legal frameworks alone can sufficiently capture.

As highlighted at the outset of this study, personal data breaches are not only on the rise, they are escalating at a global scale. The risks carry serious implications, not only for individual rights but for society as a whole. This underscores the continuing importance of seeking multidisciplinary solutions to address these evolving challenges.

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MODERNIZING THE OUTER SPACE TREATY: ARTICLE IX AND THE LEGAL GOVERNANCE OF KINETIC ANTI-SATELLITE ACTIVITIES

YUG RAMAN SRIVASTAVA¹

ABSTRACT

This paper analyses and evaluates how the *corpus juris spatialis* will influence jurisprudence after ASAT Tests were conducted during the 2019 Indian Mission Shakti operation to increase the risk of systemic harm caused by the resulting debris created from testing. Tracing its inquiry back to India's 2019 Mission Shakti operation, this article critically examines the interpretive flexibility and effectiveness of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST). While Article IV of the OST's arms control focus is limited to Weapons of Mass Destruction, contemporarily, kinetic-based space operations are not constrained by these standards. This article proposes an evolutionary approach to legally interpret Article IX of the OST as a supporting mechanism for reducing orbital pollution and preventing systemic destabilisation in space. This article argues that “due regard” and “prohibition on causing harmful contamination” should be interpreted widely to cover intentional creation of orbital debris, in alignment with the stated purposes of the OST and norm of international law prohibiting harm. This study outlines a new conceptual framework to address the evolving challenges of space security and to develop an applicable regime for state liability and collaborative risk reduction for outer space.

KEYWORDS: Anti-Satellite Weapons (ASAT), Space Debris, Outer Space Treaty, Article IX, Mission Shakti, Space Law, Due Regard, Harmful Contamination.

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1. INTRODUCTION: THE PARADOX OF A CONTESTED COMMONS

Outer space is at a crossroads today. It is a shared resource on the one hand, which pushes science, world trade, navigation, and communication. Conversely, many nations are considering it as a strategic region, in which the major powers can strategise wars. That combination is quite agitating. The primary space regulations were created throughout the Cold War, and they are having a hard time adjusting to the multipolar world and all the emerging technologies.² That tension is most evident in the competition to construct and test anti-satellite (ASAT) weapons, specifically those capable of destroying satellites literally in space³. On 27th March 2019, a historic event took place as India put into orbit Mission Shakti. During that test, India destroyed one of its satellites in low-Earth orbit using a missile. Back home, it was welcomed as an indication of the increasing technological might of India and space power. Far away, however, all were concerned, above all due to the fact that the strike left behind them a ton of space debris.⁴ The experiment brought it out clearly that it is not only the US and Russia, or even China, that can now destroy satellites. The emergence of new spacefaring powers will raise complicated concerns regarding both orbital debris and space security, which will require a comprehensive regulatory framework that does not yet exist. It has now proliferated, raising the spectre of a celestial tragedy of the commons, where the orbital environment, a finite resource, is rendered unusable by the cumulative effect of debris-generating events.

This proliferation of kinetic ASAT capabilities⁵ presents a formidable challenge to the international legal regime governing outer space, which is anchored by the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty).⁶ Drafted with the primary aim of preventing the placement of nuclear weapons in orbit, the Treaty's provisions appear, upon a cursory examination, to be conspicuously silent on the matter of conventional, non-orbital weaponry.⁷ This apparent lacuna has led to a prevailing view among some states that such ASAT tests, while perhaps politically unwise, are not *per se* illegal under existing international law.

This paper contests a narrow interpretation. It will argue that despite the significant and undeniable loopholes in the Outer Space Treaty's arms control provisions, a purposive, systemic, and evolutive interpretation of its foundational principles provides a viable, albeit imperfect, legal pathway to constrain, and potentially prohibit, debris-generating ASAT tests. The central thesis is that while a literalist reading

² Space Strategies. (2025, February 13). *Space law evolution: From Cold War treaties to commercial space regulation*. <http://www.spacestrategies.org/policy/space-law-evolution-cold-war-commercial-regulation/>.

³ Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India. (2019, March 27). *Frequently asked questions on Mission Shakti* [Press release]. https://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/31179/Frequently_Asked_Questions_on_Mission_Shakti.

⁴ China National Space Administration. (2026, January 20). *Chinese capsule damaged by space-junk strike returns to Earth* [Video]. Space.com. <https://www.space.com/space-exploration/human-spaceflight/chinese-capsule-damaged-by-space-junk-strike-returns-to-earth-video>.

⁵ Schmitt, M. N. (Ed.). (2017). *Tallinn manual 2.0 on the international law applicable to cyber operations*. Cambridge University Press.

⁶ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, January 27, 1967). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outer-spacetreaty.html>.

⁷ Pobjie, E., & Azcárate Ortega, A. (2024). *Outer space and the use of force* (UNIDIR Space Security Legal Primer No. 1). United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. https://unidir.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/UNIDIR_Outer_Space_and_Use_of_Force.pdf.

of Article IV of the Treaty appears permissive, a contemporary and contextually appropriate understanding of the obligations contained within Article IX, namely the duties to conduct activities with ‘due regard’ to the interests of other states and to avoid the ‘harmful contamination’ of outer space, can and should be construed to encompass the deliberate creation of orbital debris. To substantiate this claim, this inquiry will proceed in four parts. First, it will contextualise the strategic and environmental peril posed by ASAT weaponry, establishing the urgency of a robust legal response. Second, it will conduct a critical textual analysis of Article IV of the Outer Space Treaty, elucidating the lacuna that enables the development of kinetic ASATs. Third, it will undertake a detailed re-evaluation of Article IX, proffering an evolutive interpretation of its key clauses informed by general principles of international law and the contemporary realities of orbital congestion. Finally, the paper will apply this re-evaluated legal framework to the case of India’s Mission Shakti, demonstrating how an act that may comply with the letter of Article IV can nevertheless be construed as a violation of the spirit and substantive obligations of Article IX. This analysis seeks to contribute to the academic and diplomatic discourse on space security governance by demonstrating how the existing *lex lata* can be dynamically interpreted to address the most pressing threats to the long-term sustainability of space activities.

2. THE STRATEGIC IMPERATIVE AND CELESTIAL PERIL CONTEXTUALISING ASAT WEAPONRY

The weaponisation of outer space is not a futuristic hypothetical; it is a historical reality and a present danger. From the earliest days of the space race, both the United States and the Soviet Union pursued ASAT capabilities as a strategic imperative, recognising the immense military advantage conferred by space-based assets for reconnaissance, navigation, and communication.⁸ This has created an enduring security dilemma: the increasing reliance of terrestrial military forces on satellite infrastructure makes these assets high-value targets in any potential conflict, which in turn incentivises the development of weapons to deny an adversary the use of those assets.⁹

Modern ASAT systems can be broadly categorised into four types: *kinetic* (e.g., direct-ascent interceptor missiles), *co-orbital* (manoeuvrable satellites designed to interfere with or destroy other satellites), *directed-energy weapons* (lasers or high-powered microwaves), and *electronic warfare* (jamming or spoofing signals).¹⁰ While all pose a threat, it is the debris-generating potential of kinetic systems that presents the most immediate and indiscriminate danger to the space environment. The physics of hypervelocity impacts in orbit means that the destruction of a single satellite can create thousands of pieces of debris, each travelling at speeds exceeding 7 mt per second.¹¹ This leads to the existential threat famously conceptualised as the ‘Kessler Syndrome’, a cascading chain reaction where orbital debris collisions create more debris, exponentially increasing the probability of further collisions until certain orbital bands become entirely unusable.¹²

⁸ Harvard International Review. (2020, August 30). *Anti-satellite weapons and the emerging space arms race*. <https://hir.harvard.edu/anti-satellite-weapons-and-the-emerging-space-arms-race/>.

⁹ Moltz, J. C. (2019). *The politics of space security: Strategic restraint and the pursuit of national interests* (3rd ed.). Stanford University Press.

¹⁰ Weeden, B., & Samson, V. (2021, April). *Global counterspace capabilities: An open-source assessment*. Secure World Foundation. <https://swfound.org/counterspace>.

¹¹ Johnson, N. (2011). *The physics of space debris*. NASA Orbital Debris Program Office. <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/>.

¹² National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2023). *Micrometeoroids and orbital debris (MMOD)*. <https://www.nasa.gov/centers-and-facilities/white-sands/micrometeoroids-and-orbital-debris-mmmod/>.

The 2007 Chinese ASAT test, which destroyed the Fengyun-1C satellite, is a case in point; it single-handedly created over 3,000 pieces of trackable debris, much of which will remain in orbit for decades, posing a persistent threat to all operational satellites, including the International Space Station.¹³ The debris from such events does not discriminate; it threatens the assets of the state that created it as much as those of its adversaries and non-belligerent third parties. A kinetic ASAT test is not any other poppycock demonstration of military power, such as firing guns on planet Earth. The effect is larger since it disturbs the space environment, which is in fact a global common that can be used by all. This type of test leaves behind an enormous number of debris that renders space all the more hazardous to everyone who relies on the satellites to provide them with comms, GPS, research, and security.¹⁴ And so, when you think of it that way, the problem is bigger than arm-sizing. It also raises some larger questions of state responsibility, the necessity of international cooperation, and how we are expected to conserve the space environment, which is fundamental to the Outer Space Treaty. When considered from the perspective of shared risk, it becomes necessary to examine the provisions of the Treaty and the opportunities within it that have yet to be fully explored.¹⁵

3. THE LACUNA OF ARTICLE IV: A PERMISSIVE SILENCE ON KINETIC WEAPONRY?

A close reading of the text reveals its origins in the Cold War and demonstrates how it proves inadequate when applied to ordinary kinetic weapons. In short, two megaliths of things are forbidden in the article: “States Parties to the Treaty undertake not to place in orbit around the Earth any objects carrying nuclear weapons or any other kinds of weapons of mass destruction, install such weapons on celestial bodies, or station such weapons in outer space in any other manner.” The Moon and other celestial bodies shall be used by all States Parties to the Treaty exclusively for peaceful purposes. The establishment of military bases, installations and fortifications, the testing of any type of weapons and the conduct of military manoeuvres on celestial bodies shall be forbidden.¹⁶ The first paragraph explicitly proscribes the placement in orbit of nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction (WMDs). The doctrine of legal interpretation, *expressio unius est exclusio alterius* (the express mention of one thing excludes all others), suggests that by specifically enumerating WMDs, the drafters implicitly permitted the placement or use of all other types of weapons.¹⁷ This creates a significant loophole. A conventional kinetic weapon, such as an interceptor missile, is not a WMD. Therefore, its use is not explicitly prohibited by this clause. Furthermore, the prohibition applies to weapons placed in orbit or stationed in outer space. A direct-ascent ASAT, like the one used in Mission Shakti, is launched from the ground on a sub-orbital trajectory. It does not complete an orbit and is not "stationed" in space. Consequently, it neatly circumvents the textual prohibition of the first paragraph. This demonstrates a critical lack of foresight by

¹³ Broad, W. J., & Sanger, D. E. (2007, January 18). China tests anti-satellite weapon, renewing U.S. concerns. *The New York Times*. <https://web.archive.org/web/20120101000000/https://www.nytimes.com/2007/01/18/world/asia/18cnd-china.html>.

¹⁴ King & Spalding. (2024, March 4). *Anti-satellite tests and the growing demand for space debris mitigation*. <https://www.kslaw.com/news-and-insights/anti-satellite-tests-and-the-growing-demand-for-space-debris-mitigation>.

¹⁵ *Supra* note 6, Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty.

¹⁶ *Ibid*.

¹⁷ Byers, M. (2010). The shifting sands of law: A legal-realist inquiry into the status of customary international law. *European Journal of International Law*, 21(3), 531–576.

the drafters, who were primarily concerned with preventing a scenario of orbiting nuclear bombs, not with the more technologically nascent threat of conventional interceptors.¹⁸

The second paragraph of Article IV establishes a more stringent demilitarisation regime, but its application is geographically limited to ‘the Moon and other celestial bodies’. It does not apply to outer space itself – the void between these bodies. The testing of ‘any type of weapons’ is forbidden on the Moon, but not in Earth orbit.¹⁹ This creates a clear legal distinction between celestial bodies, which are reserved exclusively for peaceful purposes, and outer space, where military activities short of placing WMDs in orbit are implicitly permitted. Therefore, a state conducting a kinetic ASAT test can plausibly argue, based on a literalist and formalistic reading of Article IV, that its actions are not in violation of the Treaty. The weapon is not a WMD, it is not placed in orbit, and the test does not occur on a celestial body. This strict, textualist interpretation, which relies on the principle of *argumentum a contrario*, has been the default position for states developing these capabilities.²⁰ It renders Article IV largely obsolete as a tool for constraining the most prevalent contemporary threat to space security. This jurisprudential vacuum necessitates a search for legal principles elsewhere within the Treaty’s architecture – a search that leads directly to Article IX.²¹

4. RE-IMAGINING ARTICLE IX: FROM ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION TO A DE FACTO ARMS CONTROL PROVISION

Article IV stipulates what states are not to do in space, whereas Article IX describes how they are to behave there. The main concept here is to cooperate with other nations, not to delve into one another’s problems, and take care of our planet. The thesis of this paper is that we can establish the legal foundation of restricting the scope of the anti-satellite tests that result in debris by construing the main provisions of Article IX in an incremental and feasible manner. The relevant part of Article IX states: “In the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, States Parties to the Treaty shall be guided by the principle of co-operation and mutual assistance and shall conduct all their activities in outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties to the Treaty. States Parties to the Treaty shall pursue studies of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, and conduct exploration of them so as to avoid their harmful contamination and also adverse changes in the environment of the Earth resulting from the introduction of extraterrestrial matter and, where necessary, shall adopt appropriate measures for this purpose.”²² If a State Party to the Treaty has reason to believe that an activity or experiment planned by it or its nationals in outer space would cause potentially harmful interference with activities of other States Parties, it shall undertake appropriate international consultations before proceeding with any such activity or experiment.²³

4.1. An Evolutive Interpretation of ‘Due Regard’

¹⁸ von der Dunk, F. J. (2018). *An introduction to space law* (4th ed., p. 215). Kluwer Law International.

¹⁹ Arms Control Association. (2025). *The Outer Space Treaty at a glance*. <https://www.armscontrol.org/factsheets/outer-space-treaty-glance>.

²⁰ *Supra* note 6, Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty.

²¹ *Ibid*.

²² Kessler, D. J., & Cour-Palais, B. G. (1978). Collision frequency of artificial satellites: The creation of a debris belt. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 83(A6), 2637–2646. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JA083iA06p02637>.

²³ Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty.

The obligation to act with ‘due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties’ has traditionally been interpreted as a soft, procedural obligation, primarily requiring states to consult with one another in cases of potential interference.²⁴ However, in the context of a congested and contested orbital environment, this interpretation is no longer tenable. In the practice of the International Court of Justice (ICJ),²⁵ the evolution of interpretation is needed to help understand the terms of a treaty based on how we perceive and use something, rather than by using the same definition based on what the person writing it believed back when it was created.

Many treaties, such as *the European Convention on Human Rights* (ECHR),²⁶ are also designed in this same way and are thus referred to as “living instruments”, according to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR).²⁷ Applying this principle, “due regard” must now be construed as a substantive obligation of conduct. The Outer Space Treaty Article IX requires states to exercise “due regard” for the interests of other states that are parties to the Treaty when conducting activities in space, but it is difficult to interpret how the conduct of an activity, such as test of a kinetic anti-satellite (ASAT), which results in the generation of many thousands of pieces of indiscriminately and long-living orbital debris could be consistent with this requirement.

The evidence from actual tests has shown that the debris created by these tests can remain in orbit for decades after the destruction of the satellite, which dramatically increases the likelihood of catastrophic collisions within the region of space affected by such tests and puts at risk both civilian and scientific satellites. The Chinese ASAT test of 2007 against the Fengyun-1C satellite created more than 3,000 trackable debris items and tens of thousands of smaller fragments that are still capable of causing collisions in low Earth orbit. Similarly, the destruction of Cosmos 1408 by Russia in 2021 resulted in the generation of over 1,500 trackable debris items, requiring the emergency evasive manoeuvres of the International Space Station (ISS), thereby endangering the lives of astronauts and international co-operative space missions. These activities create a risk for the entire community of nations, including nations which did not participate in the activities, and erode the cooperative and beneficial principles of the Outer Space Treaty.

In a broader view, the requirement for “due regard” under Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty is much more than simply following the procedure of courtesy; it is also an imperative to act responsibly in a manner that does not significantly or foreseeably diminish the collective space environment while undertaking actions within that environment. If “due regard” were to be construed as only a procedural obligation, the Article would have no real normative value, as it would allow States to comply with it solely by notifying others about their intended actions, while concurrently performing actions which would irreparably damage and destabilize the long-term safety and sustainability of outer space. Such a way of interpreting the Treaty would be inconsistent with the object and purpose of the Treaty, which aims to assure that outer space will be used peacefully, cooperatively, and sustainably in the future as a global common.

²⁴ *Supra* note 6, Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty.

²⁵ International Court of Justice. (1971). *Legal consequences for states of the continued presence of South Africa in Namibia (South West Africa) notwithstanding Security Council Resolution 276* (Advisory opinion). <https://www.icj-cij.org/en/case/53>

²⁶ Council of Europe. (1950). *European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*. https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/convention_eng.pdf.

²⁷ ICJ. (1997). *Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary/Slovakia)* (Judgment). <https://www.icj-cij.org/en/case/92>.

Considered from a systemic point of view, international law has increasingly regarded “due regard” clauses as establishing substantive limitations on unilateral activities that are capable of causing transboundary damage when it is foreseeable. The law of the sea and the international environmental law have similar provisions that have been interpreted to require States to take into account their own entitled rights and freedoms. However, in certain circumstances, States must refrain from performing actions that would cause significant or disproportionate damage to other parties. When applied to outer space, the intentional creation of orbital debris through the testing of kinetic anti-satellite weaponry fails to meet this balancing test since the resulting risk would be widespread, long-lasting, and imposed upon all users of outer space regardless of their consent.

Furthermore, the foreseeability of harm has become a settled issue. There is the ability to accurately forecast potential environmental impacts of activities that generate debris through ongoing scientific studies on the use of contemporary capabilities for tracking and monitoring debris hazards, decades of advancing science to model debris behaviours, and numerous data points from historic incidents of collision avoidance. The issue of “due regard” cannot continue to rely on a narrow, formalized view, nor could it provide States with the opportunity to take advantage of the regulatory silence associated with it while passing on systemic risk to the international community, which would be contrary to both the precautionary principle and the evolving standard of conduct for sustainable operations in outer space. A substantive view of the requirement for “due regard” aligns the requirements of Article IX with the developing norms of what is considered to be “responsible” behaviour and maintains its relevance in a time of increased congestion and contentious uses of outer space by all nations.

Consequently, the understanding of the term “due regard” should not only include a requirement for consultation but should also encompass an obligation not to compromise the integrity of the shared orbital environment through foreseeable significant effects. This understanding will not only establish new prohibitions on State activities, nor will it constrain State's freedom of use, but it will provide a substantive basis to operate under Article IX that is supported by the collective interest in the long-term sustainable use of outer space by all nations. A substantive reading of ‘due regard’ would therefore imply a duty to refrain from activities that foreseeably and significantly degrade the shared space environment.

4.2. Expanding the Ambit of “Harmful Contamination”

The prohibition on “harmful contamination” of outer space has historically been interpreted in a biological or radiological context, for example, preventing contamination of celestial bodies with terrestrial microbes (‘forward contamination’) or of Earth with extraterrestrial matter (‘back contamination’).²⁸ This narrow construction, however, ignores the plain meaning of the term.

‘Contamination’ is the introduction of a substance which has a harmful or poisonous effect.²⁹ Orbital debris is, in essence, a form of physical or particulate contamination of the orbital environment. Its effect is demonstrably harmful, as it renders orbits hazardous and potentially unusable.³⁰ This interpretation is strongly supported by an analogy to general international environmental law, particularly the “no-harm”

²⁸ Committee on Space Research. (2017). *COSPAR planetary protection policy* (G. Kminek, C. Conley, V. Hipkin, & H. Yano, Eds.). <https://cosparhq.cnes.fr/assets/uploads/2019/12/PPPolicyDecember-2017.pdf>.

²⁹ Space Security Portal. (2024, September 3). *Harmful contamination*. <https://spacesecuritylexicon.org/terminology/harmful-contamination>.

³⁰ Shelton, C. (2004). Regulating the space commons: Treating space debris as abandoned property in violation of the Outer Space Treaty. *Chicago Journal of International Law*, 3(2), 715–735. <https://cjl.uchicago.edu/print-archive/regulating-space-commons-treating-space-debris-abandoned-property-violation-outer>.

principle. This principle, affirmed as a rule of customary international law in the *Trail Smelter* arbitration³¹ and the ICJ's *Advisory Opinion on the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*,³² holds that states have a responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause significant damage to the environment of other states or of areas beyond national jurisdiction.³³ Outer space is unequivocally an area beyond national jurisdiction. A debris-generating ASAT test is an activity under a state's control that causes direct and significant harm to that shared environment. Thus, the deliberate creation of space debris can be convincingly characterised as a form of "harmful contamination" proscribed by Article IX. This reading transforms the clause from a niche planetary protection rule into a potent environmental provision with direct relevance to arms control.

5. CASE STUDY: INDIA'S MISSION SHAKTI AND ITS ENCOUNTER WITH THE *CORPUS JURIS SPATIALIS*

India's justification for Mission Shakti rested on two pillars: national security and legal compliance. The Ministry of External Affairs³⁴ stated that the test was conducted "to verify India's capability to safeguard its space assets" and emphasised that it was "not directed against any country". Legally, India asserted that the test was conducted in the lower atmosphere in order to ensure that no space debris would be created. Whatever debris that is generated will decay and fall back onto the earth within weeks.³⁵ Moreover, it maintained that the test did not violate any rule of international law or any treaty obligation to which India is a party. Applying the legal framework developed in this paper, these claims can be critically assessed.³⁶ Under the narrow, literalist approach to Article IV of the Outer Space Treaty, India's position is arguably correct. The interceptor was a conventional weapon, not a WMD; it was on a sub-orbital trajectory and thus not 'placed in orbit', and the test did not occur on a celestial body. From a purely formalistic standpoint, no explicit prohibition in Article IV was breached.

However, when analysed through the lens of a purposive and evolutive interpretation of Article IX, the legality of the act becomes far more questionable. First, consider the obligation of "due regard". Mission Shakti generated an estimated 400 pieces of orbital debris.³⁷ While India claimed this would decay quickly, subsequent tracking by US space surveillance networks indicated that dozens of pieces were thrown into higher orbits, posing a direct threat to other satellites and the International Space Station, and

³¹ *Trail Smelter Arbitration* (United States v. Canada). (1941). *Reports of International Arbitral Awards*, 3, 1905–1965. https://legal.un.org/riaa/cases/vol_III/1905-1982.pdf.

³² International Court of Justice. (1996). *Legality of the threat or use of nuclear weapons* (Advisory opinion). <https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/95/095-19960708-ADV-01-00-EN.pdf>.

³³ United Nations Conference on Environment and Development. (1992). *Rio Declaration on Environment and Development*. https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_CONE.151_26_Vol.I_Declaration.pdf.

³⁴ ICJ. (1996). *Legality of the threat or use of nuclear weapons* (Advisory opinion). <https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/95/095-19960708-ADV-01-00-EN.pdf>.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India. (2019, March 26). *Frequently asked questions on Mission Shakti, India's anti-satellite missile test* [Press release]. https://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/31179/Frequently_Asked_Questions_on_Mission_Shakti_Indias_AntiSatellite_Missile_Test.

³⁷ Subramanian, T. S. (2019, March 28). Debris from Mission Shakti will "vanish" in 45 days. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/science/debris-from-mission-shakti-will-vanish-in-45-days/article26605754.ece>.

were not expected to decay for over a year.³⁸ The act of creating a debris cloud in a commonly used orbital region, without prior international consultation, which foreseeably increased the risk to the space assets of all other nations, is difficult to reconcile with a substantive duty to act with “due regard” for their corresponding interests. It prioritised a unilateral security interest over the collective interest in a safe orbital environment.³⁹

Second, it is necessary to consider the prohibition on “harmful contamination”. India’s assertion that the debris would not be a long-term problem does not negate the fact that the orbital environment was, for a period of time, contaminated with hundreds of high-velocity projectiles. The harm caused by this contamination is the elevated risk of a catastrophic collision. The fact that the contamination might be temporary does not render it permissible, particularly when the potential consequences of a single collision are so severe. By deliberately introducing a large quantity of harmful material into shared global commons, India’s actions are congruous with the definition of harmful contamination, especially when viewed through the prism of the no-harm principle of general international environmental law.

In conclusion, while Mission Shakti may not have violated the antiquated *letter* of Article IV, it arguably contravened the enduring *spirit* and substantive obligations of the Outer Space Treaty as embodied in a contemporary reading of Article IX. India’s claim to be a “responsible” space actor is undermined by an act that contributed to the very problem – orbital debris – that the international community has identified as the most significant threat to the long-term sustainability of space activities.

6. CONCLUSION: NAVIGATING THE LACUNAE TOWARDS A REGIME OF CELESTIAL RESPONSIBILITY

The proliferation of kinetic anti-satellite weaponry, exemplified by India’s Mission Shakti, has exposed the critical deficiencies of the Cold War-era *corpus juris spatialis*. This paper has argued that the primary arms control provision of Article IV of the Outer Space Treaty is manifestly ill-equipped to address the contemporary threat posed by conventional, debris-generating weapons. Its textual limitations and narrow focus on weapons of mass destruction have created a permissive environment for the development and testing of kinetic-kill vehicles.

However, this jurisprudential lacuna is not absolute. This paper has argued that a viable legal pathway for constraining such activities exists within the text of Article IX of the Treaty. Through a purposive and evolutive interpretation, the obligations to act with “due regard” and to avoid “harmful contamination” can be transformed from soft, ambiguous principles into substantive duties of conduct with direct applicability to the problem of orbital debris. Such a reading requires understanding “due regard” as a duty to refrain from foreseeably harming the shared interests of all states in a safe orbital environment, and “harmful contamination” as encompassing the deliberate introduction of hazardous physical debris. This hermeneutic approach is not a radical rewriting of the law, but rather an adaptation of its core principles to the changed technological and environmental realities of the 21st century, consistent with the canons of treaty interpretation and the general principles of international environmental law. This interpretation is, admittedly, not without its challenges. It is a contested reading that runs counter to the established practice of the few states that have conducted such tests. For this evolutive understanding to solidify into a clear rule of customary international law, it requires consistent and widespread state practice (*usus*) and a corresponding belief that such practice is legally required (*opinio juris*). Encouragingly, recent diplomatic trends suggest a growing international consensus in this direction. The

³⁸ Foust, J. (2019, April 2). NASA chief calls India’s ASAT test a “terrible thing”. *SpaceNews*. <https://spacenews.com/nasa-chief-calls-indias-asat-test-a-terrible-thing/>.

³⁹ Hobe, S. (2009). Article IX. In S. Hobe, B. Schmidt-Tedd, & K.-U. Schrogl (Eds.), *Cologne commentary on space law* (Vol. 1, p. 160). Carl Heymanns Verlag.

United Nations General Assembly has passed resolutions, with overwhelming support, calling on all states to commit to not conducting destructive direct-ascent ASAT missile tests.⁴⁰ The ongoing discussions within the UN Open-Ended Working Group on reducing space threats further reflect a collective will to establish clear norms of responsible behaviour. These developments can be seen as the crystallisation of the very principles latent within Article IX.

Ultimately, the international community stands at a crossroads. It can continue to adhere to a rigid, literalist interpretation of a 50-year-old treaty, a path that leads inexorably towards a tragedy of the commons in orbit. Or, on the other hand, it can embrace a more dynamic, purposive, and responsible interpretation that adapts the foundational principles of the Outer Space Treaty to meet contemporary challenges. The choice is not merely a matter of legal interpretation; it is a choice that will determine whether outer space remains a domain of opportunity and exploration for future generations or becomes an impassable wasteland of our own creation. The preservation of the celestial commons demands that we choose the latter.

⁴⁰ United Nations General Assembly. (2022). *Destructive direct-ascent anti-satellite missile testing* (Res. A/RES/77/41). <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n22/801/24/pdf/n2280124.pdf>.

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ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE IN ORBIT: NAVIGATING EIA AND ESG PRESSURES IN THE NEWSPACE INDUSTRY

LAKSHAY BENIWAL¹

ABSTRACT

As private equity and venture capital investment in the NewSpace sector rapidly increases, investors are placing growing emphasis on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) compliance. A key tool in assessing environmental responsibility is the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). However, current EIA frameworks are fragmented, Earth-focused, and inadequate for evaluating the impacts of space activities. This paper examines how this regulatory gap hinders both sustainability goals and investor confidence. Drawing on legal instruments such as the Outer Space Treaty, Moon Agreement and the Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines, the paper advocates for the development of soft-law-based extraterrestrial EIA guidelines. Institutions such as the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee (IADC) and United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) are well placed to lead this initiative. The analysis also considers broader structural issues affecting the implementation of ESG in the space sector, including the resource limitations of space start-ups and the growing expectations of institutional investors. Considering these factors, the paper recommends the introduction of harmonised standards and soft law guidelines as a realistic and commercially viable first step.

KEYWORDS: ESG (Environment, Social, Governance), EIA (Environmental Impact Assessments), NewSpace, Venture Capital.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At the dawn of the space age in 1957, with the launch of Sputnik-1 by the USSR, there was a major push toward the development of space technologies by States across the globe. One of the key drivers for the development of space technologies was getting the technological edge over other States, and it is this reason why an international legal framework was the need of the hour. This motivation was the basis for States establishing the international law principles and the core space law frameworks. These principles are still applicable over 60 years later and continue to emphasize peace and international cooperation.² The primary international legal instrument embodying these principles is the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty)³. Through the end of the 20th century, space activities remained primarily dominated by government entities.

This trend began to shift in the late 1990s as non-state actors became increasingly involved in space activities. While early private initiatives often relied on government support, the early twenty-first century marked a turning point with the emergence of privately driven space enterprises operating more independently.⁴ Technological advancements enabled non-state actors to develop and deploy space technologies, encouraging entrepreneurs to address operational and technological gaps within the commercial space sector. These ventures range from start-ups to established companies, and governments worldwide have responded by introducing regulatory frameworks to promote entrepreneurship and expand access to space. As a result, commercial investment in space operations has grown significantly. There has been a steady growth of private equity and venture capital firms backing NewSpace companies, and in the five years from 2018 to 2023, commercial investments within the space sector increased by 22% annually.⁵ Since 2019, 234 different lead investors have led 347 deals in the European NewSpace sector alone. Most of the investment volume was led by the private sector, consisting of 67.3%.⁶ This shows that NewSpace companies are increasingly and majorly backed by private investors. On one hand, this opens a lot of opportunities for NewSpace companies in terms of access to the global financial market, access to diverse forms of capital investments, etc. However, it also raises the important question of increased scrutiny when it comes to Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) compliance.

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on ESG compliance when evaluating investment opportunities. However, in the context of venture capital, many start-ups are still in the early stages of development and often lack the capacity or resources to adequately address ESG issues, and this holds true for the NewSpace industry as well. Many venture capital funds are placing greater emphasis on ESG criteria to differentiate themselves as long-term, reliable partners for responsible investing focused on sustainability. These venture capital funds also have to satisfy the sustainability-linked “green” requirements of their limited partners or parent investors, thereby triggering this increased scrutiny of

² Schneider, S. (2025). 54: NewSpace and the law. In *Elgar concise encyclopedia of space law*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies* (610 U.N.T.S. 205). <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=0800000280025899>.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Sandhu, N., Harrington, J., & Klein, J. (2023, July 20). *R & D for space: Who is actually funding it?* McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/aerospace-and-defense/our-insights/r-and-d-for-space-who-is-actually-funding-it>.

⁶ European Space Policy Institute. (2024, March). *Bridging the financing gap in the European space sector: Facts & figures*. <https://www.espi.or.at/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/ESPI-Facts-Figures-Bridging-the-Financing-Gap-in-the-European-Space-Sector.pdf>.

ESG criteria while making investments.⁷ This leads to additional compliance costs for NewSpace start-ups, operating in cutting-edge frontier technologies with limited resources and often leads to incomplete compliance or not meeting the required “sustainability” threshold and therefore critically reducing the access to financial markets for NewSpace companies. The current paper seeks to explore this by examining the evolution of ESG principles within venture capital and private equity funds and their application in high-growth, innovation-driven industries such as NewSpace. It will then assess how these factors impact the NewSpace industry by looking at private investment trends and their respective ESG criteria. The second half of the paper will address the legal challenges that arise for NewSpace companies, including compliance with fragmented or underdeveloped regulatory frameworks, specifically with regard to ESG compliance and sustainability obligations. Finally, the paper will offer observations on how emerging companies can navigate these challenges through the evolution of a uniform framework to better support ESG-conscious investment in the space sector. It contends that soft law instruments developed through international coordination bodies such as the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) or Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee (IADC) represent the most feasible pathway for the development of extraterrestrial EIA standards. Therefore, this paper asks: To what extent can Environmental Impact Assessments be adapted to regulate environmental impacts in outer space, and how can such frameworks support ESG-driven investment in the NewSpace industry?

2. RISE OF ESG INVESTING IN VENTURE CAPITAL AND NEWSPACE

In recent years, investors have increasingly prioritized Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations, evaluating not only the profits companies generate but also the manner in which those profits are achieved. This growing interest is supported by market research indicating that, as of early 2018, global sustainable investment assets had reached USD 30.7 trillion – an increase of 34% since 2016 – with Europe representing the largest share of these assets. Additionally, the most recent figures show that more than 3,000 organisations worldwide have become signatories to the United Nations’ Principles for Responsible Investment (UN PRI).⁸ This is also in line with the broader EU Green Deal objectives, wherein the European Commission seeks to (i) reorient capital flows toward more sustainable investments, (ii) manage sustainability risks, and (iii) improve transparency. For the past few years, investors have developed and refined their appetite for sustainable investments. Many investors have shifted from a traditional two-dimensional “risk/return analysis” to a three-dimensional “risk/return/sustainability analysis”. The *Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)*⁹ in the EU has contributed to this phenomenon. For example, the European Investment Fund (EIF) has committed EUR 5.64 billion in equity, including private equity, venture capital and debt finance, for investments that align with the UN Sustainable Development Goals.¹⁰ This points to a gradual and widespread shift taking place across the globe, and in Europe, where investors are keen to invest in projects that align with sustainability goals.

⁷ Bird & Bird. (2022, July 13). *The role of ESG considerations in venture capital investments*. <https://www.twobirds.com/en/insights/2022/global/the-role-of-esg-considerations-in-venture-capital-investments>.

⁸ Botsari, A., & Lang, F. (2020, June). *ESG considerations in venture capital and business angel investment decisions: Evidence from two pan-European surveys* (EIF Working Paper No. 2020/63). European Investment Fund. https://www.eif.org/news_centre/publications/EIF_Working_Paper_2020_63.html.

⁹ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2019). *Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2019 on sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector* (OJ L 317, 9.12.2019, p. 1). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R2088>.

¹⁰ EY. (2023, May 9). *SFDR funds: The power of voluntary assurance*. https://www.ey.com/en_lu/insights/wealth-asset-management/sfdr-funds-the-power-of-voluntary-assurance.

Applying this evolving emphasis on ESG considerations to the NewSpace sector, which is predominantly financed through private equity and venture capital, highlights a significant shift in investment dynamics. As ESG factors become integral to investment decisions, NewSpace companies must align their operations and product designs with sustainability criteria to attract and retain funding. This alignment is not merely a compliance exercise but a strategic imperative, as investors increasingly view robust ESG practices as indicators of long-term viability and risk mitigation. Consequently, NewSpace enterprises are encouraged to integrate ESG principles into their core strategies, ensuring that their innovations contribute positively to environmental and social objectives, thereby meeting the heightened expectations of contemporary investors. Another key aspect of NewSpace companies is that they are often founded by engineers or space enthusiasts who seek to develop new products and services from scratch and require extensive testing, certifications, and resources.¹¹ This can sometimes also translate to many startups lacking the relevant expertise or resources to develop comprehensive ESG strategies. Additionally, the absence of standardized ESG metrics and reporting frameworks can make it difficult for companies to demonstrate their ESG performance effectively. These factors can act as barriers to securing investment, as investors may perceive higher risks or question the company's long-term viability.¹²

3. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS IN NEWSPACE

3.1. Environmental Concerns

Space exploration is a polluting industry;¹³ its environmental impact on the outer space environment and the Earth varies depending on the nature and phase of the activity. Launching a space object raises different environmental issues than extracting resources from a celestial body. In the space industry, there exist two broad forms of contamination, forward contamination and backward contamination. Forward contamination refers to the introduction of terrestrial material into the outer space environment and onto other celestial bodies, such as the Moon, Mars or asteroids. For example, when landing on celestial bodies, it is impossible to ensure the complete absence of chemical and radiological contamination. Rocket exhaust, gas release from activities, and astronauts' life support systems inevitably release chemicals into the outer space environment. By contrast, backward contamination refers to the risks associated with introducing extraterrestrial materials into the Earth's environment.¹⁴ This is also where Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty comes into effect, where state parties are required to conduct all their activities in outer space with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other state parties, and parties must avoid harmful contamination of outer space as well as prevent adverse changes in the environment of the earth, resulting from the introduction of extra-terrestrial matter and, where necessary shall adopt appropriate measures for this purpose.¹⁵ In addition to Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty, Article 7 of the *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Agreement)¹⁶ provides that all State parties must take measures to prevent the disruption of the existing balance of its environment, whether by introducing adverse changes in that environment or by its harmful

¹¹ Hameed, H., & Veneziano, A. (2023). The Space Protocol of the Cape Town Convention: A tool to promote greater commercialisation and private financing in the space sector. In P. De Man (Ed.), *Routledge handbook of commercial space law* (p. 88). Routledge.

¹² Bird & Bird, *supra* note 7.

¹³ Ahuja, V. (2015). Space activities and environmental pollution. In V. S. Mani, B. Bhatt, & V. Balakista Reddy (Eds.), *Recent trends in international space law and policy*. Lancers Books.

¹⁴ Leterre, G. (2023). Environmental protection. In F. von der Dunk (Ed.), *Elgar concise encyclopedia of space law* (p. 88). Edward Elgar Publishing.

¹⁵ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies* (610 U.N.T.S. 205), art. IX. <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=0800000280128cbd>.

¹⁶ United Nations. (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_34_68E.pdf.

contamination through the introduction of extra-terrestrial matter.¹⁷ That said, it is important to note that the Moon Agreement has 17 signatories and has not been ratified by any state capable of human spaceflight; therefore, it has little relevance in international space law.¹⁸

A contemporary example illustrating the environmental implications of space activities is the rapid deployment of large satellite constellations in low Earth orbit. Companies developing global broadband networks plan to launch thousands of satellites, significantly increasing the density of objects in orbit. This raises concerns related to space debris generation, collision risks, and the long-term sustainability of the orbital environment. The cumulative environmental impact of such constellations demonstrates the need for systematic environmental assessments capable of evaluating both terrestrial and orbital consequences of space missions.¹⁹

However, over the past decades, space activities have largely been governed by soft law instruments, including initiatives such as the Artemis Accords,²⁰ the UNCOPUOS Long Term Sustainability Guidelines (LTS Guidelines),²¹ and the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines developed by the IADC.²² These voluntary instruments, of course, do not have the same binding value as an international treaty, but are seeing an increased usage, specifically with regard to sustainability. These soft law instruments can take several forms, such as declarations, principles, standards or guidelines. Several non-legally binding instruments have been adopted to mitigate space debris. In 2002, IADC adopted space debris mitigation standards addressed to space operators. Likewise, the UNCOPUOS adopted in 2007 its own voluntary guidelines to help states and international organisations in the space debris mitigation process. Although these guidelines are voluntary, it can be noted that several states have implemented them in their domestic legal system.²³ As States have the power to voluntarily enforce soft law instruments, they become binding upon governmental and non-governmental entities operating within the space sector. For example, several states have decided to make space debris mitigation measures a requirement for authorisation to conduct space activities, and for some states, the national legislation requires compliance with international standards and guidelines.²⁴

3.2. Evolutions Of Environmental Impact Assessments in Space Governance

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) requirements and licensing regulations are critical components of the space industry's regulatory framework, ensuring that space activities are conducted responsibly and sustainably. These requirements vary across jurisdictions but generally aim to assess and mitigate the environmental impacts of space operations. However, EIA have existed for a considerable period. One of the earliest instances of mandatory EIA procedures in the United States can be traced back to the 1969

¹⁷ United Nations. (1979). *Agreement governing the activities of states on the moon and other celestial bodies* (1363 U.N.T.S. 3), art. 7. <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%201363/volume-1363-I-23002-English.pdf>.

¹⁸ Tronchetti, F. (2024). Moon Agreement: Key provisions. In F. Tronchetti & S. Freeland (Eds.), *International space law in the new space era*. Oxford University Press.

¹⁹ McDowell, J. (2020). The Low Earth Orbit Satellite Population and Impacts of the Starlink Constellation. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/2041-8213/ab8016>

²⁰ National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2020). Artemis Accords: Principles for cooperation in the civil exploration and use of the Moon, Mars, comets, and asteroids (Version 1.0). <https://www.nasa.gov/office/spacepolicy/accords>.

²¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf.

²² Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee. (2007). IADC space debris mitigation guidelines. https://www.iadc-home.org/documents_public/view/id/97.

²³ Leterre, *supra* note 14.

²⁴ *Ibid*.

National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA).²⁵ This act followed from the historic US vs. Canada *Trail Smelter Arbitration*, where obligations under international environmental law that required EIAs were first introduced.²⁶ In the decades that followed, international jurisprudence further developed these principles. For instance, in the *Gabcikovo-Nagymaros case*, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) found a duty to conduct EIAs before proceeding with serious transboundary projects under customary international law as well as treaty and customary obligations to consult and cooperate in the implementation of projects which might affect other states' interests.²⁷ Thereafter, EIAs have been a successful tool to mitigate and understand the environmental impact of developmental activities. However, despite its success in other fields, environmental impact assessment is not a well-established tool in the international law of outer space. As noted *infra*, the national legislation of some spacefaring countries requires an EIA to be conducted for space activities.²⁸ According to Section 11 of the *2018 Space Industry Act* (United Kingdom), the applicant seeking permission to conduct space activities must submit an assessment of environmental effects. This is an assessment of the effect that launches from the spaceport are expected to have on the environment. It should cover air quality, emissions targets, biodiversity, marine impacts, noise pollution, etc.²⁹ Further, the European Space Agency (ESA) conducts Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) rather than EIAs for its missions, and ESA's clean space initiative has developed guidelines to support this process.³⁰ However, the guidelines state that the LCA methodology has been developed to quantify environmental impacts on the Earth's ecosphere and, therefore, impacts to the extraterrestrial environment are presumably excluded from consideration. The LCA studies performed by ESA to date have focused on spacecraft and launchers and have identified the environmental impact in terms of environmental indicators, such as global warming potential, ozone depletion potential, etc.³¹

The current landscape of EIA requirements in the space sector reveals a fragmented and inconsistent approach across jurisdictions, with most regulations primarily focused on terrestrial environmental impacts. While countries like the United States, through NEPA, and the United Kingdom, via Section 11 of the 2018 Space Industry Act, mandate environmental assessments as part of their space activity licensing regimes, these typically address conventional indicators, such as air quality, emissions, biodiversity, and noise pollution, concerns rooted firmly in Earth-based ecosystems. Similarly, the European Space Agency's use of LCAs under its Clean Space initiative, though commendable, is limited to assessing environmental burdens on Earth, explicitly excluding extraterrestrial environments from consideration. This creates a regulatory blind spot, as the cumulative impacts of orbital debris, surface contamination, and resource extraction on celestial bodies remain largely ungoverned. Without a standardized, globally recognised EIA framework that incorporates the protection of the outer space environment, claims of sustainability in the NewSpace sector remain incomplete. For investors

²⁵ National Environmental Policy Act of 1969, Pub. L. No. 91-190, 83 Stat. 852 (1969). <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/STATUTE-83/pdf/STATUTE-83-Pg852.pdf>.

²⁶ United States v. Canada, *Trail Smelter Arbitration* (1938, 1941) 3 R.I.A.A. 1905. https://legal.un.org/riaa/cases/vol_III/1905-1982.pdf.

²⁷ Court of Justice. (1997). *Case concerning the Gabcikovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary/Slovakia)*, I.C.J. Reports 1997, p. 7. <https://www.icj-cij.org/case/92>.

²⁸ Viikari, L., Escobedo, R., Suomalainen, K., Drolshagen, G., & Lehr, C. (2004). Environmental impact assessment and space activities. *Advances in Space Research*, 34(11), 2363–2369. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234520430_Environmental_Impact_Assessment_and_Space_Activities.

²⁹ Stevens & Bolton LLP. (2023, April 4). *UK space law: The Space Industry Act 2018 and regulations*. <https://www.stevens-bolton.com/insights/102ljzu/uk-space-law-the-space-industry-act-2018-and-regulations-key-provisions-for-sp/>.

³⁰ European Space Agency. (2016). *Space system life cycle assessment (LCA) guidelines* (ESA LCA Working Group). European Space Agency.

³¹ Morozova, E., & Pozdnakova, M. (2018). Sustainability in outer space: Legal framework and current practices. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 21(3), 496–518. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1500092>.

increasingly guided by ESG criteria and sustainability mandates, this regulatory gap poses a reputational and operational risk, potentially deterring capital flows into space ventures that cannot credibly demonstrate their environmental responsibility beyond Earth.

3.3. Establishing the Need for Extraterrestrial EIA

As NewSpace enterprises increasingly venture into advanced activities such as in-orbit servicing, asteroid mining, and lunar exploration, they are required to comply with legal obligations under international space law. For example, Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty (OST) mandates that states avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies and conduct activities with due regard to the interests of other states. However, the current global framework for EIAs in space activities is fragmented and primarily Earth-centric, lacking comprehensive provisions for assessing impacts on extraterrestrial environments.³² This regulatory gap poses risks for NewSpace companies, as non-compliance with international obligations could lead to legal challenges. Furthermore, it is now a common and established practice for investors to increasingly prioritize ESG considerations, and the absence of robust extraterrestrial environmental safeguards may deter investment in space ventures. Therefore, establishing clear, internationally recognized EIA protocols that encompass extraterrestrial impacts is crucial for ensuring legal compliance, promoting sustainable space activities, and attracting responsible investment.

Despite the fragmented EIA requirements, two areas of extra-terrestrial environmental protection have been taken more seriously by the international community: space debris mitigation and planetary protection. But other issues of similar importance have been given far less attention. For example, potential contamination by radioactive material, which is often used by landers and spacecrafts³³ has received comparatively limited attention. Radioisotope power systems are widely used in deep space missions to provide electrical power and thermal regulation where solar energy is insufficient. These systems rely on radioactive isotopes such as plutonium-238 to generate heat. Another unexplored issue concerns the protection of environmental resources on celestial bodies. Research highlighted by Prof. Irmgard Ehrenfreund emphasizes that unregulated extraction or contamination of such resources could irreversibly damage scientifically valuable environments or disrupt future exploration efforts. The absence of clear environmental safeguards for activities such as resource extraction, infrastructure construction, or waste disposal on celestial bodies highlights a significant gap in the current regulatory framework.³⁴ In order to achieve a more uniform, comprehensive and inclusive extraterrestrial EIA framework, there are a few technical barriers which need to be addressed⁶ such as how to screen and scope EIAs to ensure that any drastic effects on the extraterrestrial environment are assessed, and are not within the scope of this paper.³⁵ However, hypothetically assuming that these technical barriers have been addressed, better norms for the protection of outer space are an imperative need as States as well as non-state actors increasingly exploit outer space. The amount of pollution and debris that is being generated impairs present and future space activities.³⁶

The author is of the view that soft law instruments have been more effective than binding treaty law in advancing sustainability in outer space. Instruments such as the IADC Space Debris Mitigation

³² National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). *Environmental assessment for space missions: Proceedings of a workshop*. National Academies Press. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/25172/chapter/4>.

³³ Lyall, F. (2010). Planetary protection from a legal perspective – General issues. In M. Hoffman, P. Rettberg, & M. Williamson (Eds.), *IAA cosmic study 2010: Protecting the environment of celestial bodies* (pp.55–62). International Academy of Astronautics.

³⁴ Ehrenfreund, P., Race, M., & Labdon, D. (2013). Responsible Space Exploration and Use: Balancing Stakeholder Interests. New Space. <https://doi.org/10.1089/space.2013.0007>.

³⁵ Morozova and Pozdnakova, *supra* note 31.

³⁶ Gupta, V. (2016). Critique of the international law on protection of the outer space environment. *Astropolitics: The International Journal of Space Politics & Policy*, 14(1), 20–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2016.1148462>.

Guidelines and the UN Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines for Outer Space Activities, despite their non-binding nature, have influenced a growing number of national space laws, demonstrating how soft law coupled with an urgent regulatory need can work in our favour. For example, France and Belgium have taken preliminary steps by referencing extraterrestrial environmental impact assessment requirements in their national legislation. Yet, such instances remain rare, isolated, and lacking in harmonization, leading to many commercial actors falling short of meeting consistent sustainability benchmarks.³⁷

To overcome the current patchwork of regulations, organizations like the IADC are in a strong position to lead the way in shaping soft law guidelines for extraterrestrial EIAs. Just as their work on space debris mitigation has been widely embraced by national space agencies, similar guidance on EIAs could offer a practical foundation for countries to build on. This approach would help bring consistency and clarity to how space activities are assessed for environmental impact, creating a more coordinated and reliable framework. Ultimately, it would support not just the sustainability of space operations today but also safeguard the extraterrestrial environment for the generations that will follow.³⁸

4. CONCLUSION

The NewSpace sector is experiencing an unprecedented surge in private equity and venture capital investment, driven by technological advancements and the growing commercial viability of space-based services. As this industry matures, investors are no longer focused solely on innovation and profitability; they are increasingly aligning their portfolios with ESG principles, seeking ventures that demonstrate responsible practices and long-term sustainability. One of the principal tools that investors use to assess environmental responsibility is the EIA, which helps to identify and mitigate the environmental risks associated with a company's activities.

Existing legal instruments, such as the Outer Space Treaty, recognise the importance of preventing harmful contamination and protecting the space environment, yet they provide limited guidance on how environmental impacts should be assessed in practice. While certain national licensing regimes incorporate environmental review processes, these mechanisms rarely extend to the protection of extraterrestrial environments or the cumulative impacts of space activities. As commercial actors increasingly engage in activities such as satellite mega-constellations, lunar exploration, and potential resource extraction, this regulatory gap becomes increasingly significant. In this context, the development of extraterrestrial EIA frameworks could serve as a practical tool for operationalising environmental governance in space. Importantly, such mechanisms would also help address investor concerns related to ESG compliance, enabling NewSpace companies to demonstrate that their activities align with emerging sustainability expectations.

However, as this paper has demonstrated, the current EIA frameworks applicable to the space sector are fragmented, inconsistent, and largely Earth-centric. While some jurisdictions, such as France and Belgium, have taken early steps to incorporate environmental assessments into their space licensing regimes, these efforts remain rare and lack harmonisation. As a result, the true objective of sustainability, particularly in relation to the extraterrestrial environment, remains unfulfilled. Without a unified and comprehensive approach to EIAs that extends beyond Earth's ecosystem, investors face difficulty in accurately evaluating the environmental impact of space ventures. This uncertainty can reduce investment confidence and limit access to capital for otherwise promising NewSpace companies. To address this

³⁷ Mustow, S. E. (2018). Environmental impact assessment (EIA) screening and scoping of extraterrestrial exploration and development projects. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 36(6), 467–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1500092>.

³⁸ Smith, L. J. (2017). *National licensing practices and regulation of private sector involvement in space*. Secure World Foundation. https://swfound.org/media/50897/smith_nationallicensing.pdf.

regulatory gap, the international community have to develop a more coherent and standardised framework for conducting EIAs for space activities, including their potential impacts on extraterrestrial environments. Such a framework, most realistically developed through soft law mechanisms, could provide practical guidance for states and private actors while remaining flexible enough to accommodate the rapidly evolving nature of the NewSpace sector. Institutions such as the UNCOPUOS and the IADC are particularly well-positioned to lead this effort. Both bodies have already demonstrated their capacity to shape international norms through instruments such as the UNCOPUOS Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines and the IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines, which have significantly influenced national regulatory practices despite their non-binding character.

Building upon these existing initiatives, similar guidelines addressing extraterrestrial EIAs could establish common principles for evaluating the environmental consequences of space missions, including risks of contamination, resource disruption, and long-term impacts on the orbital and planetary environment. Although such standards would initially take the form of soft law, they could gradually influence national licensing regimes as states incorporate them into domestic space legislation and authorisation procedures. In doing so, they would contribute to the emergence of more harmonised international practices governing the environmental sustainability of space activities. For NewSpace companies, this would facilitate better access to global capital markets by demonstrating alignment with sustainability expectations, thereby fostering a more responsible, competitive, and future-proof space industry.

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TOWARDS A UNIFIED APPROACH TO THE GOVERNANCE OF COMMERCIAL SPACE MINING

TATSIANA KLISHCHANKA¹ & ANASTASIA RUTKAUSKAS²

ABSTRACT

The emergence of commercial space mining prospective has exposed a critical difference in approaches to the interpretation of certain core principles in the existing legal framework. This article argues that the current trajectory, characterized by two fundamentally opposed interpretations of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty and the 1979 Moon Agreement, leads to dangerous fragmentation. The first, restrictive approach views commercial resource extraction as a violation of the non-appropriation principle and both the concepts of the “province of all mankind” and the “common heritage of mankind.” The second, permissive approach distinguishes the OST's provisions from the Moon Agreement, justifying granting property rights over extracted resources.

This doctrinal divide has materialized in a patchwork of national laws, creating regulatory competition and undermining the OST's core principles. The article contends that a proactive move towards a unified international regime is necessary to avert conflict and inequality. It analyzes the theoretical underpinnings of the legal debate and its practical implications and evaluates potential pathways to unification. The consideration of these issues emphasizes that forging a single, coherent regulatory approach is essential for the sustainable and peaceful governance of space resources.

KEYWORDS: Space Mining, Equal Sharing, Common Heritage of Mankind, International Space Governance, Non-Appropriation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The commercialization of outer space has transformed a once purely scientific domain into a potential arena of economic competition. Today, human activities in space are featured by the rise of private space companies: what was once a state-only domain is increasingly being reshaped by private ventures like SpaceX and Blue Origin.³ The growing involvement of private actors in space activities has often been described as the beginning of a “new space race,” driven not only by states but increasingly by private investment in launch services, space tourism, and asteroid mining.⁴ What adds urgency to this debate is that space resources such as lunar Helium-3 could potentially meet humanity’s energy needs for up to 10,000 years.⁵ Yet, it is essential to declare that, without robust governance, clear decision rights and accountability, international oversight of environmental and safety risks, transparent data and AI standards for resource assessment, and coordination among governments, private actors, and scientific institutions, resource exploitation could instead trigger conflict, deepen global inequality, and cause irreversible environmental harm.

Advances in technology have made the extraction of extraterrestrial resources from celestial bodies technically feasible, while the emergence of private actors has intensified pressure on the existing legal framework. The 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, OST)⁶ and the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (the Moon Agreement)⁷ form the core of this framework, establishing the principles of freedom of exploration, non-appropriation, and use “for the benefit of all countries” that can challenge unilateral, profit-driven exploitation of extraterrestrial resources. However, the interpretation and interaction of these principles remain deeply contested.

Two doctrinal approaches to the question of space resource exploitation can be identified. The first, restrictive approach argues that the extraction and privatization of space resources by private actors violate international law, particularly the OST⁸ and the Moon Agreement,⁹ which emphasizes that exploitation should be governed by an international regime ensuring equitable sharing. Under this

³ Gomes, J. R., Devezas, T. C., Belderrain, M. C., Salgado, M. C. V., & de Melo, F. C. L. (2013). *The road to privatization of space exploration: What is missing*. 64th International Astronautical Congress. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289635460_The_road_to_privatization_of_space_exploration_What_is_missing.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Xu, F. (2020). The approach to sustainable space mining: issues, challenges, and solutions. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. IOP Publishing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338933560_The_approach_to_sustainable_space_mining_issues_challenges_and_solutions.

⁶ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (1967). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

⁷ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (1979). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/intromoon-agreement.html>.

⁸ This approach is represented, for example, by Lee, R. J. (2012). *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer; Lyall, F. & Larsen, P. B. (2025). *Space Law: a Treatise*. Routledge; Ma, B. & Liu, J. (2021). Realistic Dilemma and Legal Countermeasures against the “Non-Appropriation” Principle in Outer Space Treaty. *Advanced Space Law*, Vol. 7, 45-55.

⁹ This approach is represented by Hobe, S. and Chen, K.-W. (2017). Legal status of outer space and celestial bodies. In R. S. Jakhu & P. S. Dempsey (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of space law*. Routledge; Yun, Z. (2020). A Multilateral Regime for Space Resource Exploration and Utilization. *Indonesian Journal of International Law: Vol. 1, No. 3*, 327–340; Lefeber, R. (2016). Relaunching the Moon Agreement. *Air and Space Law: Vol. 41, Issue 1*, 41-48.

approach, it is supposed that a new treaty regime for governing space resource activity is necessary¹⁰ and a potential model for it can be found in the regulation of deep seabed mining.¹¹ This article not only examines such options but also proposes other solutions for the problem of governing space resource activity in Section 4.

The second, permissive approach distinguishes the legal obligations in the two treaties, arguing that the OST's concept of the "province of all mankind" is broader¹² and does not prohibit commercial use, including commercial use by private actors in the process of privatization – terms which in this article are used interchangeably, unlike the Moon Agreement's "common heritage of mankind." The latter introduces explicit obligations for collective management of resources, while the former is broader and does not prohibit commercial use or require benefit-sharing. This doctrinal divide has materialized in a growing patchwork of national space-mining laws. Several states that are not parties to the Moon Agreement have adopted domestic legislation explicitly allowing private actors to extract and own space resources, while arguing that such activities remain consistent with the OST. Their interpretation relies on distinguishing between the treaty's prohibition of national appropriation of celestial bodies and the permissibility of ownership of extracted resources.

This fragmentation underscores a critical ambiguity in the current legal regime governing the extraction, ownership, and commercial use of outer space resources. Therefore, the international community faces the problem of how to avert a dangerous "first-come, first-served" system. Such a regime would effectively allow technologically advanced states and private corporations to monopolize the most valuable space resources, entrenching existing global inequalities and excluding less developed countries from meaningful participation. It could also incentivize a competitive rush to secure strategic locations, such as resource-rich regions of the Moon, thereby increasing the risk of geopolitical tensions and disputes over access and use. Moreover, without coordinated international rules, unregulated extraction could lead to environmental degradation of celestial bodies and undermine the principle that outer space should be used for the benefit of all humankind.

2. A BATTLE OF TWO APPROACHES: THEORETICAL PERCEPTION OF THE EXISTING LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The existing legal framework on the issue of exploitation of natural resources in outer space is formed primarily through the OST and the Moon Agreement. The number of states parties to these treaties differs greatly. The OST has been ratified by over 110 countries, including all the major space powers. No state has ever withdrawn, nor has any amendment been proposed.¹³ The Moon Agreement is a multilateral treaty opened for signature in 1979 following negotiations within the UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS).¹⁴ It currently has only 17 States Parties, and none of the major space-faring nations has ratified it. Notably, Saudi Arabia withdrew from the Moon Agreement in 2023, likely to facilitate the pursuit of commercial activities.¹⁵ While the treaty is legally binding on its parties,

¹⁰ Tronchetti, F. (2009). *The exploitation of natural resources of the Moon and other celestial bodies: A proposal for a legal regime* (Studies in Space Law, Vol. 4). Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.

¹¹ Masson-Zwaan, T. & Sundahl, M. J. (2024). National and international norms towards the governance of commercial space resource activity. In L. J. Smith, I. Baumann & S.-G. Wintermuth (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of commercial space law*. Routledge.

¹² Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11; Byers, M. & Boley, A. (2023). *Who Owns Outer Space? International Law, Astrophysics and the Sustainable Development of Space*. Cambridge University Press.

¹³ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

¹⁴ Kopal, V. (2010). *The Progressive Development of International Space Law by United Nations and its Present System*. Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law.

¹⁵ Wedenig, S.-M., & Nelson, J. W. (2023, 26 January). The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread? Institute of Air & Space Law, McGill University. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

its limited ratification weakens its perceived legitimacy and broader authority within the international community, particularly because key actors with the technological and economic capacity to exploit space resources are not bound by its provisions.

Presumably, this difference in the number of parties is due to the scope of the obligations established by these treaties. Some of the provisions of the Moon Agreement might become a legal barrier to resource extraction in space. In particular, Article 11 declares the Moon and its natural resources the “common heritage of mankind” and requires the establishment of an international regime to govern resource exploitation. This regime is expected to ensure the orderly development of resources, equitable sharing of benefits among states, and the prevention of monopolization. Additionally, the agreement requires international oversight of activities, environmental protection of the lunar environment, and the sharing of scientific information. For example, Article 11(5)-(7) calls for the establishment of an international regime to govern the exploitation of lunar natural resources and to ensure equitable sharing of benefits. Article 7(1) requires states to take measures to prevent disruption of the existing balance of the lunar environment and avoid harmful contamination. Furthermore, Article 6(1) encourages the sharing of scientific results obtained from lunar exploration with the international community. For private actors and technologically advanced states, these provisions could introduce regulatory uncertainty, limit exclusive control over extracted resources, and potentially require redistribution of economic benefits.¹⁶ However, certain obligations contained in the OST are also sometimes interpreted as limiting the possibility of exploiting space's natural resources.

In particular, Article I provides that the exploration and use of outer space shall be carried out “for the benefit and in the interests of all countries” and that outer space is the “province of all mankind,” which some scholars interpret as implying a requirement of equitable access or benefit-sharing. Article II prohibits national appropriation of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, by claims of sovereignty, use, or occupation, raising questions about whether exclusive control over resource-rich areas could amount to *de facto* appropriation. Additionally, Article IX requires states to conduct activities with due regard to the interests of other states and to avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies, potentially limiting large-scale extraction activities that could interfere with other missions or damage the space environment.¹⁷

Thus, there are two approaches to the issue of compatibility of resource exploitation with the existing legal framework. Under the first, strictest approach, it is argued that the OST itself prohibits resource extraction in space.¹⁸ The second one focuses on the difference between the scope of obligations established by the OST and the Moon Agreement.¹⁹ Its proponents consider that only those states that have signed the Moon Agreement are bound by a number of obligations regarding space mining, while the OST does not address this issue.²⁰

To examine these two approaches, it is necessary to refer to the relevant provisions of the OST and the Moon Agreement. Three key issues will be: 1) the concepts of “the province of all mankind” and “common heritage of mankind”; 2) the principle of non-appropriation and its relevance to the exploitation of natural resources in outer space; 3) an obligation to take into account the corresponding interests of other states.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Lee, *supra* note 8.

¹⁹ Hobe & Chen, *supra* note 9.

²⁰ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

2.1. The concepts of “the province of all mankind” and “common heritage of mankind”

Article I(2) of the OST secures the freedom of exploration and use of outer space, freedom of access to all areas of celestial bodies and freedom of scientific investigation. ‘Freedom’ in this sense means that any entity that benefits from freedom does not need to seek permission to perform these activities from other governments.²¹

Entities entitled to this freedom are primarily states and, in accordance with Article XIII of the OST, international intergovernmental organizations. However, access by individuals, non-governmental organizations, and private enterprises is also possible.²² Conditions of these private actors’ access are established in Article VI of the OST, according to which states are obliged to issue authorization for activities of non-governmental entities in outer space and supervise them.

However, this freedom, secured by Article I(2), is not unlimited. Article I(1) of the OST means that the exploration and use of outer space, being the “province of all mankind,” is not aimed at serving only the interests of those states that have the technological capability to explore and utilize outer space, but those of all states, no matter what their degree of economic and scientific development is.²³

The Moon Agreement's regime differs from the general regime established by the OST. This difference is primarily reflected in Article 11(1) of the Moon Agreement, which introduces the concept of “the common heritage of mankind.” This concept, which is also applied to the resources of the seabed,²⁴ implies not only a prohibition on the appropriation of resources, but also the creation of an international regime for the management of these resources in the interests of all states, which is required by Article 11(5). Within the future framework of such a regime, the procedure and conditions for states to gain access to natural resources will be provided.

Thus, there are two different concepts of the “province of all mankind” and the “common heritage of mankind.” These concepts were always interpreted differently by developing countries (states which, unlike space-faring nations, have no relevant space capabilities and programmes)²⁵ and major space-faring states. For example, the US understood “common heritage of mankind” and “the province of all mankind” to be indistinguishable and, as such, they were considered an expansion of the principle of *res communis*, which means that something may not become the subject of appropriation by states.²⁶

For developing states, the “province of all mankind” principle meant that all nations had vested rights in common resources and should be shared equitably among them.²⁷ This brings the interpretation of the concept “province of all mankind” closer to the “common heritage of mankind” enshrined in the Moon Agreement. Therefore, both the US and developing countries have tended to mix the scope of obligations under these provisions, but only in different directions.

Some scholars take a position close to that expressed by developing states. They interpret the provision on the “province of all mankind” in the way that all states have the right to enjoy the benefits derived from space activities and should establish how to share them among all nations.²⁸

²¹ Hobe, S., Schmidt-Tedd, B. & Schrogl, K.-U. (Eds.). (2017). *Cologne commentary on space law, Volume I: Outer Space Treaty*. Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag.

²² Ibid.

²³ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

²⁴ See Art. 136 of UNCLOS provided that “The Area and its resources are the common heritage of mankind.” https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

²⁵ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd & Schrogl, *supra* note 21.

²⁶ Gabrynowicz, J. I. (1992). The “Province” and “Heritage” of Mankind Reconsidered: A New Beginning. *Lunar and Planetary Institute*, 691-695. https://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1992lpsa.conf.691G/0000691_000.html.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

This line of thought is also supported by the interpretation of the “province of all mankind” concept in accordance with other provisions of the OST. Even if the “province of all mankind” was not designed to lay down specifics of the distribution or sharing of the benefits and products derived from activities carried out in outer space, nor did it create an international entity charged with the power to make such distribution, this fact does not affect the obligatory nature of the concept.²⁹ The provisions of Article I(1) should be interpreted to mean that states should comply with their duty to carry out the exploration and use of outer space in the interest and for the benefit of all, through a voluntary sharing process and international cooperation.³⁰

Proponents of another approach, which is close in its results to what is expressed by major space-faring states, consider debatable the proper obligatory nature of the provision laid down in Article I(1) of the OST. It is formulated rather vaguely and can give the impression that it was meant to establish only general principles with no legally binding force.³¹ For example, Gabrynowicz argues that the “province of all mankind” provision of the OST is declaratory in nature and not a specific legal maxim, as is well supported in the legal literature.³²

However, analysis of the wording of the OST article shows that the “province” concept covers different activities. In general terms, this provision means that the exploration and use of outer space, being the “province of all mankind,” is not aimed at serving only the interests of those states that have the technological capability to explore and utilize outer space, but those of all states, no matter what their degree of economic and scientific development.³³ In contrast, the wording of the Moon Agreement demonstrates that “common heritage” refers to objects and resources. This difference in the meaning of the two concepts cannot be ignored. Thus, the interpretations which do not take this difference into account should not be accepted.

2.2. Non-appropriation principle

Article II of the OST establishes the principle of non-appropriation, which is reaffirmed by Article 11(2) of the Moon Agreement. However, neither provision specifies whether extracting and commercializing resources of celestial bodies can be in line with the principle.³⁴ It is noteworthy that Article II of the Outer Space Treaty has attained the status of customary international law; accordingly, even States that have not ratified the Treaty are expected to comply with its provisions.

The provisions containing the “prohibition of appropriation” clause may be interpreted in a literal manner. This position is based on the drafting history of the OST. The declarations of states made in response to draft Article II suggest that their intent was to exclude any possibility of acquiring property rights in outer space.³⁵

Moreover, proponents of this approach argue that the OST does not distinguish between celestial bodies and their resources, and, therefore, the resources of celestial bodies should be subject to the same prohibition of appropriation as the celestial bodies themselves.³⁶ They support this conclusion by citing Article 11 of the Moon Agreement, historically adopted as a development of the OST. As for the subjects, which claims are prohibited, Jakhu and Buzdugan stress that Article II must be understood to prohibit all

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Gabrynowicz, *supra* note 26 at 692.

³³ Tronchetti, F. (2015). Legal aspects of space resource utilization. In F. von der Dunk & F. Tronchetti (Eds.), *Handbook of space law*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

³⁵ Gorove, S. (1971). Limitations on the principles of freedom of exploration and use in outer space: Benefits and interests. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Colloquium on the Law of Outer Space*, 74-78.

³⁶ Ibid.

forms of appropriation, governmental or private, since allowing private claims would undermine the treaty's purpose.³⁷ This interpretation was later confirmed by legal scholars, who declared private property claims on celestial bodies legally void.³⁸

Other scholars insist on a narrow interpretation of the provisions of the OST according to which “a distinction can be drawn between the appropriation of a celestial body as a whole, and the appropriation of resources that have been extracted from it.”³⁹ It means that only a celestial body, as a whole, cannot be appropriated. Some scholars also suggest that the prohibition of national appropriation in Article II primarily applies only to states.⁴⁰ Interpreting it this way, private actors may gain property rights for resources in space.

The position of certain states may be found due to their participation in certain instruments, for example, in the Artemis Accords signed by 56 states. Section 10 of the Accords addresses space resource activity specifically by establishing that the extraction of space resources does not violate the ban on national appropriation under Article II of the OST. Therefore, states participating in the Artemis Accords support the conclusion that the non-appropriation principle does not prohibit the exploitation of space's natural resources.

2.3. The principle of due regard

In addition, Article IX of the OST obliges states to conduct activities in space, taking into account the corresponding interests of other states. In this regard, it establishes the mechanism of consultation. The principle of due regard “functions as a limitation to the freedom of exploration and use of outer space” provided for in Article I(2) of the OST.⁴¹ In this perspective, the freedom to use outer space means that a state is entitled to undertake activities that would not threaten the activities of other states.⁴² Thus, its wording and drafting history show that this clause was intended to prevent harmful interference, rather than to prohibit lawful operations.

Therefore, Article IX is procedural rather than prohibitive: it cannot be interpreted as a substantive restriction on resource extraction. As long as a state's resource-extraction activities are carried out with reasonable precautions and prior consultations where relevant, they remain consistent with Article IX.

3. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE AMBIGUITY IN APPROACHES

When it comes to the attitude of states toward the differences in approaches, those states that possess the technical capabilities for space mining will most likely take the least burdensome approach. This trend is also reflected in some states' national legislation. However, such a position entails dangerous practical consequences and is likely to undermine the effectiveness of the existing legal framework, giving it an interpretation that effectively deprives the provisions of their purpose.

³⁷ Jakhu, R., & Buzdugan, M. (2006). *The Role of Private Actors: Commercial Development of the Outer Space Resources, Including Those of the Moon and other Celestial Bodies: Economic and Legal Implications*. Workshop Proceedings: Workshop Convened at McGill University's Institute of Air & Space Law.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ de Zwart, M., Henderson, S. & Neumann, M. (2023). Space resource activities and the evolution of international space law. *Acta Astronautica*, 211, 155–162, at 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.06.009>.

⁴⁰ Harris, D. J. (2004). *Cases and materials on international law*. Sweet & Maxwell.

⁴¹ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd & Schrogl, *supra* note 21 at 568.

⁴² Ibid.

3.1 *An overview of states' approach to the OST*

Some national laws, such as the 2015 U.S. *Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*⁴³ and the 2017 *Luxembourg Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources*,⁴⁴ attempt to grant property rights to extracted resources. These states are not parties to the Moon Agreement but ratified the OST and most likely want to be secured by the “freedom” it provides. However, Xu emphasizes that the OST only clearly protects scientific investigation, not commercial exploitation.⁴⁵ Moreover, Article I’s mandate that space activities be conducted “for the benefit of all countries” is legally binding, yet its vague wording leaves benefit-sharing dependent on a state’s good faith.

This tension ultimately hinges on the very question of how Article I of the OST is interpreted in relation to Article II: whether the “use” permitted under Article I extends to the extraction and commercial sale of extraterrestrial resources. If so, national laws that recognize ownership of mined materials could arguably remain compatible with the OST. If not, such activities risk constituting indirect appropriation, undermining the non-appropriation principle that lies at the core of international space law. The unresolved nature of this issue has become the central legal fault line between proponents of open commercial exploitation and advocates of collective governance.

A textualist approach to this debate reads Article I and II strictly, concluding that any activity leading to ownership claims, directly or indirectly, is prohibited. This view, endorsed by Jakhu and Buzdugan, treats “use” as limited to exploration, research, and non-exclusive activities.⁴⁶ By contrast, a teleological or purpose-driven interpretation focuses on the OST’s objective of ensuring outer space is used for the benefit of all countries. Under this reasoning, if commercial exploitation is conducted transparently and its benefits are shared, it may still align with the OST’s spirit. A pragmatic perspective, increasingly reflected in national laws, argues that since space activities are now technologically and economically feasible, law must adapt to enable sustainable commercial use. The challenge, then, lies in reconciling these approaches to balance legal continuity with evolving realities of space commerce. This interpretive pluralism mirrors broader tensions in international law between stability and flexibility.

3.2 *The impact of the Moon Agreement*

With around 16,000 near-Earth asteroids considered easily accessible, space has become an increasingly attractive prospect for resource extraction and an additional source of minerals and materials.⁴⁷ Once states realized the realistic prospects of exploitation, the Moon Agreement was adopted. It sought to achieve a compromise by reaffirming the freedom of exploration and use of the Moon while committing parties to establish an international regime to govern the exploitation of lunar natural resources once such exploitation became feasible.⁴⁸

However, the Moon Agreement failed to gain broad adherence; few major spacefaring nations have ratified it.⁴⁹ As a result, several states have opted to develop their own national frameworks for space resource utilization, such as the United States, Luxembourg, the United Arab Emirates, and Japan. As Masson-Zwaan notes, rather than a patchwork of national laws, a unified international regime would be preferable to avoid legal fragmentation. She further argues that if ownership of space resources was

⁴³ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, Pub. L. No. 114-90, 129 Stat. 704 (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/114/plaws/publ90/PLAW-114publ90.pdf>.

⁴⁴ Grand Duchy of Luxembourg. (2017). *Law on the exploration and use of space resources* (Law of 20 July 2017). <https://space-agency.public.lu/dam-assets/publications/2017/07/Law-on-the-exploration-and-use-of-space-resources-2017.pdf>.

⁴⁵ Xu, *supra* note 5.

⁴⁶ Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁴⁷ Casey, J. P. (2019, March 18). *A history of space mining: The future of resource extraction*. *Mining Technology*. <https://www.mining-technology.com/features/history-of-space-mining/>.

⁴⁸ Kopal, *supra* note 14.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*.

inherently illegal under the OST, the adoption of the Moon Agreement would make no sense, since that treaty explicitly contemplates the use and potential ownership of such resources.⁵⁰

3.3 The patchwork of national laws with dangerous consequences

Contemporary national frameworks build upon this expansive interpretation of the OST, seeking to legitimize private property rights through domestic legislation. National measures such as the U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act (2015) and Luxembourg's Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources (2017) both recognize ownership of extracted extraterrestrial materials, granting private entities the right to "possess, own, transport, use, and sell" resources they obtain in space.⁵¹ These laws exemplify an emerging trend of unilateral regulation, one that risks bypassing the collective governance framework envisioned by the Moon Agreement. Supporters claim that these statutes simply operationalize the OST's guarantee of the "free use" of outer space, while critics view them as a form of indirect appropriation that undermines the non-appropriation principle and exacerbates normative fragmentation in space law.⁵²

By consolidating their regulatory power at the national level, these states not only enable commercial actors but also challenge the international community to clarify where "use" ends and "appropriation" begins. The issue thus reflects a broader tension between state sovereignty, private enterprise, and the global commons ethos that underpins international space law.

National legislation on space resources has emerged unevenly across jurisdictions. The United States took the lead with its 2015 *Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*,⁵³ explicitly allowing private ownership of extracted resources.⁵⁴ Luxembourg followed in 2017, motivated by its ambition to become a hub for "NewSpace" investment, offering a licensing regime and legal certainty for companies.⁵⁵ The United Arab Emirates adopted its 2019 *Space Activities Law*,⁵⁶ balancing commercial incentives with adherence to international obligations, requiring state authorization and supervision of private missions.⁵⁷ Japan's Space Resources Act (2021) similarly permits resource utilization but embeds it within a state approval framework.⁵⁸ These laws collectively signal a regulatory trend toward nationalization of space governance, where domestic regimes fill the vacuum left by the absence of an international authority. Yet, their divergence raises concerns about forum shopping and regulatory competition; companies might relocate to jurisdictions offering the most permissive terms. Scholars such as Masson-Zwaan and

⁵⁰ Masson-Zwaan, T. L. (2024). Some thoughts on the future of space law. In C.-J. Cheng (Ed.), *New trends in international law: Festschrift in Honour of Judge Hisashi Owada*, 377–394. Brill | Nijhoff.

⁵¹ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, *Pub. L. No. 114-90*, 129 Stat. 704 (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262/text/pl>; Luxembourg. (2017, July 20). *Law of 20 July 2017 on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources*. Journal Officiel du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg, A–No. 674, 1–7. https://space-agency.public.lu/en/agency/legal-framework/law_space_resources_english_translation.html.

⁵² Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra note 37*; Nasr, M., Hoffman, J., Masson-Zwaan, T., Rapp, D. & Newman, D. (2023, March 2). A policy framework for sustainable and equitable space resource utilization. SSRN. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4375679.

⁵³ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, *Pub. L. No. 114-90*, 129 Stat. 704 (2015). <https://www.congress.gov/114/plaws/publ90/PLAW-114publ90.pdf>.

⁵⁴ U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, *supra note 51*.

⁵⁵ Luxembourg, *supra note 51*.

⁵⁶ United Arab Emirates. (2019). Federal Law No. 12 of 2019 regulating the space sector (English translation). <https://www.moj.gov.ae/assets/2020/Federal%20Law%20No%2012%20of%202019%20on%20THE%20REGULATION%20OF%20THE%20SPACE%20SECTOR.pdf.aspx>.

⁵⁷ United Arab Emirates. (2019). *Federal Law No. (12) of 2019 on the Regulation of the Space Sector*. <https://www.moj.gov.ae/assets/2020/Federal%20Law%20No%2012%20of%202019%20on%20THE%20REGULATION%20OF%20THE%20SPACE%20SECTOR.pdf.aspx>.

⁵⁸ Japan. (2021). *Act on Promotion of Business Activities Related to the Exploration and Development of Space Resources (Act No. 76 of 2021)*. Japanese Law Translation. <https://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/en/laws/view/4332/en>.

Tronchetti warn that such fragmentation risks creating a de facto property regime in outer space, driven by market logic rather than multilateral consensus.⁵⁹

Proponents of national resource laws argue that the OST permits “use” of resources without restriction. However, as Jakhu and Buzdugan emphasize, private entities do not enjoy autonomous rights under international law, they can only act under state authorization and continuous supervision.⁶⁰

This tension also plays out in practice: new private actors (e.g., Planetary Resources, Deep Space Industries) pursue asteroid mining projects, yet face serious barriers in law, technology, and economics, particularly the “lack of details for private missions” in the OST.⁶¹ Investors demand property rights guarantees before committing capital, but such guarantees currently conflict with international non-appropriation rules.⁶²

Xu sharpens this critique by identifying three key risks of a laissez-faire approach: 1) conflicts between states: a “first come, first served” system could trigger waste, disorder, and even militarization; 2) inequalities in benefit-sharing: spacefaring nations may accumulate disproportionate gains, while developing countries are excluded; 3) environmental contamination: activities could spread hazardous waste, debris, or even biological material, harming both outer space and Earth environments.⁶³

4. HOW TO AVOID THE NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES?

In light of the presented doctrinal and practical approaches, the more widespread interpretation is that the OST does not establish any significant restrictions on the extraction of natural resources in space. Given that most of the states have signed the OST but not the Moon Agreement, some complicated problems arise. These include mining activities falling into a regulatory gray area, the ineffectiveness of some provisions of the Moon Agreement and even the OST, and the issue of a fragmented approach to the exploitation of natural resources in the national law of various states.

The doctrinal disagreement between restrictive and permissive interpretations of the OST not only shapes legal theory but also directly influences the policy options discussed in Section 3. Each proposed solution reflects an attempt to reconcile these competing interpretations. For example, proposals for universal adoption or amendment of the Moon Agreement largely reflect the approach, which emphasizes collective governance and equitable benefit-sharing. By contrast, reliance on national legislation or soft-law mechanisms aligns more closely with the permissive interpretation that allows commercial resource extraction within the existing framework of the OST. Consequently, the feasibility of the solutions discussed below depends largely on which interpretation of the current legal regime ultimately prevails.

4.1. Universal adoption of the Moon Agreement

The first one is to adopt the Moon Agreement universally and, most importantly, agree on the parameters for the exploitation of natural resources in space. The key to this will be the creation of a detailed regime, as required by Article 11(5), as otherwise, such a measure would be incomplete.

⁵⁹ Nasr, Hoffman, Masson-Zwaan, Rapp, & Newman, *supra* note 52; Tronchetti, *supra* note 10.

⁶⁰ Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁶¹ Gomes, Devezas, Belderrain, Salgado, & de Melo, *supra* note 3 at 4-5.

⁶² Jakhu & Buzdugan, *supra* note 37.

⁶³ Xu, *supra* note 5.

At first glance, this option allows for the most consistent regulation, promoting a cohesive and coordinated international approach. However, even the states parties are in no hurry to implement the provisions of the Moon Agreement. Although they have thus committed to reaching an international agreement to govern commercial mining activities, it is unclear whether this means that no commercial activity can take place before such an agreement is in place⁶⁴. A Joint Statement was issued by the States Parties in 2008, proclaiming that the “common heritage of mankind” principle as embodied in the treaty does not constitute an obstacle to space mining initiatives⁶⁵.

Furthermore, the current trend regarding the Moon Agreement is that states (especially major space-faring nations) are not becoming parties to it and are even withdrawing from this treaty.⁶⁶ In this regard, the prospect of the Moon Agreement achieving at least the same level of acceptance as the OST does not currently appear realistic.

However, despite counterarguments regarding this option, the Moon Agreement remains a valid treaty directly addressing the issue of space resources, which must be taken into account. Furthermore, the interpretation given to it may not be final. The parties themselves can influence the interpretation of the treaty and, by subsequent agreement, modify this interpretation, making it more relevant and prudent in terms of “permissiveness.”

4.2. *The guidance of other regimes*

Given these unresolved tensions, scholars and policymakers have looked to other international regimes for guidance. Debates over the governance of space resources often turn into analogies with existing regimes for areas beyond national jurisdiction. One of the most frequently invoked examples is the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)*⁶⁷ and its regulation of deep seabed mining.⁶⁸ Under UNCLOS Part XI, the resources of the seabed beyond national jurisdiction are declared the “common heritage of mankind,” and their exploration and exploitation are managed through the International Seabed Authority (ISA).⁶⁹ This body licenses mining activities, ensures benefit-sharing, and imposes environmental safeguards. Proponents argue that a similar model could be applied to outer space, where an international institution would coordinate licensing and guarantee that commercial exploitation does not lead to monopolization or inequitable distribution of benefits⁷⁰. Critics, however, note that the ISA regime has been politically contested and bureaucratically heavy, leading some spacefaring states to resist importing it wholesale into space law.⁷¹

Another relevant analogy is the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS). The 1959 *Antarctic Treaty*⁷² in Article IV declares Antarctica a demilitarized zone dedicated to peaceful purposes and scientific research, suspending rather than resolving sovereignty claims. It also guarantees freedom of scientific investigation

⁶⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ Wederlig, S.-M. & Nelson, J. W. (2023, January 26). *The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread?* McGill Institute of Air and Space Law. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

⁶⁷ United Nations. (1982). *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea*. United Nations. https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

⁶⁸ Tronchetti, *supra* note 10; Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

⁶⁹ International Seabed Authority. (2023). *Just and equitable management of the common heritage of humankind*. In *Secretary-General annual report 2023*. https://www.isa.org/jm/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/ISA_Secretary_General_Annual_Report_2023.pdf.

⁷⁰ Lodge, M. W. (2013). *The common heritage of mankind* (ISA Technical Study No. 3). International Seabed Authority, 15-19; Nandan, S. N., Lodge, M. W. & Rosenne, S. (2002). *The development of the regime for deep seabed mining*. International Seabed Authority, 45-52.

⁷¹ Freestone, D. (2009). Problems of the ISA regime for deep seabed mining. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 24(3), 385-398; Boyle, A. (1983). Further development of the common heritage concept. *British Yearbook of International Law*, 53, 327-358.

⁷² Antarctic Treaty. (1959). *Treaty on Antarctica*. <https://www.ats.aq/e/ats.htm>.

and encourages international cooperation.⁷³ The ATS demonstrates that states can successfully cooperate in managing a territory rich in potential resources by prioritizing science, peace, and transparency over competition.⁷⁴ For space governance, the Antarctic model illustrates the possibility of maintaining international harmony while setting aside contentious sovereignty questions. Yet, unlike Antarctica, space mining involves direct commercial interests in extractable resources, which the ATS deliberately avoids.⁷⁵

These analogies highlight that cooperative governance of shared domains is possible, but designing a workable framework for space, where commercial incentives are far stronger, remains an unsolved challenge.

In any event, such regimes should be assessed on the basis not of potential copying but of analogy, taking into account all their work experience, with successes and failures.

4.3. The amendment of the Moon Agreement

The third option is to amend the Moon Agreement, eliminating the key contradictions between developing and space-faring states. In doing so, it is necessary to take into account the experience of UNCLOS and the 1994 Agreement, as well as the compromises that ultimately allowed states to reach a consensus. Furthermore, again, an agreement must be reached on a benefit-sharing regime, and a governing body similar to the ISA must be established for this purpose.

However, a significant obstacle to implementing this option may be the fundamental difference between UNCLOS and the Moon Agreement. UNCLOS initially featured a rather comprehensive and detailed system for mining technology transfer, funding, licensing, production control, and the equitable sharing of financial and other economic benefits.⁷⁶ It is “the most elaborated application of the concept of the common heritage of mankind in any instrument of international law.”⁷⁷ The Moon Agreement, by contrast, is merely a framework. The specific details for regulating the exploitation of natural space resources are to be agreed upon by the parties to the Moon Agreement through the process of establishing an international regime.⁷⁸ Consequently, if states are unwilling to even adopt the framework regulation, thereby forfeiting the opportunity to subsequently advance their vision for a more precise regulatory structure, this option appears unlikely.

Another obstacle is the limited influence of the Moon Agreement, which has very few ratifications and is not generally regarded as a strong instrument for regulating outer space activities. This, in turn, further diminishes both the perceived need for and the value of any amendment to the Moon Treaty.

4.4. Soft law with prospectives

The fourth option is regulation of exploitation through soft law. Today, non-binding forms are taking primacy through the work of the UN bodies.⁷⁹ These soft law instruments are resolutions of the UN General Assembly, as well as guidelines, such as the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines of the UNCOPUOS.⁸⁰ In 2025, the UNCOPUOS presented an Initial draft set of recommended principles for

⁷³ *Ibid*, Articles II-III.

⁷⁴ Joyner, C. C. (1995). The Antarctic Treaty System and the Law of the Sea: Competing regimes in the Southern Ocean. *International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 10(3), 301–331.

⁷⁵ Dodds, K. & Hemmings, A. D. (2017). The Antarctic Treaty System and the politics of governance. In K. Dodds, A. D. Hemmings & P. Roberts (Eds.), *Handbook on the politics of Antarctica*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁷⁶ Lee, R.J. (2012). *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer.

⁷⁷ *Ibid*. at 245.

⁷⁸ Moon Agreement, Article 11(5), *supra* note 7.

⁷⁹ Pecujlic, A.N. (2023). *The Space Law Stalemate: Legal Mechanisms for Developing New Norms*. Routledge.

⁸⁰ *Ibid*.

space resource activities.⁸¹ In their commentaries, some states not parties to the Moon Agreement acknowledge that its provisions are nevertheless part of the existing legal framework, which should be taken into account to develop the regulation.⁸²

Thus, some provisions of the Moon Agreement could become non-binding principles for states planning active exploitation of space resources. Although such principles are not obligatory, states can nevertheless bind themselves to them through certain acts: 1) to adopt national legislation which would implement the principles, making them obligatory for themselves on the national level; 2) to make declarations promising to follow these principles as mandatory (as unilateral acts); 3) through their consistent and widespread practice and perception of principles as obligatory, states can develop new rules of customary law.⁸³

These mechanisms would help legally obligate states to comply with a number of the Moon Agreement's provisions without their participation in the treaty itself. However, in this case, to truly establish a benefit-sharing regime (with or without a relevant authority), it would still be necessary to create multilateral regulation sooner or later, as national laws and unilateral acts could be inconsistent. Customary law also will not help with the description of the specific benefit-sharing procedure due to its nature not being as detailed as that of treaties.

Nevertheless, as reaching states' agreement on a universal approach is a complex and lengthy process, the first steps towards it can certainly be made in the form of soft law.⁸⁴

5. CONCLUSION

As this paper has demonstrated, the international community is fundamentally divided between two principal approaches – permissive and restrictive. Developing countries tend to adopt the restrictive approach, while space-faring nations embrace and operationalize the permissive approach through national legislation granting property rights over extracted resources.

The practical implications of this divergence are significant and potentially dangerous. The current trajectory, characterized by national laws, risks undermining the core principles of international cooperation that underpin not only the Moon Agreement, but even the OST. It creates a regulatory grey area where powerful states and private entities can advance their interests, potentially deepening global inequality and triggering political tensions. The international community, thus, needs a coherent and universally accepted regulatory framework.

Given the unlikelihood of the Moon Agreement achieving universal adoption and the political infeasibility of a comprehensive new treaty in the short term, the path forward must be pragmatic. A wholesale amendment of the Moon Agreement or the creation of a mandatory international regime akin to the ISA, while ideal in theory, faces substantial political hurdles. Therefore, the most viable immediate solution lies in the development of a soft law framework. This could take the form of a set of recommended principles, outlining at least some of the Moon Agreement's ideas.

⁸¹ Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2025). *Initial draft set of recommended principles for space resource activities* (A/AC.105/C.2/L.339). United Nations. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/v25/021/86/pdf/v2502186.pdf>.

⁸² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2025). *Contribution of the Delegation of the Russian Federation to the Working Group on Legal Aspects of Space Resource Activities of the Legal Subcommittee of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space on elements for an initial draft set of recommended principles for space resource activities*. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/lsc/space-resources/DraftPrinciplesContributions/Russian_Federation_Contribution_to_the_WG_on_space_resources.pdf.

⁸³ Pecujlic, *supra* note 79.

⁸⁴ Masson-Zwaan & Sundahl, *supra* note 11.

In conclusion, the search for a unified approach to commercial space mining is a pressing necessity for the sustainable and peaceful future of human activities in outer space. Without such an approach, the commercialization of space risks replicating the historical patterns of terrestrial resource competition, thereby betraying the visionary spirit of international space law.

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GOVERNING ART IN OUTER SPACE

MARIA BORISLAVOVA POPOVA¹

ABSTRACT

Art has always been a means for humanity to find common grounds for communication, joy, and even peace. As space innovation has emerged, artists have found ways to diversify their work and expand their capabilities, sharing their ideas in space. They started sending artworks into outer space, which led to the occurring opportunity to consider supporting those creators through legal and ethical frameworks for space-based art.

The main benefits for the artist from those regulations would be licensing, copyright protections, and intellectual property rights. This could help establish originality, secure funding, and stimulate global recognition. Space-based artworks, however, and especially those launched by private entities, raise significant jurisdictional questions. Issues regarding national laws should be addressed. It should matter whether the artwork is under State protection or is a private initiative. Without legal clarity, disputes over ownership, liability, and cultural representation may arise.

Furthermore, artworks in orbit risk disrupting the space environment by contributing to light and noise pollution or generating debris, undermining the principles of the Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. The Treaty establishes principles of peaceful use, non-appropriation, and shared benefit. As space becomes increasingly commercialised, artistic projects may be treated differently from commercial advertising or satellite infrastructure. Moreover, space art may also serve as a form of cultural diplomacy as it may be a symbolic gesture of peace and unity.

This article argues for the development of legal instruments that encourage sustainable and peaceful artistic activity in space.

KEYWORDS: Space, Art Innovations, Copyright, Environment, Diplomacy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Outer space was historically perceived as a primarily scientific domain,² where States pursued technological advancement and the collection of data on celestial bodies.³ However, much of this activity was also closely tied to geopolitical interests, as national programs often operated under the guise of science while advancing military and strategic capabilities.⁴ Although the placement of weapons of mass destruction in orbit and the use of celestial bodies for hostile military purposes were prohibited, the presence of military personnel in space, who historically comprised the majority of astronauts and cosmonauts, was not restricted.⁵

Over time, the focus of outer space has expanded beyond scientific exploration and geopolitical competition.⁶ Outer space has evolved into space for artistic expression.⁷ Artists have grown an interest in technology and exploration of territories beyond Earth's atmosphere.⁸ They have collaborated with entities which launch space objects and have even finished projects on painted rockets, orbital sculptures, space museums, and satellite-borne digital artworks. Those efforts often symbolise the never-ending aspirations of humanity to learn and explore, as well as the capabilities of human nature.⁹ It only shows how close the fields of science and art are related.

As art leaves the Earth's borders, new questions are posed before the legal sphere. Importance needs to be drawn to the distinction between commerciality and the pure willingness of people to expand their field of creativity,¹⁰ on the one hand, and, on the other, to connect with each other based on that creative expression, especially on an intercultural level.¹¹ The prerequisites of those aspects are different as they serve a slightly different purpose from one another. It should be theorised about the morality of creating just for the sake of it on the plain of personal interest, parallel to the benefits to all humankind.

The existing body of space law is not designed to accommodate cultural activities, regardless of their objectives. Though there is some progress, e.g. the One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space (OSS2PHH) Act in the US, it is merely a recommendation and not a policy act, which has not

² Pyne, S. J. (2006). *Seeking newer worlds: An historical context for space exploration* (Chapter 1). In S. J. Dick & R. D. Launius (Eds.), *Critical issues in the history of spaceflight* (7). NASA History Division. <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/sp-4702.pdf>.

³ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl (Eds.), Popova & Reynders (Asst. Eds.), & Volynskaya, Katsura-Trumpel, & Ladeyshchikov (Trans.). (2017). *Cologne Commentary on Space Law* (14). BWV. BERLINER WISSENSCHAFTS-VERLAG.

⁴ Farooqui, M. O., & Qureshi, T. (2024). Outer space militarization and the emerging paradigm of weaponization: Implications for space security and international regulation. *Revista Justiça do Direito*, 38(2), 116–145. <https://doi.org/10.5335/rjd.v38i2.15311>.

⁵ Gres, T., et al. (2022). *Astronaut profile evolution through time and space: Study of the past, current and future requirements*.

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Tania-Gres/publication/364351942_Astronaut_profile_evolution_through_time_and_space_Study_of_the_past_current_and_future_requirements/links/634e67296e0d367d91a7390d/Astronaut-profile-evolution-through-time-and-space-Study-of-the-past-current-and-future-requirements.pdf.

⁶ Triscott, N. (2016). *Critical art and outer space: A curatorial inquiry into space as a global commons* [Conference paper]. Westminster Research. https://westminsterresearch.westminster.ac.uk/download/cbb3f32394f4bcf305f83908d30388f5f89d7645926b4a2e51753b5ee2ead3ce/180168/CriticalArtandOuterSpace_Triscott.pdf (westminsterresearch.westminster.ac.uk).

⁷ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Dissanayake, E. (2010). *Why we make art: And why it is taught* (2nd ed.) (p. 5). Intellect / Chicago University Press.

https://books.google.bg/books?hl=en&lr=&id=DvmACgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=why+we+create+art&ots=9LquHwLS-g&sig=Uh6e3hubsrsmdBgj86uWqagqB1g&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=why%20we%20create%20art&f=false.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

yet been applied by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).¹² International treaties primarily focus on fundamental aspects of space policy, including scientific advancement, security, safety, and liability.¹³ While some national laws address issues such as intellectual property, taxation, or even voting rights for space-based activities, there is no comprehensive legal framework specifically tailored to regulate cultural initiatives in space.¹⁴ As a result, space art exists in a regulatory gap, raising questions about authorization, jurisdiction, environmental impact, and the protection of creators' rights that current instruments do not explicitly address.¹⁵ The methodology of exploring space should be altered in order to meet the needs of the emerging focus on art.¹⁶ The regulations should leave space for the cultural development, irrespective of the purpose – either commercial, or universal and non-profitable.¹⁷ Alongside that necessity, another question is debated – how to govern the art field in the space context. The duality of the problem lies in the debate over whether art should be governed as a collective good or as a private enterprise.¹⁸ The advantages of both should be discussed, as well as their downsides for both artists and the public.

2. METHODOLOGY

This article adopts a doctrinal methodology, combining legal analysis and theoretical reflection. Its aim is to explore the question of whether artistic expression should be subject to legal regulation in the context of sending artworks into outer space for various reasons.

It includes an analysis of the legal space instruments, such as sources of law and subsidiary materials, to identify any possible protection of cultural activities in relation to the space field, considering environmental protection.

The article proposes policy and legal recommendations to align artistic expression in outer space. It adopts a cultural-commons perspective, arguing that outer space should be understood as a scientific frontier and simultaneously, as a shared aesthetic and diplomatic domain.

3. THE EMERGENCE OF ART IN OUTER SPACE

3.1. Historical overview

The philosophical and legal dilemmas around artistic activities in outer space are not merely theoretical. Artists have already begun the exploration of space art in the twentieth century. Examples of early space artworks are the Moon Museum¹⁹ in 1969 and the Voyager Golden Record²⁰ in 1977. They both carry the heritage of human civilisation into interstellar space and depict the striving of

¹² One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act, Pub. L. No. 116-275, 134 Stat. 3358 (2020).

¹³ United Nations. (1967). Article I. *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies* (Outer Space Treaty). https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_21_2220E.pdf.

¹⁴ Vafai, N. (2023, November 15). Celestial art law: An exploration of the artistic landscape and laws governing art in space. Center for Art Law. <https://itsartlaw.org/2023/11/15/celestial-art-law-an-exploration-of-the-artistic-landscape-and-laws-governing-art-in-space/>.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Triscott, *supra* note 6 at 5.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Rendell, J. (2000). Public art: Between public and private. In *Locality, regeneration & divers[c]ities* (p. 21). <http://ndl.ethernet.edu.et/bitstream/123456789/44947/1/167.pdf#page=20>.

¹⁹ Guridi, R. (2019). A museum on the moon? *The Moon Museum, exhibition space off limits*. *Revista de Arquitectura*, 21. https://www.proquest.com/openview/fdedc429df0bc2f54975c92cd7f9160b/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=1216382&casa_token=Xj_8nu6AmBYAAAAA:LPJCySuweIEwCL2tOFXDfaJHSanIRfOMItk5EjwAjjKdgM7IF6-KC_NsjrEvK6QGdYl4OSNKBdqA.

²⁰ Robinson, Z. (2022, January 23). *Diplomacy with aliens: The story of the Voyager Golden Records*. <https://zsrobinson.com/posts/diplomacy-with-aliens/>.

humanity for peace, identity, and human capabilities. Despite their objects being different, the Moon Museum showcases the works of six American artists on a tiny ceramic chip,²¹ while the Golden Record is a display of the sounds and images of our civilisation;²² they both illustrate the growing involvement of artists in space activities and the necessity for regulation of the field of space art.

Another aspect of the influence of space art is its relation to nationalistic urges and State propaganda.²³ During the Cold War, space imagery and artistic renderings were not merely neutral expressions of human aspiration; they were potent tools used by both the United States and the Soviet Union to signal technological superiority and cultural dominance.²⁴ For instance, the Soviet Union commissioned posters, stamps, and large-scale public art celebrating Sputnik and Yuri Gagarin's flights, portraying space exploration as proof of socialist scientific and ideological supremacy.²⁵ Similarly, the United States leveraged imagery of the Apollo missions, including iconic photographs such as the 'Earthrise' from Apollo 8, in combination with media campaigns and commemorative art, to convey American technological prowess and leadership in space.²⁶ This historical context complicates the notion of space art as a purely non-political diplomatic endeavour. Even contemporary projects launched via national agencies risk being perceived as soft-power instruments designed to support national prestige rather than foster universal unity. Acknowledging this legacy is vital for any modern regulatory framework that seeks to distinguish between state-sponsored messaging and independent creative expression.

3.2. Contemporary development

More recent art projects incorporate technology, demonstrating that artistic creativity can be closely connected to scientific progress. They encompass a modern take on artistic means through the creation of, for instance, orbital light installations,²⁷ satellite-based digital art, and even blockchain certification of the art via space NFTs. Tavares Strachan is an example of an artist whose work investigates science, technology, and history.²⁸ His practice draws upon the conceptual frameworks of aeronautical and astronomical science, deep-sea exploration, and extreme climatology to produce allegories that examine cultural displacement and human aspirations. The ENOCH project demonstrates Strachan's engagement with these themes, most notably through his collaboration with SpaceX to launch the artwork aboard one of the company's spacecraft.²⁹ ENOCH is expected to burn up in the atmosphere in December 2025, as the name refers to a biblical figure who is able to enter the afterlife according to the story.³⁰

Strachan is not without precedent in the twenty-first century. Many other artists have his aspirations to create a work, which is enriched with symbolism and leaves a message to humanity about their understanding of the world, while also demonstrating the capabilities of contemporary society and reflecting on the technological achievements of our civilisation.³¹ For instance, the Mayak satellite

²¹ Guridi, *supra* note 19 at 245.

²² Robinson *supra* note 20.

²³ Kallen, S. (2019). Nationalism, ideology, and the Cold War Space Race. *Constellations*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.29173/cons29377> (p. 6); Conversi, D. (2009). Art, nationalism and war: Political futurism in Italy (1909–1944). *Nations and Nationalism*, 15(1), 92–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2008.00185.x>.

²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ Banerjee, A. (2013). Between Sputnik and Gagarin. *Space Flight, Children's Periodicals, and the Circle of Imagination*. In M. Balina & L. Rudova (Eds.), *Russian children's literature and culture* (p. 68). Routledge.

²⁶ Keltner, K. A. (2007). *From myth to metaphor to memory: A rhetorical analysis of televised representations of Project Apollo, 1968–2004* (Doctoral dissertation, Ohio University). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (Publication No. 3280032).

²⁷ Yalcinkaya, G. (2019, March 22). *Trevor Paglen's art installation in limbo in Earth's orbit*. *dezeen*. <https://www.dezeen.com/2019/03/22/orbital-reflector-trevor-paglen-design/>.

²⁸ Strachan, T. (n.d.). *Artist profile*. Galerie Perrotin. https://www.perrotin.com/artists/tavares_strachan/797#videos.

²⁹ Strachan, T. (2015–17). *ENOCH (display unit)* [Sculpture]. The Metropolitan Museum of Art. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/856524>.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid.*

project in 2017 launched a reflective structure designed to unfold in space and shine brightly in the night sky, transforming a satellite into a visible artistic object for observers on Earth.³² In addition to the symbolic nature of the project, it exposes the importance of scientific value in such undertakings. The significance lies not only in the necessity to draw attention to space research and activities, but also in the contribution to the problem-solving in areas such as the apparent stellar magnitude of space objects.³³

Similarly, Rocket Lab's 'Humanity Star' satellite was conceived as a symbolic mirror-like sphere intended to orbit the planet as a reminder of humanity's shared presence in space.³⁴ Another example is Trevor Paglen's 'Orbital Reflector', developed with the Nevada Museum of Art, which placed a reflective sculptural satellite into orbit to function as a temporary celestial monument visible from Earth.³⁵ Even though not all of the projects demonstrate a direct link between science and aesthetics, they become a blueprint of how artists increasingly collaborate with aerospace engineers and private space companies to transform orbit into a new exhibition space.

4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF SPACE LAW IN ART CONTEXT

4.1. Deficiency of the legal framework of art

As the importance of space art has now been clarified, it is vital for artists, scientists, and even States to picture its place within the legal system.

Existing space law was not originally designed to accommodate artistic and cultural activities. Perhaps, it was not anticipated to play a role in the development of the world, as historically, the focus of space legislation has been on the scientific and technological space evolution,³⁶ rather than creative or recreational endeavours in outer space. It was necessary to first understand the basics of the space possibilities, and only then, room for secondary activities may have been left. The *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty; OST)³⁷ primarily established principles for the peaceful use of outer space, liability, and resource ownership, without considering the unique challenges posed by art projects in space. The reason behind it is enshrined in the historical context as the negotiation process of the treaty was materializing the final draft in an era dominated by State actors and Cold War imperatives.³⁸ No State currently has a specific, standalone 'Space Art Act' or comprehensive legislation dedicated solely to artistic and cultural pursuits in outer space.

4.2. Existing regulations

All international instruments reflect this historical line. Those instruments highlight the principles, aiming to preserve safety and protect stability between States. The main focuses of the Outer Space Treaty are to avoid militarization of outer space, prevent national appropriation of any celestial bodies, ensure State responsibility and liability, respectively for any breaches and damages, and to promote peaceful exploration of space. Those goals are reaffirmed in the subsequent treaties and conventions (i.e. the *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return*

³² Cosmo Mayak. (2017). *Mayak satellite – The Mayak satellite is the brightest star in the night sky*. Retrieved from <https://www.cosmomayak.com/>.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Rocket Lab Reveals "The Humanity Star," a "Disco Ball" Satellite Shining From Space. (2018). Space.com. Retrieved from <https://www.space.com/39482-rocket-lab-reveals-humanity-star-satellite.html>.

³⁵ Paglen, T. (2018, November 25). Orbital Reflector: The artist firing a satellite into space. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2018/nov/25/orbital-reflector-trevor-paglen-satellite>.

³⁶ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3 at 110.

³⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. (1967, January 27). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

³⁸ Collis, J. (2009). The geostationary orbit: A critical legal geography of space's most valuable real estate. In D. Bell & M. Parker (Eds.), *Space travel and culture: From Apollo to space tourism* (p. 47). Routledge.

of Objects Launched into Outer Space (ARRA),³⁹ the Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects (Liability Convention; LIAB),⁴⁰ the Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (Registration Convention; REG),⁴¹ and the Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (MOON), although the latter has only been ratified by 17 States).⁴² The outer space area is also governed by multiple customary rules, existing in national laws and international practice;⁴³ however, there is also no mention of the new role of private actors in the art field. At a national level, States with advanced space sectors have their own regulatory regimes. In the Russian Federation, e.g., space activities are governed by the *Law on Space Activities* (No. 5663-1 of 1993), which sets out general principles, licensing requirements for the manufacture, testing, launch, and control of space objects, and certification regimes for space technology, all aimed at scientific, national-economic, and security goals.⁴⁴ Supplementary normative acts, such as the statute on licensing procedures and government resolutions that define the mandate of Roscosmos, implement these requirements and make clear that any actor planning to conduct space operations under Russian jurisdiction must be licensed and compliant with State oversight.⁴⁵

Because neither the existing international treaties nor most national frameworks were drafted with artistic or cultural projects in mind, they leave ambiguities when such projects are proposed – whether concerning licensing, responsibility for orbital debris, or how creative content in space should be regulated.⁴⁶ For example, even a satellite launched for aesthetic purposes must typically navigate the same licensing and registration requirements as a scientific spacecraft, despite no harmful intent or traditional space use.

4.3. New necessities

Even though art, as a space activity, is still relatively rare, its rise is inevitable in the near future.⁴⁷ Therefore, new regulations need to emerge to protect the human values embodied in such creations. Law should be a pre-emptive governance tool, which, based on the existing precedents,⁴⁸ ensures the legal certainty with regard to the protection of intellectual property and financial benefits of artists, on the one hand, but also the protection of the space environment, human rights, and scientific research, on the other. In practice, this dual function means that law would establish clear guidelines on what

³⁹ Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space. (1968, April 22). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/rescueagreement.html>.

⁴⁰ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects. (1972, March 29). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

⁴¹ Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space. (1975, January 14). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/registration-convention.html>.

⁴² Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. (1979, December 18). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/moon-agreement.html>.

⁴³ Vereshchetin, V. S., & Danilenko, G. M. (1994). Custom as a source of international law of outer space. Routledge.

⁴⁴ Law on Space Activities, No. 5663-1 (Russ.) of 20 August 1993. On Space Activities. Retrieved from <https://legalacts.ru/doc/zakon-rf-ot-20081993-n-5663-1-o/>.

⁴⁵ Federal Law No. 19-FZ (Russ.) of 2 February 2006, as amended up to Federal Law No. 216-FZ of 13 July 2015. *On Amendments to Certain Laws and the Repeal of Certain Provisions of Certain Laws of the Russian Federation in Connection with the Adoption of the Federal Law on the Placement of Orders for the Supply of Goods, Performance of Work, and Provision of Services for State and Municipal Needs*.

⁴⁶ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁴⁷ Wang, F. Y., & Zhai, C. (2026). The evolution of space art: Dream, Monolith and Revelation. *Acta Astronautica*, 238(Part A) (p. 908). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.09.049>.

⁴⁸ Stockdale, L. P. D. (2013). *Governing the future, mastering time: Temporality, sovereignty, and the pre-emptive politics of (in)security* (Doctoral dissertation, McMaster University). McMaster University Institutional Repository. <https://prod-ms-be.lib.mcmaster.ca/server/api/core/bitstreams/aeac37f6-fe83-4c34-a2da-ea47be0c4d3f/content>.

types of artistic activities are permissible, require authorization and supervision for space-based projects, and set technical and ethical standards for materials, reflectivity, or orbital behaviour. By combining protective and regulatory measures, law can both empower artistic expression and ensure that the human values underlying space art are aligned with the collective, long-term interests of the global community.

The fact that there is no single legal regime specifically designed for artistic activities in outer space does not mean that such projects exist outside regulation. They are situated at the intersection of two already highly regulated fields: *space activities*⁴⁹ and *artistic or cultural production*.⁵⁰ International space law instruments, such as the Outer Space Treaty, the Liability Convention, and the Registration Convention, establish obligations relating to State responsibility, liability, and the registration of space objects. At the same time, artistic creation and cultural heritage are governed by separate national and international frameworks, including cultural property laws, intellectual property regimes, and conventions such as the UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions.⁵¹ The difficulty arises because these two regulatory spheres were developed independently and pursue different objectives: space law prioritizes safety, liability, and the sustainable use of the orbital environment, whereas cultural and art-related legislation focuses on creativity, cultural expression, and heritage protection. As a result, projects that place artworks in orbit or otherwise use space as a medium often fall between regulatory categories.⁵² Authorities may struggle to determine which rules should apply, how artistic intent should be assessed within technical licensing frameworks, or how cultural value should be weighed against operational or environmental concerns.⁵³ This fragmentation can create practical difficulties in implementation and may also leave legal *lacunae*, where neither body of law provides clear guidance for the governance of artistic activities conducted in outer space.⁵⁴

There are two main possible approaches to achieve the goal of filling the legal gap in the regulation. The first one involves incorporating targeted amendments or interpretative guidelines into the already existing sources⁵⁵ of law, including space law as part of public international law. An instance could be by clarifying within the Outer Space Treaty⁵⁶ or through implementing guidelines adopted by international bodies⁵⁷ that artistic and cultural projects constitute a legitimate form of ‘use of outer space’, provided that they comply with existing obligations regarding authorization, supervision, and environmental protection. In practice, such an approach could require States to explicitly include cultural or artistic missions within their national licensing frameworks for space activities, ensuring that projects initiated by artists or cultural institutions are subject to the same authorization and supervision requirements that apply to other non-governmental space activities under Article VI of the OST.

⁴⁹ Santos, E. A. (2025, July 4). *International law and the regulation of outer space*. Diplomacy & Law. <https://www.diplomacyandlaw.com/post/international-law-and-the-regulation-of-outer-space>.

⁵⁰ UNESCO. (2023). *Artistic freedom: International standards and challenges* (UNESCO Creativity Policy Series). UNESCO. https://www.unesco.org/creativity/sites/default/files/medias/fichiers/2023/01/artistic_freedom_pdf_web.pdf.

⁵¹ UNESCO. (2005). *Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* (adopted 20 October 2005; entered into force 18 March 2007). <https://legal.un.org/avl/ha/cppdce/cppdce.html>

⁵² Brobst, J. A. (2024). *Legal strategies to preserve the natural and cultural heritage of space*. In S. Bhat B. (Ed.), *Space tourism: Legal and policy aspects* (pp. 133–152). Routledge India.

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁵⁵ Azaria, D. (2020). ‘Codification by interpretation’: The International Law Commission as an interpreter of international law. *European Journal of International Law*, 31(1), 171–200. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/cha016>.

⁵⁶ UNOOSA. (2025, May 5). *Clarifying ambiguities in the Outer Space Treaty: Conference room paper by Space Renaissance International* (A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.17). https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac.105c.22025crp/aac.105c.22025crp.17_0.htm

⁵⁷ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

The second approach concerns the adoption of a new regulatory instrument,⁵⁸ specifically addressing artistic and cultural activities in outer space. Such an instrument could take the form of either a *binding* international agreement⁵⁹ or a *non-binding* soft-law framework.⁶⁰ A binding treaty would provide clear and enforceable obligations for States regarding the authorization, supervision, and protection of space-based artworks, as well as rules on liability, environmental responsibility, and the preservation of culturally significant space objects.⁶¹ Alternatively, a non-binding instrument, such as international guidelines, principles, or recommendations adopted within forums like the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), could offer a more flexible and politically feasible solution.⁶² Such soft-law mechanisms could establish the best practices for licensing artistic missions and promote standards which ensure that artistic projects do not interfere with scientific missions or contribute to orbital debris. Such techniques may encourage States to integrate cultural considerations into national space legislation.

Irrespective of the approach the international community chooses, new legislation would be beneficial to expand the human reach in outer space, as it is already not merely a scientific frontier, but also a creative commons. In this regard, future regulation could draw inspiration from international frameworks developed for the protection of cultural heritage, such as the UNESCO Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage and adapt some of their governance mechanisms to the space domain. For example, the UNESCO Convention principles can be incorporated into space law by treating outer space as a ‘shared aesthetic and diplomatic domain’ similar to how Earth-bound heritage sites are protected. International law could adopt the UNESCO view that certain cultural achievements belong to all humankind. This aligns with Article I OST, which defines space as the ‘province of all mankind’. Furthermore, UNESCO’s focus on ‘natural heritage’ as defined in Article 2 of the Convention can be used to bolster space law’s environmental protection, specifically regarding the mitigation of orbital debris and ‘light and noise pollution’ caused by artistic installations. Additionally, States can incorporate the principles under the Convention into their domestic authorization and supervision process as required under Article VI of the OST. For instance, national regulators could require artists and private companies to prove that their space-based art complies with ethical and environmental standards similar to those used for protected sites on Earth.

5. SECTION ART AS MEANS IN DIPLOMACY FOR INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND DIALOGUE

5.1. Advantages of cultural diplomacy

Few artists set out with the explicit goal of contributing to diplomacy; indeed, art often challenges authority and questions commonly accepted norms.⁶³ Yet one of the enduring advantages of art is its potential to serve as a vehicle for diplomacy.⁶⁴ There are several types of diplomacy, with the political one being the main field. However, subsidiary to its relevance is also the cultural diplomacy. Cultural

⁵⁸ Asatryan, A. (2023). The concept of filling, eliminating gaps in law and ways to overcome them. *Byurakan Young Scientists’ Journal*, 14(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.46991/BYSU:C/2023.14.1.003>.

⁵⁹ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

⁶⁰ Waibel, M. (2024, September 18). *Potential indirect legal effects of non-legally binding instruments* (Panel 2 statement, Second Practitioners’ Workshop on Non-Legally Binding Instruments in International Law, Vienna, Austria). Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/panel-2-statement-m-waibel-final/1680b1f73d>.

⁶¹ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

⁶² Waibel, *supra* note 60.

⁶³ Adeleke, K. (2025, August 25). *How art challenges social norms: A bold history of creative disruption*. ARTCENTRON. <https://artcentron.com/2025/08/25/how-art-challenges-social-norms/>.

⁶⁴ Tibererwa, E. (2025). *Cultural diplomacy: Art as a tool for international relations*. *Eurasian Experiment Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 92–102. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390696010_Cultural_Diplomacy_Art_as_a_Tool_for_International_Relations.

diplomacy is grounded in two preconditions.⁶⁵ Firstly, mutual respect and understanding between actors and, secondly, the understanding of culture as a combination of art, language and education.⁶⁶ Those areas lead to some of the most effective human exchanges, as they are meant to overcome prejudice and disinformation.⁶⁷ An example in practice of cultural diplomacy is the loan by the Vatican to the Albert Museum in London. During a visit of the Pope in Great Britain, the Vatican lent 16th-century tapestries, illustrating scenes from the Acts of the Apostles. These invaluable artworks, seldom displayed outside the Vatican, convey another narrative about the Catholic Church, enriching its public image and fostering engagement through a medium which is less politically contentious.⁶⁸ Such examples once again show the importance of diplomacy through cultural means.

5.2. Cultural diplomacy in space

Space art can also serve the purpose of cultural diplomacy, as it generally represents another form of art. It could be a unifying symbol, transcending borders, which preconditions its potential for cultural exchange and global cooperation. Such an approach is coherent with the principles of Article III of the OST regarding the obligation for international cooperation and understanding. It may be used in the peacekeeping process through collaborative international art. States can initiate collective projects to show their alacrity for international peace.

However, without appropriate coordination, this tool for soft diplomacy risks becoming a form of cultural dominance where only wealthy nations are able to send art since those projects are costly, both the materials for the artwork, which need to be altered in a way to be safe for launch, and the spacecrafts.⁶⁹ Proper coordination is required in order for any political messages to be avoided.⁷⁰ Political influence is contrary to the goals of cultural diplomacy, which encourages mutual understanding among actors.⁷¹

The new space art framework should ensure equitable cultural access to any Party. Space should remain canvas for all humanity and not be limited to the privileged few. States should effectively coordinate among themselves in such a way that even the least developed countries, according to the United Nations,⁷² should have the opportunity to participate in world policymaking.⁷³ Each State should also have the obligation to foster creativity by allowing any artist to join the initiatives. They may include financial support practices in their legal frameworks in order to stimulate all artists to create the future of the international community.⁷⁴

In this context, a future space art framework could clarify procedural aspects, such as authorization mechanisms, criteria for international representation, and the registration status of artistic payloads.

⁶⁵ Goff, P. M. (2013). *Cultural diplomacy*. In A. F. Cooper, J. Heine, & R. Thakur (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of modern diplomacy* (420). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199588862.013.0024>.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Ibid, 422.

⁶⁹ Watlington, E. (2023, May 16). *The best and worst artists of our time are sending their work into space*. ARTnews. <https://www.artnews.com/art-in-america/columns/space-art-jeff-koons-xu-bing-xin-liu-1234667481/>.

⁷⁰ Demirel, I. N., & Altıntaş, O. (2012). Relationship between art and politics. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 51, p. 446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.08.241>.

⁷¹ Tibererwa, E. (2025). *Cultural diplomacy: Art as a tool for international relations*. EURASIAN EXPERIMENT Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 7(1), (93). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390696010_Cultural_Diplomacy_Art_as_a_Tool_for_International_Relations_researchgate.net+1.

⁷² United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. (n.d.). *UN list of least developed countries*. <https://unctad.org/topic/least-developed-countries/list>.

⁷³ Mabry, M. C., & Mabry, B. D. (1981). *The role of the arts in developing countries: Thailand, a case study*. *Ekistics*, 48(288), (248). https://www.jstor.org/stable/43620542_jstor.org+1.

⁷⁴ United Nations Human Rights Council. (2013). *Report of the Special Rapporteur in the field of cultural rights, Farida Shaheed: The right to freedom of artistic expression and creativity* (A/HRC/23/34). <https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/23/34>.

By aligning artistic initiatives with existing legal obligations under international space law, space art can develop as a legitimate form of cultural diplomacy without undermining the principles of responsibility, transparency, and cooperation that govern activities in outer space.

6. SPACE COMMERCIALIZATION

6.1. Commercialization of space posing new challenges

Whether private initiatives for space art exist is no longer a matter for debate, as the answer is affirmative.⁷⁵ Numerous private companies now launch space objects and collaborate with artists, willing to develop the space art field. As aforementioned, there are already some cases of artists sending their works into space, both presently and historically, such as Tavares Strachan, Xu Bing,⁷⁶ Jeff Koons,⁷⁷ and also the early collaborative project Moon Museum.

Commercialization of space has gradually transformed the exclusive domain of national space agencies into a rapidly expanding frontier for private actors. Those actors include companies, artistic institutions, private sponsors, and individual artists. As access to outer space becomes increasingly feasible, questions arise on how to regulate private artistic initiatives in outer space.⁷⁸

From a regulatory perspective, private space activities are already governed by several foundational norms of international space law, which regulate both responsibility (e.g. the aforementioned in Article VI OST) and liability regimes. Liability considerations play a central role in regulating private initiatives. The Liability Convention establishes that launching States are internationally liable for damage caused by their space objects. Consequently, if an artwork forms part of a spacecraft payload or constitutes an independent object placed in orbit, the launching State may incur liability in the event of damage to other space objects, the space environment, or property on Earth. This legal framework incentivizes States to adopt strict authorization procedures and technical requirements for private launches, including those involving artistic payloads.

Another relevant regulatory aspect concerns planetary protection.⁷⁹ While many artistic projects are intended for orbit or symbolic missions, some initiatives have proposed sending artworks to the Moon or other celestial bodies. Such activities must comply with broader international obligations aimed at preventing harmful contamination of outer space environments. Article IX OST requires States to conduct activities in outer space with due regard to the interests of other States and to avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies. In practice, these principles are implemented through internationally recognized planetary protection standards developed by the Committee on Space Research.⁸⁰ Artistic missions directed toward celestial bodies would therefore need to comply with scientific contamination control requirements, even if their primary purpose is cultural rather than scientific.

Even if we accept that artworks sent into space should remain under the jurisdiction of that launching State, new regulations are still necessary in order to draw the limitations of the artists' involvement in the space sector. Taken together, these legal and normative mechanisms demonstrate that private artistic initiatives in space must operate within the broader framework governing space activities. By

⁷⁵ Watlington, *supra* note 69.

⁷⁶ Xu Bing. (n.d.). *Project #707*. <https://www.xubing.com/en/work/details/707?type=project>.

⁷⁷ Rabb, M. (2024, February 16). Jeff Koons sculptures launched on a SpaceX mission to the moon. <https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-jeff-koons-sculptures-launched-spacex-mission-moon>.

⁷⁸ Amruta, G. K. S. (2025). *The role of private entities in outer space activities*. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 7(2), Article 41334. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2025.v07i02.41334>.

⁷⁹ Coustenis, A., et. al. (2023). Planetary protection: Updates and challenges for a sustainable space exploration. *Acta Astronautica*, 210, 446–452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.02.035>.

⁸⁰ Ehrenfreund, P., et. al. (2026, January). *Editorial to the 2026 version of the COSPAR Policy on Planetary Protection* (Space Research Today No. 224, pp. 15–16). COSPAR. https://cosparhq.cnes.fr/assets/uploads/2026/01/SRT_224_Editorial_PPP-Nov-2025.pdf.

integrating artistic missions into existing regimes of authorization, liability, environmental protection, and international cooperation, States can promote cultural expression in outer space, while also ensuring that such activities remain consistent with the principles of sustainability and peaceful use. In this way, space art can develop not merely as an individual creative endeavour but as a structured instrument of cultural diplomacy capable of fostering inclusive participation in humanity's shared space future.

6.2. *Legal aspects of space artworks – current and new regulations*

The increasing congestion of the low Earth orbit (LEO) represents one of the most pressing challenges in contemporary space governance. The proliferation of commercial satellites and other privately operated space objects has intensified concerns regarding orbital crowding and the sustainability of space activities.⁸¹ In this context, the question arises whether new types of objects fall within the existing definition of a 'space object'. Article I(d) LIAB defines a 'space object' as including component parts of a space object as well as its launch vehicle and parts thereof. Although this definition is intentionally broad, many objects may fall out of the scope of any of the instruments. Such ambiguities may arise when dealing with unconventional payloads, such as artworks sent into orbit independently or attached to a spacecraft's structures.

Such ambiguity may generate jurisdictional and accountability concerns. If certain artistic objects were interpreted as falling outside the existing legal definition of a space object, they could potentially escape the established frameworks of responsibility and liability under international space law. In such a scenario, no State would bear the obligations arising from activities conducted in outer space, thereby undermining the fundamental principle of State responsibility established in Article VI OST. For this reason, clarification regarding the legal classification of artistic payloads may be necessary to ensure that all activities conducted in space remain attributable to a launching State and therefore subject to international obligations.⁸²

The term 'space art' is currently only a doctrinal one. It is defined as a genre of art, which encompasses two distinct concepts.⁸³ The first one refers to the visual depiction of the universe through various artistic styles, such as paintings or digital works depicting the cosmos. The second one indicates that artworks are sent into space.⁸⁴

The artworks in space can remain in orbit indefinitely if effective measures for its de-orbit are not implemented.⁸⁵ This is an issue since those objects may become new long-term space debris. For this reason, the principles of OST should be fulfilled, and any new legislation could further deepen the measures for a solution. In this sense, the new regulations may appear to be *lex specialis* to the existing instruments.

However, addressing these challenges does not necessarily require entirely new binding legislation. While the development of specific legal instruments may eventually become necessary, significant regulatory progress can also be achieved through soft-law mechanisms, industry standards, and cooperative governance frameworks. The international space community relies on non-binding guidelines to address emerging challenges. For example, the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines adopted by COPUOS and endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly encourage States and

⁸¹ Borowitz, M. (2018). Strategic implications of the proliferation of space situational awareness technology and information: Lessons learned from the remote sensing sector. *Space Policy*, 45, 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.05.002>.

⁸² World Intellectual Property Organization. (2004). *Intellectual property and space activities: Issue paper prepared by the International Bureau of WIPO* (OECD Contribution, para.47, p.12). Retrieved from https://www.wipo.int/documents/d/patents/docs-en-topics-outer-space-ip_space_wipo-contribution_oecd_2004.pdf.

⁸³ NASA. (2016, August 4). *NASA art program: The art of air and space*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/art/nasa-art-program-the-art-of-air-and-space>.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*

⁸⁵ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3 at 515.

private operators to design space missions in ways that reduce the creation of debris and ensure the long-term sustainability of orbital activities. Similar approaches could be extended to artistic missions through voluntary standards developed in collaboration with commercial launch providers, satellite operators, and cultural institutions.

New applications of the obligations of authorisation and supervision under Article VI OST should also be discussed. Measures regarding the tracking of the objects and their control of space art should be taken,⁸⁶ and the new framework should also include systems for de-orbit or in-space destruction if the piece is made from suitable, non-harming materials to the space environment.⁸⁷ Mechanisms for collision avoidance are also necessary in order for the work to fulfil its purpose and not to interfere with scientific objects,⁸⁸ especially since those mechanisms are still not fully developed in practice, and even the automated collision avoidance manoeuvres are undergoing improvements.

Additionally, the dark and quiet skies should be protected since the sun's reflections are a problem,⁸⁹ which is further magnified by the reflective spacecrafts.⁹⁰ Astronomers have raised growing concerns about the visual brightness and radio interference generated by large satellite constellations and other reflective spacecraft. These issues have been examined in international discussions on the protection of dark and quiet skies, which is an initiative supported by organizations such as the International Astronomical Union. The concept reflects a broader environmental perspective often described as 'space environmentalism', which emphasizes the need to protect both the orbital environment and the observational integrity of the night sky for scientific research and cultural heritage.⁹¹

Artistic space projects may unintentionally exacerbate these challenges. Several of the artistic initiatives mentioned earlier, such as the Mayak project and the Rocket Lab, involve highly reflective materials or symbolic objects designed to attract visual attention.⁹² The artists proudly present their projects as 'the brightest star in the night sky'. While such characteristics may serve artistic purposes, they can also increase light reflectivity in orbit, thereby contributing to optical interference with ground-based astronomical observations. If widely replicated, such projects could intensify existing concerns regarding orbital light pollution.⁹³

To mitigate these risks, several practical measures could be adopted within future governance frameworks for space art. First, authorization procedures under Article VI OST could require environmental impact assessments for artistic payloads, similar to those already implemented for certain scientific or commercial missions. Second, technical design standards could be introduced to limit reflectivity and reduce optical brightness, drawing on ongoing collaboration between satellite operators and astronomical institutions. Third, licensing authorities could require artistic objects placed in orbit to incorporate reliable end-of-life disposal mechanisms, including controlled de-orbiting within a specified timeframe. Finally, transparency mechanisms such as mandatory

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ Ibid, 505.

⁸⁸ Ibid, 181.

⁸⁹ Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2025, June 25–July 2). *Report of the Scientific and Technical Subcommittee on its sixty-second session: Conference room paper on dark and quiet skies for science and society* (Sixty-eighth session, Item 6 of the provisional agenda). United Nations. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/v25/047/48/pdf/v2504748.pdf>.

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ Marino, A., & Cheney, T. (2023). Centring environmentalism in space governance: Interrogating dominance and authority through a critical legal geography of outer space. *Space Policy*, 63, 101521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101521>.

⁹² Lardies, G. (2025, July 9). *What is Rocket Lab launching into space and why are people angry about it?* The Spinoff. <https://thespinoff.co.nz/society/09-07-2025/what-is-rocket-lab-launching-into-space-and-why-are-people-angry-about-it>.

⁹³ Ibid.

registration and tracking could ensure that artistic payloads remain identifiable and manageable within existing space traffic coordination systems.

Ultimately, the emergence of space art reflects a broader transformation in the nature of space activities, as new actors and new forms of engagement enter the extraterrestrial domain. Rather than focusing exclusively on redefining the concept of a ‘space object’, future space governance frameworks should address the wider implications of these emerging activities. Binding legal obligations could be combined with soft-law instruments, technical standards, and collaborative governance mechanisms, which would lead the international community to be able to ensure that artistic expression in outer space develops in a manner consistent with the principles of sustainability, scientific protection, and the shared interests of humanity.

It is evident that balance should be sought to achieve optimal benefits for both the public interest, especially in the field of environmental protection and outer space scientific exploration, and private interest, which lies in the freedom of expression⁹⁴ and financial turnover,⁹⁵ and these two interests should be balanced.

7. BALANCE OF INTERESTS THROUGH LICENSING

7.1. *Why licensing is important*

When art is launched into outer space, it occupies a unique legal and ethical position. The creative expression is materialised in an existing object, which should fall into the jurisdiction of a specific State. If not regulated, it would belong to all humankind, which, although sounding altruistic, can cause problems to countries and artists.

Therefore, the principle of licensing in the field of intellectual property should be discussed to be applied by analogy in the international context of outer space. Depending on the goal of the project, a different type of Creative Commons (CC) license shall apply.⁹⁶

Regardless of the objective of the initiative, a minimum of protection should apply to artists. They need to be credited for their authorship of the artwork and need to have the right to control the use, reproduction, and modification of it. The current challenge is to protect the artist’s originality without diminishing the cultural value of international cooperation regarding outer space.⁹⁷

Creative Commons licensing allows creators to retain certain rights, while granting the public permission to use, share, or modify the artwork under specific conditions. They are beneficial to all Parties involved since they preserve the authorship of the artist whose works are publicly available.⁹⁸ On the other hand, they prevent monopolisation by private companies and individuals that might commercialise space art as exclusive intellectual property due to its specifics. This would promote collaboration between artists, companies and national space agencies.⁹⁹

7.2. *Types of CC licenses and their applications*

Depending on the purpose of the space art launch, two different types of launches may be defined: *commercial* and *non-commercial*. The commercial ones reflect the interest of the private entities,

⁹⁴ Dissanayake, *supra* note 9 at 10.

⁹⁵ Gupta, P. (2022). *If artists were given more opportunities, would they have a better chance at financial viability?* International Journal of Innovative Science & Research Technology, 7(12), p. 1404.

⁹⁶ Kim, M. (2008). *The Creative Commons and copyright protection in the digital era: Uses of Creative Commons licenses*. College of Communication, p. 192, doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00392.x.

⁹⁷ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁹⁸ *Ibid*.

⁹⁹ *Ibid*, 202.

which may be related to extending human capabilities and financial turnover.¹⁰⁰ Non-commercial are the ones that safeguard scientific and diplomatic space exploration, hence are open to humanity.

Within this context, intellectual property rights become particularly relevant in determining how artworks sent into space may be reproduced, distributed, or commercially exploited. Copyright protection for artistic works is primarily governed by international agreements such as the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works and the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, which establish minimum standards for copyright protection among participating States. These frameworks grant creators exclusive rights over the reproduction, distribution, and adaptation of their works. However, artists may voluntarily grant broader permissions through standardized open licensing systems such as those developed by the Creative Commons (CC license).¹⁰¹

The licensing regarding commercial purposes is mainly of three types: attribution (CC BY), attribution-share-alike (CC BY-SA), and attribution-no-derivatives (CC BY-ND).¹⁰² The CC BY license allows users to copy, modify, distribute, and even sell the artwork, as long as they credit the author. They are useful to the artists in a way that the authors gain exposure and are more suitable for the creators to receive recognition. The CC BY-SA allow users to use or modify the work. Its best use is that it allows others to be inspired by the artwork. The last type is the CC BY-ND, which only permits usage, but not any modifications.¹⁰³

Licenses which prohibit commercial use are attribution-non-commercial (CC BY-NC), attribution-non-commercial-share-alike (CC BY-NC-SA), and attribution-non-commercial-no-derivatives (CC BY-NC-ND). The CC BY-NC allows users to copy and adapt the work for cultural or educational purposes only. The CC BY-NC-SA requires any derivative work to carry the same license, which prevents commercial exploitation. The CC BY-NC-ND is considered the most restrictive license as it only allows sharing with proper credit (i.e. is most suitable when the artwork is merely for display).¹⁰⁴

The potential application of such licensing systems to space art initiatives raises several practical considerations. For example, artists participating in missions that involve broadcasting images of artworks from orbit, reproducing digital models of space-based installations, or displaying artistic objects on spacecraft could license those works under specific Creative Commons frameworks. This would allow the public, scientific institutions, or educational organizations to reproduce and share images or digital representations of the artwork while respecting the rights of the original creator. Moreover, licensing agreements could be incorporated into launch contracts or collaborative mission agreements between artists, sponsors, and launch providers.

Jurisdictional considerations also play an important role in determining how intellectual property rights apply in outer space. Under Article VIII of the OST, a State retains jurisdiction and control over objects launched into outer space that are registered under its authority. Consequently, intellectual property disputes relating to artworks physically placed on spacecraft or orbital platforms may be governed by the domestic law of the launching State. This principle has already been applied in contexts such as the Agreement Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station, which establishes jurisdictional rules for intellectual property created aboard the International Space Station.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁰ Gupta, *supra* note 95 at 1405.

¹⁰¹ Margoni, T., & Peters, D. M. (n.d.). *Creative Commons licenses: Empowering open access*. University of Stirling. <https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/149666/1/149666.pdf>.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ Agreement among the Government of Canada, Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of the Russian Federation, and the Government of the United States of America concerning cooperation on the civil International Space Station. (1998, January 29).

In practice, a structured licensing framework for space art could therefore function as a complementary regulatory mechanism alongside existing space law obligations. By allowing artists to define how their works may be reproduced, adapted, or commercially used, Creative Commons licenses could facilitate cultural dissemination while preserving authors' rights.¹⁰⁶ At the same time, integrating such licensing systems into launch agreements and national authorization procedures would help ensure that space art projects operate within both intellectual property law and international space governance frameworks.¹⁰⁷ In this way, open licensing models could support the development of space art as a tool for cultural exchange while maintaining legal clarity regarding ownership, usage rights, and creative attribution.

8. CONCLUSION

To balance private interests with public welfare, States should adopt a spectrum of flexible soft-law instruments and national licensing procedures that support artists through copyright protection and facilitate launch access while enforcing technical standards for de-orbiting and reflectivity limits to ensure environmental sustainability. Such a framework would establish space art as a pivotal tool for cultural diplomacy in the 'province of all mankind', providing a neutral platform for symbolic unity and innovation unburdened by national appropriation. By adapting legislation to these emerging creative interests, the international community can provide a protective shield for peaceful exploration while maintaining the necessary restrictions to preserve the outer space environment for future generations.

International Space Station Intergovernmental Agreement. Retrieved from https://aerospace.org/sites/default/files/policy_archives/Space%20Station%20Intergovernmental%20Agreement%20Jan98.pdf.

¹⁰⁶ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*

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STATE RESPONSIBILITY AND COMMERCIAL SATELLITE SYSTEMS IN ARMED CONFLICT

KAITLYN THOMAS¹

ABSTRACT

The militarization of outer space is increasingly driven by military reliance on commercial space infrastructure. Privately owned and operated satellite systems are able to provide critical communications, navigation, and intelligence capabilities that have become essential to modern military operations on Earth. These systems are typically inherently dual-use, designed for civilian purposes but easily adaptable to military use. International space law, however, remains rooted in outdated assumptions regarding State ownership and control, raising questions about its capacity to regulate this evolving form of militarization.

This paper examines why existing international frameworks struggle to address military reliance on privately owned satellite systems, using SpaceX's Starlink involvement during the Russia-Ukraine war as an illustrative case. Starlink's rapid integration into Ukraine's military operations highlights a growing disconnect between operational realities and legal applications. This analysis argues that this disconnect reflects a mismatch between traditional State-centric responsibility foundational to international law and the privatized nature of today's space activities.

This paper first examines the evolution of modern militarization, from traditional weapons-based conceptions to the rise of infrastructural militarization through commercial satellite systems. It then assesses the limitations of existing legal regimes, demonstrating their reactive nature and inability to constrain militarization *ex ante*. It then turns to State responsibility, primarily under Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty, arguing that while this offers the most appropriate mechanism for addressing private actor involvement, it remains underdeveloped.

Ultimately, this paper identifies a responsibility gap in which conduct shaping the militarization of outer space is legally recognizable yet effectively unregulated. It concludes that without clearer articulation and enforcement of State responsibility, the normalization of military dependence on commercial satellite systems will continue to outpace the law governing outer space activities.

KEYWORDS: State Responsibility, Militarization of Outer Space, Dual-use Satellite, Article VI.

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1. INTRODUCTION: COMMERCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND THE QUIET MILITARIZATION OF OUTER SPACE

The militarization of outer space has traditionally been understood through the lens of the deployment of weapons and the conduct of active warfare beyond Earth's atmosphere. International space law, notably the *1967 Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (OST, Outer Space Treaty), reflects this focus by expressly prohibiting nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in outer space.² However, modern military practice increasingly relies on outer space in ways that do not fit this traditional conception. States have increasingly integrated space infrastructure, typically via satellites, into Earth-based military operations. This shift has occurred in parallel with the explosion of commercial activity in outer space, leading to a divergence between law and practice.

Privately operated satellites have become essential to modern military effectiveness. Commercial constellations provide secure communications, intelligence, and navigation assistance at a scale and speed not currently found with many State-owned systems. The capabilities of such satellites are inherently dual-use, as they are designed for civilian purposes but can be readily adapted to military operations. As a result, military integration of commercial space infrastructure has become normalized, even in light of current legal frameworks governing outer space, primarily centered on State-owned and controlled operations with clearly distinguished civilian and military boundaries.

The Russia-Ukraine war is a particularly salient illustration of this transformation. SpaceX's Starlink constellation, a broadband internet service intended for civilian use, was rapidly integrated into Ukraine's military operations, enabling communication among airborne devices and sustaining operations during blackouts. This integration occurred without any formal transfer of ownership or incorporation into Ukraine's military. A private corporation made all decisions related to Ukraine's access to Starlink. Starlink's role exposes a growing discrepancy between how space systems are used in armed conflict and how international law addresses responsibility and regulation.

This paper asserts that existing international space law frameworks are ill-equipped to regulate military reliance on privately owned dual-use satellite systems. It argues that the illustration of Starlink in the Russia-Ukraine conflict reveals a fundamental mismatch between the State-centric responsibility framework found in the current body of space law and the realities of modern militarization in outer space. This mismatch allows the militarization of space without meaningful legal constraint.

The analysis proceeds in six parts. It will first examine the concept of militarization and how it has evolved in outer space in light of the explosion of private intervention. Next, it will present Starlink as a case study of modern militarization. The following section will study Article VI of the OST as a foundational principle for regulating the space activities of non-governmental

² Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, January 17, 1967, Article IV. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/space/space-law/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

entities. Fourth, the analysis will examine other sources of international law (namely, the Liability Convention and IHL principles) to demonstrate why these regimes, while important to armed conflict, are not best suited to address militarization. Finally, it will return to the concept of State responsibility and explain how these frameworks create a responsibility gap, thereby making militarization legally permissible yet largely unregulated.

2. MILITARIZATION OF OUTER SPACE BEYOND WEAPONS SYSTEMS

2.1. *The Evolution of Modern Conceptions of Militarization*

A traditional view of militarization in outer space has largely centered on the deployment of weapons, anti-satellite (ASAT) capabilities, and the potential for kinetic conflict beyond Earth's atmosphere. The potential weaponization of outer space was a salient concern during negotiations of the OST, prompting the drafters to explicitly prohibit the placement of nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in orbit, on celestial bodies, or in void space.³ Other forms of traditional militarization were also considered and prohibited, including the establishment of military bases on the Moon and other celestial bodies.⁴ Additionally, the moon and other celestial bodies were designated exclusively for peaceful purposes rather than for military objectives.

While militarization through non-weaponized means has existed since the beginning of the Cold War, a clearer distinction has since been drawn between weaponization and militarization. Militarization has come to be known as “force enhancement including communications, navigational and intelligence gathering activity”.⁵ Weaponization, by contrast, involves the “proliferation, testing, deployment and use of weapons or counterspace capabilities located in or directed towards space or space systems.”⁶ While the OST addresses specific forms of weaponization, it is less clear regarding the placement of conventional weapons and the military uses of space. This ambiguity has brought about concerns that non-weaponized military space objects could easily be repurposed as weapons or become legitimate military targets during armed conflict.⁷

Militarization in outer space has been an international concern since before space launches became possible. At the height of the Cold War, as the US and Russia developed rocket and nuclear technologies in the early 1950s, they regarded these two technologies as working hand in hand to deliver missiles effectively into the heart of the enemy's territory.⁸ After the launch of Sputnik 1 in 1957, the US accelerated its development program and launched its first military-use surveillance satellite, Discoverer XIII, in 1960.⁹ As the concern of nuclear weapons

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. (2003). *Outer space and global security*. Page 3. United Nations. <https://unidir.org/files/publication/pdfs/outer-space-and-global-security-307.pdf>.

⁶ Space Security Lexicon. (n.d.). *Weaponization of Outer Space*. <https://spacesecuritylexicon.org/terminology/weaponization-of-outer-space>.

⁷ See, for example Farooqui, MO., Qureshi, T. (2024). *Outer space militarization and the emerging paradigm of weaponization: Implications for space security and international regulation*. Rev. Just. Rireito. Hein Online.

⁸ Sheposh, R. (2025). *Militarization of space*. EBSCO Knowledge Advantage. <https://www.ebsco.com/research-starters/military-history-and-science/militarization-space>.

⁹ Ibid.

in space rose throughout the 1960s, the international community came together to pass the Outer Space Treaty in 1967, effectively outlawing nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in outer space. While this treaty serves as the baseline for peaceful conduct in space, it does not expressly prohibit the use of conventional weapons or the militarization of satellites. Spacefaring and non-spacefaring nations alike have used satellites and other objects for military purposes such as surveillance and intelligence sharing. While militarization in outer space is unlikely to cease, it has evolved over the decades to reflect the current realities of space activities.

2.2. Militarization Through Dual-Use Satellites

Modern militarization is increasingly embodied in the integration of space infrastructure into military systems on Earth. Infrastructure becomes militarized through its function and integration into military systems, rather than through its physical design. Dual-use satellites, in particular, enable military effectiveness while remaining non-destructive in nature. In times of armed conflict, militarized infrastructure in the form of connectivity to satellites can act as a force multiplier.¹⁰ Secure communications enable distanced command and control, coordination of geographically dispersed units, and intelligence sharing, among many other capabilities. In the same vein, disruption of these services can significantly impair military effectiveness. As a result, modern militaries around the world have become increasingly reliant on uninterrupted access to reliable satellite communications.

2.3. The Role of Private Actors in Modern Militarization

The explosion of commercial activity in outer space has significantly contributed to this shift in how militarization is constituted today. Private actors now are the main providers of services that were once the exclusive domain of States, such as satellite communications, observation, and positioning. While satellites such as these are designed primarily for civilian purposes, they are inherently dual-use. Dual-use objects can be defined as an “item [which] has civilian applications and military, terrorism, weapons of mass destruction, or law-enforcement-related applications.”¹¹ Current dual-use satellites provide the infrastructure that can serve as weapons platforms and assist with cyber operations, without being weapons themselves.¹² For example, the Finnish company ICEYE owns the world’s largest synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite constellation.¹³ The images created by these satellites are high-resolution and capable of seeing through clouds, smoke, and at night. These satellites were originally endorsed as being used for detecting rapid changes on Earth’s surface, such as flood monitoring and tracking oil spills.¹⁴ Since the first launches of ICEYE’s satellites, they have been used for military purposes by several States’

¹⁰ Aberle, A. (2003). *Strategic force multiplier: The importance of space in the Army’s future*. Space Technology. <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA525762.pdf>.

¹¹ Export Control Reform Act, 50 USC § 4801(2). (2018). [https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=\(title:50%20section:4801%20edition:prelim\)](https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=(title:50%20section:4801%20edition:prelim)).

¹² Pražák, J. (2019). *Weaponization of outer space: Double-edged blade of dual-use technology*. [Master’s thesis, Charles University]. <https://dspace.cuni.cz/bitstream/handle/20.500.11956/107927/120331323.pdf?sequence=1>.

¹³ ICEYE. (n.d.). *About us*. <https://www.iceye.com/company>.

¹⁴ European Space Agency. (2021, December 20). *ICEYE, the world’s first SAR new space constellation*. <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/success-story/iceye-the-world-s-first-sar-new-space-constellation>.

militaries, illustrating how civilian systems can be operationally militarized while remaining legally classified as commercial space activities under international space law.¹⁵

Commercial entities have become particularly attractive partners for satellite use during armed conflict due to their scale of operations and rapid deployment capabilities. Partnerships with these private actors are also commercially beneficial for government entities, as services are generally provided through various channels, including commercial contracts and informal agreements. From a governmental perspective, reliance on commercial providers can reduce costs and accelerate access to advanced technologies. For these private corporations, such partnerships offer significant commercial benefits and market security.

Despite the mutual benefits to governments and private actors of using dual-use technologies for military purposes, this increasing reliance complicates regulatory assumptions at the heart of space law and the law of armed conflict. At the time of the drafting and negotiation of the OST, States were the primary actors in outer space, a fact reflected in these frameworks in the allocation of responsibility and the enforcement of compliance. The integration of commercial infrastructure into military operations blurs the distinction between civilian and military spheres, raising questions about neutrality and responsibility attribution. Commercial satellites that support one State's military operations may be perceived as targets by another State, thereby increasing the risk to civilians and other States. These blurring challenges the core principles of international space law and underscores the growing inadequacy of existing frameworks to address contemporary militarization in outer space.

3. STARLINK AND THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR AS AN ILLUSTRATIVE CASE

Armed conflicts of recent decades have underscored the growing significance of military reliance on commercially operated space systems. Among the most prominent and recent examples is SpaceX's Starlink usage during the Russia-Ukraine war. Starlink operates in low-Earth orbit to deliver low-latency broadband internet worldwide.¹⁶ According to Starlink's web page on the satellite technology of the constellation, the internet capabilities support "streaming, online gaming, video calls and more."¹⁷ While "more" is likely to be interpreted in a broad sense, streaming, online gaming, and video calls are primarily used in civilian contexts.

3.1. Starlink's Contributions to the Russia-Ukraine Conflict

Starlink had been pivotal for Ukraine in the earlier days of the conflict with Russia. On February 26, 2022, just two days after the start of the war, Ukraine's Minister of Digital Transformation asked SpaceX CEO Elon Musk via X to provide the country with Starlink services to provide stable communication for its civilians and government.¹⁸ On the same day, Musk tweeted that

¹⁵ ICEYE. (2025, September 10). *ICEYE launches the ISR Cell, bringing tactical space-based intelligence anywhere* [Press release]. <https://www.iceye.com/newsroom/press-releases/iceye-launches-the-isr-cell-bringing-tactical-space-based-intelligence-anywhere>.

¹⁶ Starlink. (n.d.). <https://starlink.com/>.

¹⁷ Technology. (n.d.). <https://starlink.com/technology>.

¹⁸ Fedorov, M. [@fedorovmykhailo]. (2022, February 26). @elonmusk, while you try to colonize Mars – Russia try to occupy Ukraine! [Post]. X. <https://x.com/FedorovMykhailo/status/1497543633293266944?s=20>.

Starlink services were now active in Ukraine with terminals en route.¹⁹ Two days later, 500 ground terminals arrived in Ukraine.²⁰ Ukrainian citizens were thus able to stay connected to friends and family online. Additionally, energy companies and hospitals were able to remain open and operational, providing essential services to Ukrainians.²¹

Not only did the Ukrainian civilian populace benefit substantially from Starlink's rapid integration, but the Ukrainian military also stood to gain significantly from these new capabilities. Troops used Starlink for reconnaissance, coordination of counterattacks, artillery fire direction, and drone-strike operations.²² The use of Starlink involved no transfer of ownership or formal incorporation into Ukraine's armed forces. Rather, a privately owned satellite system was integrated into military operations while remaining under SpaceX's commercial control. The resulting arrangement illustrates how dual-use space technologies can become central to military operations without formal legal incorporation into State-owned armed forces.

3.2. Legal Problems Arising from Starlink's Involvement in the War

Despite the rapid deployment of Starlink in Ukraine's military operations, this integration raises several complications for classifying the satellites. Although the satellites were neither designed nor registered for military purposes, their operational role in supporting Ukraine's armed forces challenges the assumption that classification depends solely on design or intent. This blurring is particularly significant in space, where satellite systems are increasingly difficult to distinguish between civilian and military uses. As a result, existing legal frameworks struggle to account for such systems, whose status may fluctuate based on function rather than classification.

This difficulty in classification, particularly for systems owned by private actors, is significant because it raises questions about the applicability of various international law frameworks. For instance, in the context of traditional terrestrial armed conflict, several treaties exist regarding international humanitarian law, targeting, responsibility, liability for damages, and neutrality. However, when private actors enter the scene, the application of international law becomes significantly ambiguous, and these actors can evade its application.

In the context of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, authorization was granted for Starlink to be deployed in Ukraine, but similar access was not permitted in Russia.²³ This gave a significant military advantage to Ukraine. Similarly, in September 2022, it was reportedly decided that Starlink's connection in Ukraine would be disrupted during a counteroffensive against Russian

¹⁹ Musk, E. [@elonmusk]. (2022, February 26). *Starlink service is now active in Ukraine. More terminals en route.* [Post]. X. <https://x.com/elonmusk/status/1497701484003213317>.

²⁰ Abels, J. (2024). Private infrastructure in geopolitical conflicts: The case of Starlink and the war in Ukraine. *European Journal of International Relations*, 30(4), 853. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540661241260653>.

²¹ Press, L. (2026, January 6). *Starlink in Ukraine: What three years of wartime connectivity taught us.* CircleID. <https://circleid.com/posts/starlink-in-ukraine-what-three-years-of-wartime-connectivity-taught-us>.

²² Private infrastructure in geopolitical conflicts, 853.

²³ Smith, E. (2024, February 12). *Musk denies selling Starlink terminals to Russia after Kyiv alleges their use in occupied areas.* CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/2024/02/12/musk-denies-selling-starlink-terminals-to-russia-after-kyiv-alleges-use.html>.

forces, resulting in the mission's failure.²⁴ This selective treatment by a private corporation, rather than by State command structures, during armed conflict raises numerous questions about how Starlink interacts with international humanitarian law, whether Starlink satellites could be legitimate targets of Russian counterstrikes, and whether Starlink or SpaceX could be held responsible or liable for damages.

3.3. *Starlink as an Illustration, not a Precedent*

Starlink's involvement in the Russia-Ukraine war is not unique when considering the role of private entities operating in space during armed conflict. The Gulf War in the 1990s is widely regarded as the first international conflict to rely heavily on commercially operated space-based infrastructure.²⁵ Reliance on private corporations' satellite systems has only increased during times of armed conflict.

The legal binds illustrated by Starlink's role in the Russia-Ukraine war bring to the fore a central challenge for international space law: when military operations are conducted through commercial systems beyond direct State ownership or control, determining who bears responsibility, and on what basis, becomes profoundly uncertain. This incoherence between operational reliance and legal attribution sets the stage for examining whether existing doctrines of State responsibility can meaningfully address the militarization of commercial space systems.

4. STATE RESPONSIBILITY UNDER INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW

4.1. *Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty*

Responsibility is not only a foundational concept in international space law; its application in outer space entails a novel consideration in international law: the role of private actors. Article VI of the OST explicitly sets out obligations relating to "non-governmental entities," which undoubtedly includes private actors. Article VI states:

States Parties to the Treaty shall bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, whether such activities are carried on by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities, and for assuring that national activities are carried out in conformity with the provisions set forth in the present Treaty. The activities of non-governmental entities in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, shall require authorization and continuing supervision by the appropriate State Party to the Treaty. When activities are carried on in outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, by an international organization, responsibility for compliance with this Treaty shall be borne both by the international organization and by the States Parties to the Treaty participating in such organization.²⁶

²⁴ Roulette, J., Bryan-Low, C., and T. Balmforth. (2025, July 25). *Musk ordered shutdown of Starlink satellite service as Ukraine retook territory from Russia*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/investigations/musk-ordered-shutdown-starlink-satellite-service-ukraine-retook-territory-ru-2025-07-25/>.

²⁵ Tepper, E. (2022). The first space-cyber war and the new for new regimes and policies. *Center for International Governance Innovation*, 173, 2. https://www.cigionline.org/static/documents/PB_no.173_uPqYILM.pdf.

²⁶ Outer Space Treaty. Article VI.

This article provides the basis for international responsibility in outer-space contexts, particularly for private entities. Since non-governmental entities lack legal standing under international space law, this article places the onus on the State to ensure that all activities undertaken by such entities comply with the provisions of the OST. Furthermore, the second sentence of Article VI imposes obligations on States to authorize and continuously supervise the activities of non-governmental entities, thereby ensuring that State responsibility is maintained throughout the activity's life cycle.

Under Article VI, the first criterion for its application is a State's violation of an obligation, rather than the occurrence of damage, either by failing to authorize national activities or by failing to maintain continuous supervision of the entity carrying out the activity. Secondly, attribution to a State must be established. Attribution under Article VI does not require operational control over each activity but instead emanates from the characterization of activities as “national” from both governmental and non-governmental actors. The OST does not define “national activities,” but rather only specifies that they are the activities of “governmental agencies” or “non-governmental entities.” This broad formulation deliberately avoids a control-based designation, instead extending responsibility to all activities attributable to a State’s governmental or non-governmental entities, thereby capturing private commercial operations within the scope of international responsibility.

4.2. States’ Obligations Posed by Article VI

Article VI imposes three obligations on State parties regarding the national activities of non-governmental entities. First, States must “assure” that national activities are carried out in conformity with the provisions set forth in the treaty.²⁷ The word “assure” implies that States must be certain that national activities comply with international law.²⁸ The OST does not provide specific instructions on how to achieve this assurance, but it is generally understood that this entails States regulating national activities and exercising due diligence to prevent harm to others.

The second obligation requires States to authorize national activities. As is common with terms in the OST, the treaty does not define “authorization,” nor does it specify how authorization is ensured. However, it is largely interpreted and implemented through domestic licensing requirements.²⁹ National agencies such as the US Federal Communications Commission (the FCC) and *France’s Centre National d’Études Spatiales* regulate this authorization, ensuring State compliance with the OST.

Finally, States must continually supervise national activities. This obligation is twofold. Firstly, the supervision must be constant throughout the life of the space activity. The second aspect is more open to interpretation. Again, silent on its definition, the OST does not specify what “supervision” entails, thereby leaving a large margin of appreciation to States. Using the FCC as an example, the agency maintains oversight of space activities by setting reporting requirements

²⁷ Outer Space Treaty. Article VI.

²⁸ *What obligations does the OST Article VI impose on states?* (n.d.). Marius. <https://www.sjorettsfondet.no/journal/2024/584/m-1776>.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

for space station operators and by requiring annual lists identifying satellites providing services.³⁰

4.3. State Responsibility in the Militarization Context

When considering the broader context of militarization in outer space, it is important to note that State responsibility persists regardless of military utility. It has been established that militarization is not inherently illegal under the provisions of the OST. Thus, responsibility can be triggered even when the use is lawful. Moreover, Article VI does not preclude the application of State responsibility for any reason, including the use of satellites owned by private operators during periods of armed conflict. The operation of such satellites would still fall under the definition of “national activities” carried out by a “non-governmental entity,” consequently compelling States to respect their obligations.

While Article IV of the OST provides the foundational principle for State responsibility regarding non-governmental space activities, it is not the only provision regulating potential or realized harms. Other frameworks of international law also attempt to regulate damages and conduct arising during armed conflict. However, these regimes rely on distinct and sometimes narrow assumptions that limit their effectiveness in addressing militarization through privately operated satellite systems.

5. THE LIMITS OF LIABILITY AND OTHER LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN ADDRESSING MILITARIZATION THROUGH SATELLITES OPERATED BY PRIVATE ACTORS

5.1. The Liability Convention

Outer space is governed by its own liability regime enshrined in the *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects of 1972* (Liability Convention). It should be noted here that while in certain languages, such as French and Spanish, the term “responsibility” encompasses what is in English responsibility and liability. Therefore, a distinction must be made. Responsibility is engaged for internationally wrongful acts and breaches of international obligations. Liability, on the other hand, refers to acts that are not illegal but nonetheless cause damage to others.

The Liability Convention provides a system for determining liability that is rather unique to international law. Traditionally, liability is determined by control. For example, Article 106 of the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea* (UNCLOS) states that in cases of maritime seizures, the “State making the seizure shall be liable to the State the nationality of which is possessed by the ship or aircraft for any loss or damage caused by the seizure.”³¹ However, the Liability Convention’s focus on ownership rather than control has created a regime that

³⁰ Applications for earth station authorizations, 47 CFR § 25.115, 1997. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-47/chapter-I/subchapter-B/part-25/subpart-B/subject-group-ECFR2bd70fc6b2eea0/section-25.115> and Space station point of contact reporting requirements, 47 CFR § 25.171, 2023. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-47/chapter-I/subchapter-B/part-25#25.117>.

³¹ United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, December 10, 1982, Article 106. https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

inaccurately reflects contemporary realities and may impose liability on States with no direct involvement in conflicts.

The Liability Convention operates under a dual-liability regime. The first pillar of liability is absolute liability, which concerns damage on the surface of the earth or to aircraft.³² The sole exception to this determination is found in Article VI, which exonerates a launching state from liability in cases of gross negligence or intentional damage-causing omissions done by a claimant State or its natural or juridical persons.³³

The second pillar centers on fault-based liability, which is enshrined in Article III, stating:

In the event of damage being caused elsewhere than on the surface of the earth to a space object of one launching State or to persons or property on board such a space object by a space object of another launching State, the latter shall be liable only if the damage is due to its fault or the fault of persons for whom it is responsible.³⁴

Several nuances must be considered here. Firstly, fault-based liability is attributed only if the damage is caused at a location other than the Earth's surface, thereby meaning on a celestial body, in Earth's orbit, or in void space. Additionally, the damage must occur to a space object or to persons or property on board a space object.

5.2. The Liability Convention's Difficulties in Addressing Militarization

Liability is ill-suited to address the questions that arise from Starlink's involvement in the Russia-Ukraine conflict and broader militarization. First, the definition of "damage" does not encompass the types of harm that may be caused by the use of satellites for military purposes. Article I of the Liability Convention defines "damage" as "loss of life, personal injury or other impairment of health; or loss of or damage to property of States or of persons, natural or juridical, or property of international intergovernmental organizations."³⁵ While definitions in international law can be extremely useful, this narrow definition does not address emerging forms of damage that have become crucial in the context of space activities, as it is limited to physical damage. It does not consider other types of indirect losses, such as environmental damage, economic losses, or, in the case of the Russia-Ukraine war, strategic losses.

Additionally, liability attribution further complicates matters when considering the given definition of "launching State." Per Article I of the Liability Convention, a launching State is either the "State which launches or procures the launching of a space object" or the "State from whose territory or facility a space object is launched."³⁶ In light of the Starlink illustration, the United States would be determined as the launching State in both senses of the definition, as the satellites are launched from the US. Following this reasoning, the US could be held liable for any

³² Conventino on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, March 29, 1972, Article II. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

³³ Liability Convention, Article II.

³⁴ Liability Convention, Article III.

³⁵ Liability Convention, Article I.

³⁶ Ibid.

damages that Ukraine inflicted upon Russia during the war, even though the US had no direct affiliation with the hostilities.

In the broader context of broader space militarization, the Liability Convention remains less effective than proactive measures to prevent damage caused by dual-use objects through State responsibility. Since the Liability Convention requires that harm have occurred for it to apply, liability is imposed too late and does little to prevent it. Moreover, compensation as provided for by the Convention does not deter States or private corporations from lawful military integration. Even where liability could theoretically be attributed, the Convention operates only after harm has occurred, offering no mechanism to constrain the integration of commercial systems into military operations *ex ante*.

5.3. Applications of International Humanitarian Law

Despite the apparent failures of the Liability Convention in the context of militarization through privately owned dual-use objects, adjacent international law applicable to armed conflict still poses complications. The application of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) provisions to outer-space operations during armed conflict has been the subject of debate for decades. This analysis rests on the assumption that the current body of IHL is sufficiently applicable to outer space, though it presents complications when attributing responsibility for privately operated dual-use satellites. IHL is ill-suited to regulate the normalization of military dependence on space infrastructure precisely because it presumes an act of violence rather than persistent infrastructural integration. Returning to the problem of classification, dual-use objects pose a central challenge. Under IHL provisions, civilian objects are protected under IHL that sit under the umbrella of the principle of distinction.³⁷ This principle obliges parties to a conflict to distinguish at all times between military and civilian objects and between combatants and civilians, and to direct operations only against military objectives.³⁸ However, when those objects are used for military purposes, they lose that protection.³⁹ The question of dual-use satellites and their protection under IHL becomes problematic because these space objects are inherently designed to serve both commercial and military purposes, even if military purposes are not their primary objective.

The principle of proportionality is also important here. This principle prohibits attacks that would cause disproportionate harm to civilians relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁴⁰ Proportionality works in corollary with the principle of distinction as it recognizes that incidental harm to civilians and civilian objects is unavoidable during armed conflict. Thus, it places a limit on the extent to which this harm is permissible.⁴¹ An attack on a dual-use satellite would likely cause significant communication disruptions, including loss of GPS navigation or even general internet access, over large geographic areas. Additionally, this principle would only apply once

³⁷ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949 and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I), June 8, 1977, Article 52. https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/external/doc/en/assets/files/other/icrc_002_0321.pdf.

³⁸ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949, Article 48.

³⁹ ICRC. (n.d.). Rule 10. Civilian objects' loss of protection from attack. *International Humanitarian Law Databases*. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/customary-ihl/v1/rule10>.

⁴⁰ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949. Article 57.

⁴¹ Berrang, S. (202, November 2). How would IHL apply to hostilities in outer space? *Humanitarian Law & Policy*. <https://blogs.icrc.org/law-and-policy/2023/11/02/how-would-ihl-apply-to-hostilities-in-outer-space/>.

an attack has manifested. However, militarization by dual-use satellites resists this application as it merely enables operations and shapes potential outcomes.

Further underscoring the inadequacy of existing international law, the fragmentation of these regimes just studied demonstrates their systemic failure to constrain the militarization of outer space. The Liability Convention lays the groundwork for compensatory measures for ex post damages, provided that certain conditions are met. IHL provisions are similarly reactive and specific to active armed conflicts, rather than to the incremental normalization of military dependence that often occurs outside these conflicts.

In light of this analysis, the limitations of these regimes highlight the need to shift the analytical focus toward State responsibility, which, although less enforceable, offers a broader framework for examining State obligations regarding privately operated space systems used in armed conflicts.

6. THE RESPONSIBILITY GAP

6.1. State Responsibility as a Better Suited Regime to Address Militarization

While liability and IHL principles respond to harm after it occurs or depend on narrow classifications, State responsibility, as outlined in Article VI of the OST, offers a broader, conduct-based regime that is better suited to addressing militarization through commercial space systems. However, the current responsibility framework remains underdeveloped and ambiguously applied, further failing to address militarization.

Despite the evident failures of adjacent international law, State responsibility remains a better framework for addressing concerns about militarization. Firstly, responsibility relies on the conduct of States. In contrast, the Liability Convention, for example, requires physical damage to have occurred to apply. In the context of Article VI of the OST, responsibility mirrors the applications found in general international law. It arises in cases involving violations of relevant legal obligations or wrongful acts, regardless of whether physical harm occurs.⁴² This differs greatly from liability, as it concerns only compensation for damages arising from acts that are not illegal.

Thus, responsibility is able to be engaged earlier, specifically before harm occurs. Under Article VI of the OST, responsibility is triggered by a State's failure to authorize or continuously supervise activities of non-governmental entities. In the context of Starlink and its integration into Ukraine's military forces, State responsibility could be applied more readily than liability or other IHL provisions. For instance, the US would be the State responsible for Starlink, as SpaceX is an American non-governmental entity. If the US were found to have failed to effectively authorize or supervise SpaceX's activities, one could argue that it had breached its obligations under Article VI of the OST, even before any damage would have occurred.

⁴² Von der Dunk, F. (1991). Liability versus responsibility in space law: Misconception or misconstruction? *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program Faculty Publications*, 43, 366. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1042&context=spacelaw>.

However, as the following paragraphs explain, State responsibility remains an inadequate framework for addressing militarization through dual-use satellites.

6.2. Shortcomings of Reliance on State Responsibility

One of the main issues undermining responsibility, particularly in the Starlink context, is attribution. General international law and the ILC's Draft Articles on State Responsibility for Internationally Wrongful Acts have been adopted and implemented by States over the decades, resulting in a clear regime of attribution for traditional tools used in armed conflict, even those owned by private enterprises.⁴³ In outer space, however, this attribution is significantly more difficult, particularly for dual-use systems. Considering the Starlink illustration, attribution becomes uncertain where operational decisions affecting military outcomes are made by a private operator rather than State instruction. In applications of general international law in which State control is the determining factor for attribution, private entities are excluded. Since Starlink was not formally transferred to Ukraine and remained under private control, responsibility would be nearly impossible to determine. Even with respect to Article VI of the OST, responsibility attribution challenges persist. Although responsibility is assigned to States for national activities, it does not offer guidance on when it should be applied when day-to-day operational decisions are exercised through private entities for military purposes.

Responsibility is also difficult to apply to militarization because it is not inherently illegal. Article VI requires States to ensure that non-governmental entities comply with the OST's provisions, including that space is used for the benefit and interest of all countries and is the province of all mankind. It is commonly understood that conducting peaceful activities in outer space does not exclude military applications for non-hostile purposes.⁴⁴ Dual-use satellites such as Starlink exemplify this difficulty. Even when used by Ukraine's armed forces for military purposes, Starlink satellites were not employed for aggressive or hostile activities in outer space; they merely facilitated terrestrial military operations. Thus, provided that the US authorized and supervised Starlink's operations, it could be argued that no obligation had been violated either by SpaceX or the US.

Furthermore, responsibility is additionally weak in addressing militarization due to the lack of enforcement mechanisms. On an international scale, enforcement can be difficult to achieve, especially if no mechanism exists in the violated legal framework. Generally, in public international law, enforcement centers on the cessation of the wrongful act and three forms of reparation (restitution, compensation, and satisfaction).⁴⁵ Otherwise, international enforcement is typically carried out through diplomatic means, where an injured State may bring claims against the injuring State or through countermeasures under certain constraints.⁴⁶

⁴³ Von der Dunk, F. (2024, July 26). Space privateers or space pirates? Armed conflict, outer space, and the attribution of no-state activities. *Articles of War*. <https://lieber.westpoint.edu/space-privateers-pirates-outer-space-attribution-non-state-activities/>.

⁴⁴ See for example, National Aeronautics and Space Council. (1959, December 17). NSC 5918/1. US policy on outer space. *Dwight D. Eisenhower Presidential Library and Museum*. <https://aerospace.csis.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/NSC-5918-US-Policy-on-Outer-Space.pdf>.

⁴⁵ Draft Articles on Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts, May 31, 2001, Articles 30-31 and 34-37. https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/draft_articles/9_6_2001.pdf.

⁴⁶ Draft Articles on Responsibility of States, Articles 48-49.

The shortcomings in State responsibility reveal a gap between the legal design of international space law and the realities of contemporary military practice. As commercial actors increasingly provide the infrastructure upon which military effectiveness depends, the absence of clear regulatory constraints enables militarization to expand through privatized systems with limited accountability. The concluding section reflects on the broader implications of this mismatch and considers how the evolving role of commercial space infrastructure challenges the foundational assumptions of international space law.

7. CONCLUSION

The increasing integration of commercial space infrastructure into military operations marks a shift in the militarization of outer space. Unlike earlier forms of militarization centered on weapons deployment or military installations, modern militarization relies on infrastructure and is often indistinguishable from civilian use. Privately operated dual-use satellite systems now serve as enablers of military forces, reshaping strategic realities on Earth while remaining formally classified as civilian space activities under international law.

This study has shown that the current legal frameworks do little to address the growing normalization of militarization through dual-use systems owned by corporate entities. The Liability Convention offers a narrow, damage-based regime that applies only *ex post* and fails to consider the types of strategic harm generally connected to military reliance on commercial satellites. International humanitarian law, while essential during active hostilities, is similarly reactive and ill-equipped to regulate the normalization of military dependence on space infrastructure. Its reliance on object classification and armed conflict operations leaves significant gaps when applied to dual-use systems operating beyond traditional conceptions of warfare.

Considering this context, State responsibility under Article VI of the OST arises as the most conceptually appropriate framework for addressing militarization through privately operated space systems. Unlike liability regimes, responsibility focuses on State conduct and can be engaged regardless of physical damage. It imposes obligations on States to authorize and continuously supervise the space activities of non-governmental entities, offering a foundation for addressing military integration *ex ante*. However, this framework remains underdeveloped and ambiguously applied. Difficulties of attribution, the permissibility of militarization under the OST, and the absence of enforcement mechanisms undermine its effectiveness.

These shortcomings result in a responsibility gap in which States can externalize military functions to commercial actors to evade effective legal accountability. Starlink should therefore be understood not as an exceptional case, but as a cautionary tale. As commercial space actors continue to expand their role in global connectivity and security, the mismatch between legal principles and operational reality will only deepen. Without clearer articulation and enforcement of State responsibility, the militarization of outer space through commercial infrastructure risks becoming normalized and legally unchecked, thus reshaping the strategic environment in ways international space law is currently not designed to address.

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EUROPEAN UNION’S SPACE ACT’S “RIGHT OF WAY” RULES: DRIVING THE FUTURE OF ORBITAL TRAFFIC

ASHLING SUGARMAN¹

ABSTRACT

Article 103(3)(a)-(g) of the European Union’s proposed Space Act lists seven factors to determine which actor must move when avoiding a collision. Though Article 103(3) explicitly states that the list is non-exhaustive, the provision is otherwise silent regarding the interpretation of the factors. A sequential interpretation allows for each point to be considered in a simple method by starting with (a) and ending with (g). However, Article 103(3) is unclear whether it can or should be interpreted sequentially. This paper evaluates Article 103(3)(a)-(g) by combining textual analysis with technical considerations and using long-standing principles from aviation and maritime law. In finding Article 103(a)-(g) lacks practicality for sequential interpretation, this paper proposes a re-ordering of the factors (a)-(g). This new order of factors allows for sequential application when determining which actor has the right-of-way in a collision avoidance manoeuvre. Accompanying each of the seven factors is a rule statement for operators’ use during a potential collision.

The purpose of right-of-way rules is to provide space actors with predictability in their operations. Resolving conjunction events on an ad-hoc basis threatens operator efficiency and cannot be scaled to larger systems such as constellations. The EU Space Act tasks “Collision Avoidance Space Services Providers” with resolving operator disputes and deciding on a manoeuvre strategy when a collision is imminent. Given this time-sensitive mission, there must be a clear understanding of Article 103(3). Additionally, clarifying the language and application of Article 103(3) reinforces the EU’s sovereignty because comprehensible and effective regulations are more likely to become a global standard.

KEYWORDS: Right-of-way, Space Traffic Management, Orbital Rules, European Union Space Law, Collision Avoidance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The 2009 collision between the American satellite, Iridium-33, and the Russian satellite, Kosmos 2251, evidences the threat of orbital collisions, becoming a real concern among space actors.² In the worst-case scenario, a collision could obliterate a satellite, rendering it defunct and creating thousands, if not hundreds-of-thousands, of debris objects.³ In the best-case scenario, a satellite operator can proactively conduct a Collision Avoidance Manoeuvre (CAM)⁴ to reduce the risk of collision, but such manoeuvres interrupt satellite service and expend vital fuel reserves.⁵ This means that CAMs are an expensive endeavour, costing about 5-10% of total mission costs.⁶

In a potential collision, satellite operators must therefore decide between conducting a CAM or allowing their satellite to collide with another. Incentivized to preserve satellite operations and prevent a collision, the question for operators then becomes: *which* satellite should move?

Right-of-way (ROW) rules, or “rules of the road,” guide the decision of “who has the right to stay a course and who has the obligation to move out of the way to avoid a collision.”⁷ In the context of space activities, the operator with the ROW maintains course,⁸ and the operator conducting the CAM is “giving-way.”

Dictating who has the right to move in a collision path fits under a larger traffic management system, known as Space Traffic Management (STM). Though a definition has yet to be internationally recognized, nonetheless codified, the European Union has defined STM as: “an approach to safely and sustainability enter into, conduct activities in, and return from outer space.”⁹

² European Space Agency, (n.d.) *About space debris*, Space Safety, retrieved 5 October 2025, from https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/About_space_debris (Iridium-33 and Kosmos 2251 collided at a speed of 11.7km/s, destroying both satellites and creating more than 23,000 trackable debris fragments).

³ Foust, J., SpaceNews, *Potential Satellite Collision Shows Need for Active Debris Removal*, (January 29, 2020) (the conjunction of two upper stages at 981 kilometres would create between 3,375 and 12,860 objects at least 5 to 10 centimetres in size and more than 200,000 debris objects at least 1 centimetre in size).

⁴ “‘Collision avoidance’ means the execution of collision avoidance manoeuvres to reduce the risk of collision in outer space.” European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 5 point 36 at 42, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD).

⁵ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) at 138, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf.

⁶ OECD (2022), *Earth’s Orbits at Risk: The Economics of Space Sustainability*, at 31, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/16543990-en>.

⁷ Frandsen, H. O., (2023), *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 299, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>. See Chen, Y., Lai, Z., Li, H., et al., (2023, Oct. 2-6), *A Networking Perspective on Starlink’s Self-Driving LEO Mega-Constellation* [Conference Article], at 3, ACM MobiCom ’23: Proceedings of the 29th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking, Madrid, Spain, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3570361.3592519>, (Orbital manoeuvres “use the satellite’s propulsion system to raise/lower altitude, change speeds, or adjust its orbital inclination angles.”).

⁸ See *infra* note 52 (The terminology of “maintaining course” is intentional and reflects principles of maritime law.).

⁹ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022), *Pilot Project on Space Traffic Management: The Rise of Importance of Space Traffic Management (STM) Final Report*, at 26, Publications Office of the European Union.

Currently, no ROW or STM framework exists.¹⁰ The issue is self-evident: without ROW rules, efficiency is hampered because actors must resolve each potential collision on a case-by-case basis. Best described by Hjalte Osborn Frandsen: “Imagine if every time you met another car at an intersection, you had to get out and coordinate with the other driver, about who should go first.”¹¹ The process is further complicated, considering that an operator must be able to correctly identify whose spacecraft is on the conjunction event before initiating contact.¹² Then, once the owner or operator of the spacecraft is identified, communication between the two typically uses ad hoc methods like e-mails or phone calls.¹³ In total, the lack of a ROW or STM framework translates into a multi-step problem demanding significant resources and time.

The European Union’s Space Act provides a solution in Article 103(3), which lists seven factors to be taken into consideration when determining which operator in a potential collision has the ROW:

- (a) Protection of Crew Vehicle;
- (b) Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation;
- (c) Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres
- (d) State of the Spacecraft;
- (e) Eccentricity of the Spacecraft’s Orbits;
- (f) Age of the Spacecraft; and
- (g) Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.¹⁴

When there is a significant chance of collision between satellites, known as a High Interest Event (HIE),¹⁵ operators must discuss who should conduct the CAM.¹⁶ Typically, a significant chance of collision is denoted as a Probability of Collision (PoC) of 1E-4.¹⁷ This means that if a satellite’s trajectory is within 1

¹⁰ Oltrogge, D. L., Christensen, I. A., (9–12 December 2019), *Space Governance in the New Space Era*, [First International Orbital Debris Conference] IOC 2019 Conference, Sugar Land, Texas, United States, <https://www.hou.usra.edu/meetings/orbitaldebris2019/orbital2019paper/pdf/6013.pdf>, 7.4 Space Governance Gap Analysis, Table 1, (“Rules-of-the-road” are a “gap” in space governance). See National Space Society, (6 May 2025), *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf, at 1 (“[A]n international space traffic coordination system is elusive.”).

¹¹ Frandsen, 2023, at 302. Hjalte Osborn Frandsen is a PhD Fellow from the University of Copenhagen.

¹² European Commission, (15 February 2022), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 11, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>, (“[A]ll satellite operators providing services within the EU should register with a collision avoidance service . . . to ensure timely responses and coordinated collision avoidance manoeuvres.”).

¹³ See *infra* section 1.2 Lack of Governing Structure (To resolve a conjunction between the ESA’s Aerolius and SpaceX’s Starlink, the operators communicated via email).

¹⁴ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3), at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁵ HIE “means close approaches with a high level of risk, potentially requiring collision avoidance manoeuvres to be performed by a space operator.” European Commission (2025), Space Act, at 43.

¹⁶ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, at 43.

¹⁷ See Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), *Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management*, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf. See also American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice C-2: Perform CA Risk Assessment to

kilometre (0.62 miles) of another, thus rendering a 1 in 10,000 chance of collision, operators must discuss CAMs to mitigate the likelihood of a collision.¹⁸

If a resolution between operators can't be made within a "reasonable time," the process turns over to a "Collision Avoidance Space Services Provider" (CASSP).¹⁹ The CASSP is tasked with proposing a strategy based on Article 103(3)(a)-(g), shown above.²⁰ The text of Article 103(3) clarifies that the CASSP's strategy is not limited to the provided seven elements, but at bottom, the CASSP must take all seven elements into account. In practice, this means Article 103(3) is not exhaustive, but the CASSP must base their strategy on the considerations provided in Article 103(3)(a)-(g). Throughout this paper, references to "operators" can include CASSPs, but references to "CASSPs" only address CASSPs.

1.1. Proliferation of Space Objects

As space activity increases, the risk of collision between spacecraft will undoubtedly follow.²¹ This is especially true in the context of constellations, where hundreds or thousands of spacecrafts are clustered together to form one "mega-constellation" or "giga-constellation."²² One of the more notable constellations, SpaceX's Starlink, conducted 144,404 CAMs between December 2024 and May 2025, averaging one manoeuvre every 1.8 minutes.²³ In a constellation, not only does the risk of collision exist with other orbiting objects, but collisions can occur within the constellation itself, known as an "intra-collision" risk. This dual risk is too much for an operator to manage, and thus, automated CAM systems are used.²⁴

With space operations increasing in frequency, European stakeholders are feeling the heat: 72.7% strongly agree that there is a "growing risk for collision stemming from an intensification of space activities."²⁵ With more actors in orbit, the probability of a collision between any two objects increases. For instance, a data model determined that each year, a satellite can expect over one-million potential encounters.²⁶ Of these one-million encounters, nearly 25,000 are considered HIE.²⁷

The population swell in Earth's orbit increases the frequency of conjunction alerts, making it difficult for operators to parse out real threats. As referenced above, the 2009 collision between Iridium-33 and

Identify High-Risk Conjunctions That Require Mitigation, at 12 (supporting the use of PoC of 1E-4 for baseline assessments and the use of 1E-05 for conservative assessments).

¹⁸ Szondy, D., (2025, August 26), *ESA Applies CREAM to Tackle Growing Space Debris Threat*, New Atlas, <https://newatlas.com/space/esa-cream-space-debris/>.

¹⁹ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, at 41, 105, (In the EU, the EU-Space Surveillance and Tracking (SST) Programme provides collision avoidance (CA) services.)

²⁰ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article 103(3), at 105.

²¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (June 2023), *UNOOSA and ESA Release Updated Infographics About Space Debris*, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/informationfor/media/unoosa-and-esa-release-infographics-and-podcasts-about-space-debris.html>.

²² See European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article V (Definitions).

²³ O'Callaghan, J., (1 October 2025) *Heavy Traffic Ahead*, Aerospace America, <https://aerospaceamerica.aiaa.org/features/heavy-traffic-ahead/#:~:text=Mega%20numbers,from%2012%2C000%20to%2042%2C000%20satellites>.

²⁴ See section 4.6 Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation.

²⁵ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Impact Assessment Report* (Annex Report 2) at 16, SWD(2025) 335 Final, Part 2/2.

²⁶ Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), *Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management*, at 17, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (Space population as of 2 April 2023 and detected at a significance of $P_c > 1E-7$).

²⁷ *Ibid.* (Space population as of 2 April 2023, plus 34,000 satellites to represent the expected population of SpaceX's Starlink and Amazon's Kupier satellites with a significance detection of $P_c > 1E-4$).

Cosmos 2251 decimated both spacecrafts.²⁸ The estimated PoC between the two satellites was around 3 in 100,000—about one-third of the HIE manoeuvre threshold (1 in 10,000).²⁹ Not only was the PoC not significant enough to warrant a CAM, but this was one of thirty-seven other conjunctions that week.³⁰ From the operators’ perspective, it was a needle in a haystack: “the conjunction which eventually led to an actual disastrous collision did not stand out of the lot.”³¹

It is impractical for operators to respond to every conjunction alert. Operators must focus on the potential collisions with the highest risk, and once identified, each CAM requires careful planning to implement. The last thing an operator needs is a “secondary conjunction,” which occurs when the original CAM puts the spacecraft back into harm’s way, this time with a higher risk of collision with a second object. For instance, if spacecraft B conducts a CAM to avoid collision with spacecraft A, a secondary conjunction would result in spacecraft B’s CAM creating another collision risk, but this time with spacecraft C.

Whether or not an automated CAM system is used to alleviate the operator’s burden, all CAMs reduce the lifetime of the hardware itself, because a satellite needs to expend extra fuel to conduct a manoeuvre. It follows that the more conjunction events that occur, the more CAMs a satellite needs to conduct, and the less life a system gets. Moreover, when conducting a CAM, the satellite turns its instruments off, causing an interruption in service or “missed science and data” collection.³² The cost of a CAM is comprised of the meticulous planning of operators, reduced lifetime of spacecraft, and interruption in service.

Given the price to conduct a CAM and the high frequency of conjunction events, spacecraft operators are incentivized to conduct CAMs only when there is a true emergency. In such a scenario, the countdown to collision will be quick, so operators must act fast.

1.2. *Lack of Governing Structure*

In 2019, the European Space Agency’s (ESA) Aeolus satellite had a 1 in 50,000 PoC with a Starlink satellite. As time continued, the PoC increased to 1 in 10,000. Reacting to the HIE alert, ESA operators reached SpaceX via email, but these communications were left unanswered.³³ Ultimately, Aeolus conducted a CAM and successfully prevented a collision between the two satellites.³⁴

The situation between Aeolus and Starlink illustrates the ad-hoc nature of collision-avoidance communications. There are no shared protocols for collision avoidance procedures, so each operator is forced to resolve conjunction events through phone calls or e-mails.³⁵ Although remedying a HIE is in both party’s interest, a spam filter on one’s phone could mean the difference between a successful CAM or a catastrophic collision.

Not only is the mode of communication subject to improvement, but without an instruction manual to guide the conversation, the discussions between operators across the world can vary in transparency and collaboration. Operators might be less willing to divulge information about their spacecraft, citing proprietary or national security concerns. And given the cost of conducting a CAM, operators might be less willing to offer to move.

²⁸ European Space Policy Institute, (January 2020), *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*, at 26.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² *Ibid.*

³³ European Space Policy Institute, (January 2020), at 27, (“[A]fter the event became public, SpaceX blamed a bug in the company’s warning system, which prevented the operator from seeing the follow-on correspondence on this probability increase.”).

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297–318, at 299, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

When time is of the essence, operators are forced to evaluate a conjunction event based on their subjective analysis and employ negotiation tactics to determine who should have the ROW.³⁶ Far from efficient, the orbital terrain is likened to a present-day “Wild West”³⁷ where the incentivized behaviours are those in one’s self-interest.³⁸ In such a volatile environment, the predictability of operations is nearly non-existent.³⁹

1.3. *The Need for Right-of-Way (ROW) Rules*

ROW rules minimize the need for “individual and frequent negotiations,” allowing CASSPs to resolve conjunction events without engaging in operator-to-operator negotiations or contracting into bilateral agreements.⁴⁰ The less coordination required between actors equates to a lower transaction cost for participants.⁴¹ Therefore, a ROW framework “is essential for safe and economic operations in any traffic domain with many uncoordinated participants and no central actor coordinating the traffic.”⁴² By making behaviour predictable, the risk associated with space activities is reduced.⁴³

Given the time-sensitive nature of a HIE, “a standardised procedure on rules of the road should be established.”⁴⁴ ROW rules would alleviate the stress on operators during HIE alerts, enabling spacecraft operators to focus on the conjunction events that matter. “The requirement for a satellite to execute an avoidance manoeuvre resulting from a conjunction alert implies a regulatory mandate.”⁴⁵

³⁶ Frandsen, H. O., (2021, Oct. 25-29), *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 7, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854>.

³⁷ Vasile, M. & Wilson, A., (2023), The Space Sustainability Paradox, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 423, 138869, at 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138869> (“[S]pace is becoming like the Wild West and no one can be held legally accountable for their actions.”).

³⁸ Frandsen, 2021, at 8 (“[I]ndividual actors will be incentivised to make [] bilateral arrangements to ensure the safe and efficient handling of conjunctions. Such agreements . . . will not necessarily improve the overall sustainability and safety for the orbital domain.”).

³⁹ For States, this causes an additional issue. See *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty) art. VI, VII, 19 December 1966, 610 U.N.T.S. 205 (States are internationally liable for damage to another State Party caused by domestic, non-government space activities.); *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention) art. III, 29 March 1972, 961 U.N.T.S. 187 (Liability for collisions in orbit are apportioned according to fault).

⁴⁰ See *supra* note 38. See also European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article 103(1)(c), at 105, (Bilateral agreements between operators can contractually designate which spacecraft will have the ROW. In enforcing contractual obligations, the risk cannot be externalized to third parties through no secondary conjunctions.); see also American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice C-3: Pursue Adequate Mitigation Actions to Avoid High-Risk Conjunctions, at 13, (“Ensure that the selected mitigation action does not create any additional conjunctions that both exceed the high-risk threshold and that cannot subsequently be mitigated”).

⁴¹ Frandsen, H., (2021, Oct. 25-29), *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 2, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854> (Transaction costs are lowered “for participants in a system by eliminating or reducing the need for frequent coordination between actors.”)

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ Council of the European Union, (5 December 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience, and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union (EU Space Act)* (Annex), 2025/0335 (COD), 16437/25, Point (62c) at 21.

⁴⁵ Stilwell, R. E., (16 January 2018), *UTM, ATM, STM . . . slices of the sky?* [Conference Presentation], Section 2.3.4. Barriers, Space Traffic Management Conference, 2018 Seeking Sustainable Solutions, Daytona Beach, Florida, United States, <https://commons.erau.edu/stm/2018/presentations/5>.

2. ARTICLE 103(3) ANALYSIS: EVALUATION OF AN IMPLICIT HIERARCHY

Although the text of Article 103(3) specifies that the factors are not exhaustive, the text is silent regarding their exact interpretation. A natural assumption is to apply the factors sequentially by considering each point one-by-one, starting with (a) and ending with (g). Sequential interpretation is likely preferred because of its common-sense use, simple structure, and ease in application, but it is unclear whether Article 103(3) can or should be interpreted sequentially.

Determining whether Article 103(3) can or should be applied sequentially is especially necessary because failing to adhere to Article 103(3) is a breach of a CASSPs obligation.⁴⁶ If a CASSP fails to apply Article 103(3) properly, they will be subject to liability.⁴⁷ The EU's laudable effort in creating a ROW framework is eclipsed by uncertainty: is there a sequential hierarchy in Article 103(3)?

2.1. Textual Interpretation

The Article 103(3) factors are examined in light of the surrounding text, technical considerations, and principles in maritime and aviation law.⁴⁸ The advantage of this approach is its inclusion of equitable considerations, like fairness, which have permeated maritime and aviation law but otherwise might be overshadowed by a strict technical approach. The drawback of this approach is that it can lead to unwarranted conclusions, since the factors are not expressly defined.

The primary obstacle in evaluating the Article 103(3) factors is the lack of a clear definition. Although the interpretation of factor (a), “*the protection of a crewed vehicle*,” is straightforward, other factors fail to define key terms. The lack of textual clarity makes it difficult to maintain the intention of the original drafters.⁴⁹

It is helpful to analogize to maritime and aviation law for the formulation of ROW rules because these domains have successfully utilized rule-based approaches in traffic management.⁵⁰ The respective

⁴⁶ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex X, Point 5.2, at 35, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf (“A collision avoidance space service provider infringes . . . Article 103(3), first subparagraph, by failing to base the strategy of action on the principles laid down in the first subparagraph.”)

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ Bertrand, R., Michel, M., (20–23 April 2021), *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (“Rule-based approaches have the potential to be a feasible solution to determine what operator has to initiate an avoidance manoeuvre in case of a potential collision between two manoeuvrable satellites”).

⁴⁹ Without supplemental explanation, the interpretation of Article 103(3) varies. Subjective interpretation makes it difficult to understand exactly what circumstances the Article 103(3)(a)-(g) factors are intended to alleviate or circumvent. Thus, it is difficult to construct a ROW rule that maintains the intention of the original drafters. For example, in Article 103(3)(g) “Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission,” a rule for a “payload launch” would be: *In case of conjunction, the spacecraft launching with a payload must give-way to in-orbit spacecraft*. An example for a “navigation satellite” would be: *In case of conjunction, the spacecraft providing navigation service is responsible for staying on course unless the other spacecraft is providing communication services*. Both “payload launch” and “navigation satellite” address the phase and the type of the mission, but by changing the interpretation of Article 103(3)(g), it alters the ROW rule. Both ROW rules stated here stem from the text of Article 103(3)(g), yet they are completely different: one describes the ROW for launching payloads, the other describes in-orbit spacecraft providing services. The risk of interpreting Article 103(3) is the potential for error.

⁵⁰ *See supra* note 48 (“Potential technological barriers to implementation [of rule-based approaches to traffic management] are low, and the approach is known and proven in other traffic domains.”). *See also* Ligor, D. C., McClintock, B., McCormick, D., (25 June 2023), Rand Corporation, *Cross-Domain Lessons for Space Traffic Management: An Analysis of Air and Maritime Treaty Governance Mechanisms*, Research Report, “Key Findings,”

maritime and aviation industry “flourished by virtue of stable, internationally accepted rules, which regulate navigation.”⁵¹ The same can be accomplished in the space industry.

In summary, the following trifecta is utilized in the evaluation of Article 103(3)(a)–(g): (1) textual interpretation; (2) technical considerations; and (3) maritime and aviation law.⁵²

2.2. Maritime Background

Promulgated by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea* (1994) (UNCLOS) sets forth binding international maritime law.⁵³ The *International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea* (1972) (COLREG) provide the “rules of the road” for maritime navigation. Both are widely known instruments in the context of maritime law, making it a useful comparison to space law.⁵⁴ Space lawyers can essentially “adopt” legal principles that have “proved beneficial to commerce on the oceans” for use and application in space law.⁵⁵ For space regulations to be as long-lasting and globally appreciated as UNCLOS, “space lawyers need some appreciation of maritime law.”⁵⁶

Maritime law designates ships as either give-way vessels or stand-on, each attributed with respective obligations when avoiding a collision.⁵⁷ “Give-way vessels have the obligation to manoeuvre and stay out of the way. Stand-on vessels have the obligation to maintain course and speed and only manoeuvre if needed to avoid collision.”⁵⁸

Space and maritime law have similarities and differences. As to the former, the space and maritime industry mirror each other in the rising demand for traffic system stability.⁵⁹ Like the revolutionary advancement of cargo ships, features like New Space⁶⁰ and reusable rocket systems are driving the demand for STM.⁶¹ There are important distinctions between the two domains. Maritime law originated between 900 and 300 BCE, evolving at common law for hundreds of years, whereas space law is new and

www.rand.org/t/RRA2208-2, (“Elements of the ICAO [International Civil Aviation Organization] and IMO [International Maritime Organization] governance frameworks may serve as analogues for the creation of an international space traffic management organization”).

⁵¹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). *Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport)*, *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 94.

⁵² Ultimately, the advantage of this trifecta approach outweighs the disadvantage because it is flexible and equitable for considerations that are outside the scope of this paper but nonetheless might be important (such as determining what behaviours to incentivize).

⁵³ See *infra* note 85. The binding nature of UNCLOS comes from its status as customary international law (CIL). Once CIL, obligations are binding on all states, regardless of ratification status.

⁵⁴ DeSaussure, H., (1981), *Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport)*, *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 103, (“[Space lawyers] need to become conversant with basic admiralty rules . . . It is with this perspective that they can compare the two environments”).

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ Frandsen, H. O., (2023), *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol. 48(3), 297–318, at 306, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (“The requirement for stand-on vessels to refrain from manoeuvring is there to maximize predictability for the manoeuvring vessel.” The use of obligations, rather than rights, in right-of-way rules is adopted from COLREGS).

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). *Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport)*, *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 93.

⁶⁰ European Commission, (10 March 2023), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence* at 4 footnote 11, JOIN(2023) 9 final, Brussels, Belgium, (“New Space” refers to the economic change regarding space initiatives, specifically the low cost and high return relationship, encouraging involvement and resulting in significantly more space actors).

⁶¹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). *Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts: An Oceanic View of Space Transport*, *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 93.

thus lacks comparable precedent.⁶² Additionally, a vessel operating in the sea makes two-dimensional manoeuvres, but spacecraft in Earth’s orbit makes three-dimensional manoeuvres. Not only are the dimensions different, but operating a spacecraft in orbit is counterintuitive; to move a spacecraft into a higher orbit, an operator must slow the velocity of the spacecraft and vice versa.

Other objects in space are tracked and reported in Space Situational Awareness (SSA) data.⁶³ Because operators are unable to visually determine if they are on a conjunction path, they must rely on SSA capabilities to inform them of their surroundings. On the seas, however, COLREGS Rule 5 mandates that “[e]very vessel shall at all times maintain a proper look-out by sight and hearing . . . so as to make a full appraisal of the situation and of the risk of collision.”⁶⁴ The comparison between situational input mechanisms—SSA data or visual sight—underscores the importance of accurate SSA data for spacecraft operators.

The domains of space and maritime traffic management are nevertheless entwined: “[I]n the case of re-entry, the space object might end up in the sea, carrying implications for sea traffic management.”⁶⁵

2.3. Aviation Background

The interconnectedness of Aviation Traffic Management (ATM) and STM is already recognized within the EU.⁶⁶ Given the proximity of airspace and space, developing an STM approach “cannot be in complete isolation from existing conventions at the airspace level.”⁶⁷ The origin of aviation law occurred at the *Convention on International Civil Aviation* (1948) (Chicago Convention) with the creation of the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). The Chicago Convention is not customary international law (CIL),⁶⁸ but the domestic principles are largely based on the Chicago Convention.⁶⁹ Notably, Annex 2 in the Chicago Convention contains the ROW rules, which are regarded as mandatory because “safe and efficient air travel requires internationally uniform traffic rules.”⁷⁰

⁶² & Bedigian, LLC, *History of Maritime Law*, accessed September 23, 2025 (<https://www.gilmanbedigian.com/history-of-maritime-law>). See Vasile, M. & Wilson, A., (2023), The Space Sustainability Paradox, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 423, 138869, at 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138869> (“[T]he legal systems we have in place regarding space are nowhere near as comprehensive as in other spheres such as maritime law”).

⁶³ SpaceWays (May 2022). *First STM Brief: A Congested Space and its Safety*, at 3 (Space Situational Awareness (SSA) is defined as, “A holistic approach, including comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the main space hazards, encompassing collision between space objects, fragmentation, and re-entry of space objects into the atmosphere, space weather events, and near-Earth objects”).

⁶⁴ International Maritime Organization (1972). *Convention on the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea*, (COLREG) (1972), Rule 5. See Baldauf, M., Benedict, K., Fischer, S., Motz, F., & Schröder-Hinrichs, J-U., (11 April 2011), Collision Avoidance Systems in Air and Maritime Traffic, *Journal of Risk and Reliability*, vol. 225, doi: 10.1177/1748006X11408973, 333–343, at 334, (23% of maritime collisions are caused by poor look-out).

⁶⁵ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022). *Pilot Project on Space Traffic Management: The Rise of Importance of Space Traffic Management (STM) Final Report*, at 236, Publications Office of the European Union.

⁶⁶ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), at 3, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (Regulation (EU) 376/2014 sets forth a mandatory reporting scheme for incidents at the intersection between aviation and space activities.).

⁶⁷ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022), at 236.

⁶⁸ See *supra* note 53; see also *infra* note 85.

⁶⁹ Article I of the Chicago Convention reaffirms the following principle: “every State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory.”

⁷⁰ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 308, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

The Chicago Convention, like COLREGS, outlines ROW rules for aircraft. Chapter 3.2.2 starts the “right-of-way” regulations and states: “The aircraft that has the right-of-way shall maintain its heading and speed.”⁷¹ When two aircraft are heading directly towards each other, both aircrafts must manoeuvre to the right to avoid a collision.⁷² An exception to this rule is provided in Chapter 3.2.2.3 with a “pecking order” that stimulates what kind of aircraft must give way. As one example: “power-driven aircraft shall give way to aircraft which are seen to be towing other aircraft or objects.”⁷³ Also, when approaching to land, aircraft must give-way to those at lower altitudes.⁷⁴

2.4. ROW Rule Statement and Decision Matrix

Herein, the Article 103(3) factors are presented with a ROW rule statement, designating which spacecraft has the ROW and which must give way. The rules are then combined to form the Decision Matrix, a visual guide to understanding how the rule statements work together.⁷⁵ When proposing CAMs, the CASSP should refer to the Decision Matrix to decide who receives the ROW.

The operators themselves can use the ROW rules, before CASSP involvement is necessary. As a reminder, CASSP involvement is triggered when operators are unable to find a solution in a “reasonable time.”⁷⁶ It’s worth mentioning, however, that some spacecraft data is argued to be proprietary, and therefore, it won’t be available to other operators. In such a situation, CASSP involvement might be necessary.

CASSPs are third-party neutrals who can rectify disagreements between operators. But once a situation demands CASSP involvement, a CASSP will be under immense time pressure to render a strategy decision. Time cannot be spent interpreting Article 103(3). This paper provides rules for each factor under Article 103(3). Assuming textual interpretation and technical considerations are correct, these rules should properly embody the Article 103(3) elements and their application to the ROW analysis.

2.5. Limitations on Article 103(3)

The Space Act imposes several key restraints on Article 103, which are adopted as general parameters in this paper. The first limitation is in Article 103(1), which specifies that the Article only applies to HIEs between two manoeuvrable spacecraft.⁷⁷ This limitation effectively omits objects like space debris from the discussion, since they completely lack manoeuvrability capacity.⁷⁸ Second, Article 2 states that the Space Act does not apply to military spacecrafts.⁷⁹ Third, per Point 5.2 Title X in the Annex, proposed CAMs must comply with the following principles:

- (a) Take the utmost account of the protection of crewed vehicles;⁸⁰
- (b) Reduce the initial collision risk by at least one order of magnitude below the manoeuvre threshold for High Interest Event Alert; and
- (c) Not create unreasonable risks of secondary conjunctions.⁸¹

Point (a) mirrors Article 103(3)(a) in its recognition of crewed vehicles. This is further evaluated in Section 2.1 Crewed Vehicles, presented below. Point (b) regards itself with the outcome of the CAM by

⁷¹ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.

⁷² Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.2.

⁷³ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.3(d).

⁷⁴ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.5.2.

⁷⁵ The Decision Matrix is presented in Section 5 Right-of-Way (ROW) Decision Matrix.

⁷⁶ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 103(3), at 105.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Where relevant, considerations of non-maneuvrable spacecraft are briefly addressed. See section 4.5 Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres.

⁷⁹ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 2(3)(a)&(b), at 38.

⁸⁰ See section 4.1 Protection of Crew Vehicle.

⁸¹ See *supra* note 40.

providing that the Probability of Collision (PoC) should be reduced by “at least one order of magnitude” below the alert threshold.⁸² The complexities of point (b) lie outside the scope of this paper, but it is important to note that operators and CASSPs are held to this standard. Finally, point (c) requires operators and CASSPs to consider secondary conjunctions, as described in section 1.1 *Proliferation of Space Objects*. As a reminder, a secondary conjunction arises from a spacecraft’s CAM by creating another conjunction event with a second spacecraft. For instance, if spacecraft B conducts a CAM to avoid collision with spacecraft A, point (c) mandates that the CAM should not create another collision risk, this time with spacecraft C. Though the evidence supporting the explicit mention of point (c) is very important, and the proposal herein can accommodate considerations of secondary conjunctions, it is ultimately outside of the scope of this paper.⁸³

3. CUSTOMARY INTERNATIONAL LAW

Unification on the global scale is known as international custom.⁸⁴ When a policy becomes Customary International Law (CIL), it becomes binding on all states.⁸⁵ To reach CIL status, a strong national system must develop into a global practice.⁸⁶ If non-EU standards become the norm, then Union companies and government agencies would become dependent on outside systems. External dependence would curtail the sovereignty of the EU, leading to problematic situations regarding global competitiveness and national security.⁸⁷ This is especially deleterious with ROW rules, since there can only be one framework to be

⁸² European Commission (25 June 2025). *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex X, Point 5.2 at 35, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf. See Delmas, F., Nunes, P., Perez, C., (2024), Future Evolutions of EUSST Collision Avoidance Service, *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 11(1), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisse.2023.11.002> (The typical alert threshold is 5×10^{-4} . Reducing by one order of magnitude results in a PoC threshold of 5×10^{-5}).

⁸³ In this paper, certain terms are used interchangeably, such as “spacecraft” and “space asset,” and “HIE” and “conjunction.” Unless specified, the general meaning of terms is used, so “constellations” includes mega-constellations and giga-constellations, and “spacecraft” includes satellites and constellations. Additionally, the Commission conducted an impact assessment and selected “Policy Option 2+” as the preferred result: adopt a binding Union framework, paired with non-binding and support measures. In this paper, certain policies are only applicable under Policy Option 2+ (e.g. label mechanism). Overall, this paper is aligned with Policy Option 2+. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), at 7, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

⁸⁴ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf at 2, (“[D]eveloping an STM system will avoid the risk of non-EU STM standards becoming the international norm, as this dependence would have a negative effect on European technological sovereignty”), (citing Giannopapa, C., & Antoni, N., (2023), *Space Traffic Management and its Dual Use: Space Security Strategies and Cooperation in Europe*, *Acta Astronautica*, 212, 41–47, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.01.038>).

⁸⁵ “Customary international law results from a general and consistent practice of states followed by them from a sense of legal obligation.” Restatement of the Law (Third), Foreign Relations of the United States, §102(2).

⁸⁶ National Space Society, (6 May 2025), at 4.

⁸⁷ Kolovos, A. (March 2024). Unravelling the EU’s Space Policy and Strategy: Impacts on Security and Defence Evolution, *London Institute of Space Policy and Law* (ISPL), at 4, (noting the war in Ukraine prompted the EU to identify space as a strategic domain for security and defence purposes).

effective.⁸⁸ Ultimately, effective laws are *clear* laws, and for Article 103(3) to gain the requisite clarity to become CIL, operators must understand how these factors are used in practice.⁸⁹

Regulatory hegemony is not new to the EU, as such an occurrence is documented and has been coined the “Brussels effect.”⁹⁰ To create a single market and achieve sovereignty on the global scale, the development of a STM system is a litmus test for the Union’s future wellbeing and stability.⁹¹

“In addition to being technically sound and efficient,” the objective of ROW rules is to integrate the matters of a larger space community.⁹² This balancing of interests is critical for the EU’s goal to remain sovereign because global adoption is dependent on stakeholder’s positive perception.⁹³

3.1. A Cohesive Structure

A standardised ROW framework would nonetheless be absolute if *different* rules are adopted.⁹⁴ Unlike driving on the road, where rules can change depending on the geographical boundary, orbital space lacks any regard for state boundaries.⁹⁵ Lacking a cohesive structure, different ROW instructions will inevitably interact with one another, potentially *increasing* the risk of collision.⁹⁶ “An STM regime followed only by one or a handful of nations would do little to create a safer space environment.”⁹⁷ Not only would this circumstance fail to create a safe orbital environment, but nations with more lenient rules would attract

⁸⁸ See *infra* section 3.1 A Cohesive Structure.

⁸⁹ Rule of Law Education Centre, *Characteristics of Effective Laws*, n.d., <https://www.ruleoflaw.org.au/education/civics-citizenship-and-laws/characteristics-of-effective-laws/>.

⁹⁰ Bradford, A. (2020). *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World*, Oxford University Press. The Brussels Effect is “the phenomenon where the markets are transmitting the EU’s regulations to both market participants and regulators outside the EU.” This can happen by global corporations adjusting their conduct to be compatible with the EU market, then lobbying in their home states for adoption of EU regulations, to avoid the “flag of convenience” issue. This practice spreads EU regulations.

⁹¹ European Commission (15 February 2022). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 2, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004> (stating with regards to a global regulatory framework: “the EU must act now, swiftly, collectively and resolutely”).

⁹² Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 304, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

⁹³ Bertrand, R., Michel, M. (20–23 April 2021). *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (“Acceptance and thus the wider adoption will be determined primarily by how fairly the rules are valued by the entities involved.”). See also International Telecommunication Union (ITU), (1992), *Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union*, (2023 ed., Art. 44, No. 196), (“any associated orbits . . . are limited natural resources and that they must be used rationally, efficiently, and economically”).

⁹⁴ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf at 2.

⁹⁵ See Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 313, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (Orbit is multi-dimensional and governed by the “laws of astrodynamics,” making orbit “more geometrically complex.”).

⁹⁶ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 303, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (Right-of-way rules “would let operators know what behaviour to expect from another operator even if they have not succeeded in establishing communication.”).

⁹⁷ National Space Society (6 May 2025), at 2.

greater demand.⁹⁸ Rather than permit counter-productive behaviour, proposed ROW rules should alleviate the risk of collision and incorporate the “complex web of interests” of the global space community.⁹⁹

In 2020, the European Space Policy Institute (ESPI) published a report on the EU’s need for a unified framework: *Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management* (2020 Report).¹⁰⁰ The 2020 Report followed the United States’ Space Policy Directive-3 (National Space Traffic Management Policy) in 2018, a presidential memorandum that provides guidelines to establish a U.S. approach to STM.¹⁰¹

By 2022, the EU published a joint communication to the European Parliament and Council: *An EU Approach for Space Traffic Management* (2022 Report).¹⁰² Therein, it identified four “drivers” of the EU STM initiative, one being the lack of international “rules of the road” for orbital actors.¹⁰³ As noted, given the unfettered nature of space, global alignment is critical.

In response to growing pressure, the EU proposed the *Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act) in 2025 as a regulatory compendium for the “development and function of an EU single market for the space sector.”¹⁰⁴ By unifying Member States’ space policies, access across twenty-seven Member States is opened, ultimately boosting the European economy.¹⁰⁵ Especially within the context of space, where space objects are used for education, military, communication, and weather purposes, protecting space assets is vital to the health of the Union.¹⁰⁶

⁹⁸ *Ibid.* Known as the “flags of convenience” problem, where states with lenient rules garner greater demand, thereby creating a system of actors that follow insufficient rules. *See supra* note 85.

⁹⁹ Frandsen, 2023, at 304. *See* Bertrand, R., Michel, M. (20–23 April 2021). *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darnstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/>, (“Acceptance and thus wider adoption will be determined by how fairly the rules are valued by the entities involved.”); National Space Society, (6 May 2025), at 1, (“Internationally binding regulations regarding STM will only be achieved if States . . . expect a specific as well as collective benefit”).

¹⁰⁰ European Space Policy Institute (January 2020). *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.* at 1; U.S. Office of the President (18 June 2018). *Space policy directive-3: National space traffic management policy*, The White House. At the time of the United States’ SPD-3 release, the EU did not have a comparable STM policy yet.

¹⁰² European Commission (15 February 2022). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report), JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.* at 3–4, (The other three “drivers” are (in order as mentioned): 1. “New Space” (referring to the economic change regarding space initiatives, specifically the low cost and high return relationship, encouraging more space actors); 2. rise of space traffic activity; and 3. threats to the security and resilience of space assets.)

¹⁰⁴ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Commission Staff Working Document, Executive Summary of the Impact Assessment Report* (Executive Summary), at 1, SWD(2025) 336 final. Note that the EU Space Act is still in negotiations.

¹⁰⁵ European Commission (2025). *Space Act*, at 9, (The Space Act is projected to make the EU space industry a EUR 700 billion market. Unifying rules across the EU creates a single market across twenty-seven States, streamlining access and reducing administrative hurdles).

¹⁰⁶ Mazurelle, F., Wouters, J., & Thiebaut, W. (2009). The Evolution of European Space Governance: Policy, Legal and Institutional Implications, *International Organizations Law Review*, 6(1), 155-190, at 189 (“One thing is clear: . . . space will be a true case study and a genuine test for European governance itself and for the future of the EU as a global actor.”). *See also* European Commission (10 March 2023). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence* at 1, JOIN(2023) 9 final, Brussels, Belgium, (stating space is “critical” for strategic autonomy of the EU and its Member States).

4. ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE 103(3)(A)-(G)

4.1. Protection of Crew Vehicle

Rule: *In the event of conjunction, the crewed spacecraft has the right-of-way unless the other spacecraft is also crewed.*

The most important consideration is the safety of crewed vehicles during space activities. As established in the EU Space Act, the proposed CAMs by CASSPs must take “the utmost account of the protection of crewed vehicles.”¹⁰⁷ The protection of life is a moral and ethical principle that needs no explanation. In the context of international law, this concept is codified in treaties such as the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (1967) (Outer Space Treaty or OST), Article V, which regards astronauts as “envoys of mankind” whom shall receive “all possible assistance in the event of accident, distress, or emergency landing.”¹⁰⁸ Echoed in the *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (1967) (Rescue Agreement or ARRA), Article II, which requires a state to take “all possible steps to rescue [personnel] and render them all necessary assistance.”¹⁰⁹ Nearly all EU Member States have ratified the OST and ARRA,¹¹⁰ but regardless of ratification status, both treaties have become Customary International Law (CIL)¹¹¹ and therefore, are binding on all states.¹¹²

Principles regarding human safety are also reflected in aviation and maritime law.¹¹³ In the former, Article 25 of the Chicago Convention provides that states must provide “measures of assistance to aircraft in distress in its territory.”¹¹⁴ In the latter, Article 98 of UNCLOS specifies that only if “serious danger” would not be rendered onto the aiding ship, crew, or passengers, can a captain provide assistance to

¹⁰⁷ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3), at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁰⁸ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty), 27 January 1967, 610 U.N.T.S., Art. V, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

¹⁰⁹ *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Rescue Agreement), 3 November 1967, 610 U.N.T.S. 205, Art. II, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/rescueagreement.html>.

¹¹⁰ COPUOS, *Status of International Agreements relating to activities in outer space as at 1 January 2025*, (A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.9), https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_9_0.html/AC105_C2_2025_CRP09E.pdf (As of January 1, 2025, Luxembourg and Malta are signatories to the OST. Estonia has not ratified the Rescue Agreement. Latvia has not ratified the OST nor the Rescue Agreement).

¹¹¹ “Customary international law results from a general and consistent practice of states followed by them from a sense of legal obligation.” Restatement of the Law (Third), Foreign Relations of the United States, §102(2).

¹¹² *Ibid.*

¹¹³ See Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention), (1948), Art. 25, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/unts/volume%2015/volume-15-ii-102-english.pdf>; United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), (1994), Art. 98, https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

¹¹⁴ Chicago Convention, (1948), Art. 25.

vessels in distress or to those in “danger of being lost.”¹¹⁵ Member States in the EU are parties to both Conventions and portions of each treaty are regarded as CIL.¹¹⁶

Crewed vehicles should always have the right-of-way (ROW). This rule is grounded in international law and the natural inclination to protect human life. If an actor in a conjunction event is equipped with the ability to manoeuvre and is not manned, it will give-way to the crewed vehicle. To illustrate, consider a hypothetical HIE between the International Space Station (ISS) and a manoeuvrable satellite: the ISS maintains course and the satellite performs a CAM.

An exception applies during the launch of a crewed spacecraft, where it must give-way to vehicles in orbit.¹¹⁷ It is impractical to place a global burden on operators to monitor crewed launches, accurately determine if orbital adjustments are needed, and implement such CAMs with zero margin of error. Furthermore, mandating crewed spacecraft to give-way to objects in-orbit reinforces the expectation on all launches and ensures consistency.¹¹⁸

4.2. State of the Spacecraft

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft that is unresponsive or in distress has the right-of-way.*

Spacecrafts are susceptible to countless vulnerabilities like geomagnetic storms, cyberattacks, and internal electrical issues.¹¹⁹ In the worst-case scenario, these impacts can render a spacecraft defunct, or in a slightly more optimistic situation, vessels can be rendered temporarily unresponsive or distressed.¹²⁰ Because this analysis is limited to two manoeuvrable spacecraft—per Article 103(1)—this paper will only address unresponsive and distressed vessels.

Referring to the Space Act itself, it is not clear whether the state of a spacecraft is meant to include the notion of being “unresponsive.” The state of a spacecraft is mentioned in Article 65(1), which articulates the “necessary data and information” that operators must provide to the EU Space Surveillance and

¹¹⁵ UNCLOS, (1994), Art. 98.

¹¹⁶ Congressional Research Service, (2023), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS): Living Resources Provisions*, (CRS Report No. R47744), <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/R47744#fn6> (noting that portions of UNCLOS are CIL); Curtis, Mallet-Prevost, Colt & Mosle LLP, (n.d.), *Public International Law UNCLOS*, Curtis.com, <https://www.curtis.com/glossary/public-international-law/unclos#:~:text=UNCLOS%20has%20been%20ratified%20by%20the%20United%20States%20of%20America>, (noting the EU Member States have ratified UNCLOS); Wouters, J., Verhoeven, S., *State Aircraft*, Max Planck Encyclopaedia of Public International Law, Oxford Public International Law, <https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e1223> (noting portions of the Chicago Convention are CIL); ICAO Member States, <https://www.icao.int/about-icao/member-states> (listing EU Member States as Contracting Parties to the International Civil Aviation Organization, a regulatory body established by the Chicago Convention).

¹¹⁷ See American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-2: Perform Launch Collision Avoidance (LCOLA) Against Crewed Space Assets, at 9 (stating collision avoidance analysis during launch has undisputed importance in protecting crewed vehicles).

¹¹⁸ See *infra* section 4.4 Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.

¹¹⁹ *Hazards of Space: How Satellite Missions Can Go Wrong* (25 September 2018). Capital Technology University [Blog], <https://www.captachu.edu/blog/hazards-of-space-how-satellite-missions-can-go-wrong>.

¹²⁰ *Ibid.* During NASA’s Fermi mission, a satellite entered “safe mode” until an issue with a solar array was resolved; SSH Communications Security, *Satellite Cybersecurity: Threats & Impacts*, <https://www.ssh.com/academy/satellite-cybersecurity-threats-impacts#:~:text=Operational%20and%20Strategic%20Impacts%20of%20the%20disruption%20more%20damaging> (cyberattacks can cause communication loss between the spacecraft and operator).

Tracking (SST) Portal¹²¹ including: “positioning, *state* of the spacecraft, [and] possibility to communicate.”¹²² Because the terms “positioning” and “communicate” flank the term “state,” the meaning of “state” does not include positioning or communicating since it was stated separately.¹²³ With this in mind, “unresponsive” should generally refer to the operator’s inability to control the vessel.

If a spacecraft is unresponsive, the spacecraft should have the ROW.¹²⁴ This follows logically because an unresponsive spacecraft is uncontrollable and therefore unable to conduct CAMs. Similarly, COLREGS denotes a “vessel not under command” as lacking the ability to manoeuvre through “some exceptional circumstance.”¹²⁵ During a collision risk, vessels not under command are provided as a stand-on vessel, which is equivalent to having the ROW.¹²⁶

When a spacecraft is *temporarily* unresponsive, the spacecraft should still have the ROW. Rule 7(a) of COLREGS supports this, stating: “If there is any doubt, such risk shall be deemed to exist.”¹²⁷ Rule 7(a) mandates ships to err on the side of safety when there is a risk of collision. The same should apply to spacecraft.

A vessel in distress should receive the ROW. The reasoning is dual-purpose: (1) a distressed spacecraft may also be unresponsive, therefore lacking the ability to manoeuvre, and (2) if the distressed vessel is crewed, this rule adheres to the proposal in section 2.2 Protection of a Crewed Vehicle by giving the crewed spacecraft with the ROW. Like a distressed spacecraft, an aircraft completing an emergency landing is given the ROW against other aircraft.¹²⁸ In its rule statement, the ICAO references an important caveat: the status of the distressed vessel must be *known*.¹²⁹ Spacecraft operators should report status changes to the EU-SST, so others are informed. Like using the November-over-Charlie flag position to alert of a vessel in distress or the spoken word MAYDAY, notifying others through the use of distress signals is common practice, and similar reporting requirements should be imposed on operators.¹³⁰

4.3. *Eccentricity of the Spacecraft’s Orbits*

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the space object with the higher eccentricity value is responsible for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre, unless the eccentricity is required for the mission.*

The eccentricity of an orbit is defined as “[t]he amount of which the orbit around Earth deviates from a perfect circle.”¹³¹ A space object with a higher eccentricity means its trajectory uncertainty grows faster

¹²¹ EU Space Surveillance and Tracking (2025). *EU SST Expands its User Community and Sensors Network*, <https://www.eusst.eu/newsroom/news/eu-sst-expands-its-user-community-and-sensors-network> (Over 500 satellites globally are protected by EU-SST and over 200 organisations are receiving services from the EU-SST).

¹²² European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 65(1) at 81, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (emphasis added).

¹²³ The Law Dictionary.org, *Noscitur A Sociis*, <https://thelawdictionary.org/noscitur-a-sociis/> (This type of legal interpretation is known as *noscitur a sociis* (“it is known by the company it keeps”). “[I]t is the concept that the intended meaning of an ambiguous word depends on the context in which it is used”).

¹²⁴ This rule is subject to exploitation by actors who wish to have the ROW. Proper documentation requirements and investigations *inter alia* can limit the pervasiveness of unethical practices. See section 6 Proposals and Limitations.

¹²⁵ COLREGS Rule 3(f).

¹²⁶ COLREGS Rule 18(a)-(c).

¹²⁷ COLREGS Rule 7(a).

¹²⁸ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.2.5.3.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.* (ground-aircraft must be “aware” of the other’s need to conduct an emergency landing to give way).

¹³⁰ COLREGS Annex IV(f); ICAO Annex 2, Appendix 1.1.

¹³¹ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 313, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>. See The European

with time, posing a higher risk to other space actors.¹³² Additionally, objects in eccentric orbits move fastest when closest to the Earth (perigee), and slowest when farthest away (apogee). At the perigee, eccentric objects have a higher velocity, which increases the risk of collision with other space actors.¹³³ Recognizing the risk of eccentric orbits in LEO, the French national space agency, *Centre National D'Etudes Spatiales* (CNES), required “the object with the greatest eccentricity shall manoeuvre.”¹³⁴ For this factor, the following rule applies: space objects with greater eccentricity must give way to space objects with lower eccentricity values.

While spacecrafts and constellations can experience slight eccentricity during normal operations in LEO,¹³⁵ most spacecraft in LEO have a nearly circular orbit ($e < 0.1$).¹³⁶ To preserve this environment and maintain safety, it follows to incentivize space actors to correct orbital deviations to preserve the non-eccentric orbit in LEO. Imposing an affirmative duty to correct these deviations will ensure orbital space is predictable for other actors. Furthermore, by having eccentric spacecraft give way to vessels with lower eccentricity, it can incentivize appropriate behaviour in orbit and proper planning for injection launches and transfer orbits.¹³⁷

An exception is created for a conjunction event with a spacecraft that requires eccentricity because of its mission. In such a scenario, it is unnecessary to incentivize operators to reduce eccentricity because the eccentricity is *required*, and the space object is more likely to be stationed in an eccentric orbit rather than LEO.¹³⁸ For example, a spacecraft launched for an interplanetary mission requires a greater eccentricity. Here, it is unlikely that the space object with the higher eccentricity will be able to conduct CAMs, especially at the perigee, and continue the operation of its mission. In such a situation, if a spacecraft needs eccentricity for its mission-type, CASSPs should continue the Article 103(3) analysis.

The Space Act Annex IV 1.4(c)(i) supports this exception by requiring CASSPs to adjust a spacecraft’s screening volume depending on the orbit regime. This acknowledges that different orbits have different collision risk levels and a spacecraft’s collision assessment should be receptive to these differences. Considering that most objects with eccentric orbits are positioned in the Highly Eccentric Orbit (HEO) or transfer orbits, Annex IV 1.4(c)(i) works naturally with this exception.

To apply this rule, eccentricity values need to be updated, reported, and shared amongst other actors via the EU-SST Portal.

Space Agency, *Types of Orbits*, https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Space_Transportation/Types_of_orbits (Perfectly circular orbits are denoted by the number zero, and highly eccentric orbits are closer to the number one.).

¹³² See generally (1998) Jack D. Fisher, The Evolution of Highly Eccentric Orbits, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA356381.pdf>.

¹³³ C.f. Braun, V., Brunetti, G., Campiti, G., Ciminelli, C., Di Sciascio, E. (July 2023). Orbital Kinematics of Conjunction Objects in Low-Earth Orbit and Opportunities for Autonomous Observations, *Acta Astronautica*, vol. 208, 355–366, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.04.032> (Less than 1% of conjunction events in LEO involve a highly eccentric space object that only transits the LEO region near its perigee.).

¹³⁴ Frandsen, 2023, at 314.

¹³⁵ Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G. (2023). Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (Eccentricity in LEO can be caused by conducting CAMs and the impact of atmospheric drag. A simulation of the Starlink constellation utilized *daily* manoeuvres to correct orbital deviations—mirroring the function of an autonomous system).

¹³⁶ Braun, V., Brunetti, G., Campiti, G., Ciminelli, C., Di Sciascio, E. (July 2023). (Objects in a conjunction event “usually share similar orbital shapes, as 87% of all orbits are nearly-circular ($e < 0.01$).”).

¹³⁷ The European Space Agency, *Types of Orbits*. Transfer orbits modify spacecraft eccentricities in preparation for moving into a different orbit. Injection launches identify the orbit a spacecraft will first launch into, before the spacecraft moves into the orbit for long-term needs.

¹³⁸ Eccentric orbits include transfer orbits and a Highly Eccentric Orbit (HEO).

4.4. Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft in an active launch phase, re-entry phase, or in active in-space operations and services has the right-of-way.*

Mission phases include the launch & early orbit phases (LEOP), orbit raising, in-orbit operations (ISOS), and disposal phases.¹³⁹ The type of mission most plausibly refers to a spacecraft's operational behaviour, as in *how* a spacecraft flies.

Spacecraft *preparing* for launch should give-way to spacecraft established in their orbit.¹⁴⁰ Yielding to traffic in-orbit has well-grounded reasoning, as the inverse would force orbiting operators to be aware of launches around the world. This rule also incentivizes operators to screen orbits based on conjunction risks and carefully select launch times.¹⁴¹ However, criticism suggests that yielding to traffic in-orbit can effectively bar new entrants.¹⁴² But as it stands, this criticism does not hold much ground in current policies, as evidenced in *NASA's Spacecraft Conjunction Assessment and Collision Avoidance Best Practices Handbook*, which requires the spacecraft "ascending/descending" to "yield the right-of-way to existing on-orbit assets."¹⁴³

Additionally, aviation law holds a similar mandate when dealing with amphibious aircraft. When seaplanes land on or take off from the water, the aircrafts are required, to the extent practicable, to avoid impeding the activity of vessels.¹⁴⁴

When a spacecraft is moving between orbits, it should also yield to those already established in the orbit. The American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) published a report that supports this

¹³⁹ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 76(4), COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁴⁰ See *Nonreimbursable Space Act Agreement Between The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and Space Exploration Technologies Corp (SpaceX) For Flight Safety Coordination with NASA Assets*, Point 2, at 3, https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/nasa-spacex_starlink_agreement_final.pdf (Point 2 addresses Starlink's responsibility to make "reasonable efforts" to use pre-launch analysis to reduce PoC in "early-orbit operations phase").

¹⁴¹ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-2: Perform Launch Collision Avoidance (LCOLA) Against Crewed Space Assets, at 9; United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs, (2021); *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space*, at 14, (Registration requirements help States act in accordance with the OST Article VIII and the Registration Convention). See Cesari, L. (16 February 2024), *Developing an EU Space Law: The Process of Harmonising National Regulations*, *McGill Institute of Air & Space Law*, <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/developing-eu-space-law-process-harmonising-national-regulations> (Per Article 189 of TFEU, Member States in the EU have exclusive control over administrative and procedural aspects of national activities, including registration and liability).

¹⁴² Frandsen, H. O. (2023). *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 304, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> ("the granting of right-of-way to satellites already in operation over newly launched satellites could potentially make it difficult for late-comers to enter specific crowded orbits").

¹⁴³ National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). *NASA Spacecraft Conjunction Assessment and Collision Avoidance Best Practices Handbook* (February 2023). 4.1: *Ascent to/Disposal from the Constellation's Operational Orbit*, at 15, ("The ascending/descending spacecraft that is equipped to maneuver needs to yield the right-of-way to existing on-orbit assets by performing risk mitigation maneuvers or ascent/descent trajectory alterations").

¹⁴⁴ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.6.1.4.

reading: “Transiting spacecraft should assume the responsibility for performing mitigation actions to avoid other satellites that are in their main operational orbits.”¹⁴⁵

In situations where a spacecraft is actively launching, the ability of the spacecraft to conduct CAMs is significantly reduced due to the lack of manoeuvrability capacity when following a pre-planned trajectory. Similarly, a spacecraft will have limited manoeuvrability in active re-entry operations because of the Earth’s gravity or because of natural decay.¹⁴⁶ In both scenarios, the spacecraft will not have the capability to conduct CAMs and therefore, has the ROW. Like a spacecraft entering Earth’s orbit, a plane “landing or in the final stages of an approach to land” is given the ROW.¹⁴⁷

When preparing for disposal, operators must give-way to other actors to the best of their ability. Asset disposal, otherwise known as active debris removal (ADR), is a kind of ISOS.¹⁴⁸ Without ADR, space junk can accumulate in orbit,¹⁴⁹ leading to a congestion issue that constellations and New Space actors exacerbate.¹⁵⁰ During ISOS operations, the servicing spacecraft should generally have the ROW. This rule is subject to change based on the future frequency of ISOS and the risk of exploitation.¹⁵¹

When the servicer spacecraft is no longer *actively* servicing the client spacecraft or debris, it should give-way to others.¹⁵² To achieve its mission, ISOS must be equipped with manoeuvring capabilities. Therefore, to give such an equipped spacecraft the ROW, especially at the cost of others’ remaining fuel or GPS functions, would ultimately defeat the purpose of its mission: sustainability. Because the client spacecraft is maintaining its orbit, and to reduce additional interference, the ISOS spacecraft must give way. This spectrum, where an ISOS spacecraft has the ROW when operating on another but has to give way when otherwise orbiting, is meant to curtail unnecessary interference and reduce the likelihood of exploitation. To apply this rule, the understanding of *when* the ISOS operation has commenced and terminated will need to be identified.

4.5. Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft with the higher operational capacity for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre must conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

¹⁴⁵ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-1: Create and Expediently Publish Your Strategy to Transport Yourself to Your Final Orbit, at 8.

¹⁴⁶ Natural decay allows a satellite to passivate fuel reserves and remain in-orbit until the spacecraft’s eventual re-entry. Note natural decay and re-entry are permitted methods of removal under EU Space Act Annex V (3.3).

¹⁴⁷ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.2.5.1.

¹⁴⁸ See generally Institute of Air & Space Law, McGill University (Montreal, Canada), Institute of Air & Space Law, Cologne University (Cologne, Germany), International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety (Noordwijk, the Netherlands), (27 January 2012), *Active Debris Removal—An Essential Mechanism for Ensuring the Safety and Sustainability of Outer Space: A Report of the International Interdisciplinary Congress on Space Debris Remediation and On-Orbit Satellite Servicing*, Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Scientific and Technical Subcommittee, Forty-Ninth Session, A/AC.105/C.1./2012/CRP.16, Vienna, Italy, (ADR’s use is to “clean” orbit by removing unwanted debris, most commonly by expediting an object’s re-entry into the Earth’s atmosphere).

¹⁴⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (June 2023). *UNOOSA and ESA Release Updated Infographics About Space Debris*, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/informationfor/media/unoosa-and-esa-release-infographics-and-podcasts-about-space-debris.html> (Satellites in LEO will usually fall back to Earth in less than 25 years, but “[h]ad the dinosaurs launched a satellite into the furthest geostationary orbit, it would still be up there today”).

¹⁵⁰ For the EU Space Act’s proposed requirements on de-orbiting, see Article 70(3)(c) and Annex V (3.4.2).

¹⁵¹ This rule can be exploited by having routine ISOS or falsely claiming active ISOS operations to get the ROW. To curtail such exploitation, the parameters of *when* an ISOS operation is occurring can be narrowly defined.

¹⁵² EU Space Act Annex V (3.3)(f) (a spacecraft can be removed by ISOS operations).

The spacecraft with the higher operational capacity for CA manoeuvres must give way to the space object with the limited ability to manoeuvre.¹⁵³ Annex IV (2.1) of the Space Act supports this rule in requiring operators to perform CAMs when a spacecraft is manoeuvrable. Similarly, maritime law grants the right-of-way based on the manoeuvrability of vessels. For instance, when power-driven vessels encounter sailing vessels, the latter are designated as “stand-on” because they do not have propelling machinery, only the wind.¹⁵⁴ A second comparison is to CubeSats, which are “generally equipped with a limited capability to manoeuvre in orbit.”¹⁵⁵

The EU Space Act does not define what constitutes a spacecraft’s “operational capacity”, and supplementing technical definitions is a nuanced practice. For instance, consider whether fuel-efficient propulsion contributes to a higher or lower operational capacity: chemical propulsion provides powerful bursts that can quickly change a satellite’s velocity, whereas electric propulsion changes a constellation’s velocity over a cumulative effect of many small firings.¹⁵⁶ A chemical propulsion system may appear to be more efficient, but the opposite is true: electric propulsion systems have “a fuel efficiency of 10-12 times greater than a chemical thruster.”¹⁵⁷ With most constellations using electric propulsion,¹⁵⁸ mega- and giga-constellations can travel farther and for longer on a given amount of fuel.¹⁵⁹ Thus, if a conjunction event requires a CAM within twelve hours, which spacecraft has the higher operational capacity: the mega-constellation that can expend fuel with less impact to operations,¹⁶⁰ or the satellite that can enact the CAM within the provided time restraint?

As mentioned, maritime law’s Rule 18 of COLREGS specifies that the hierarchy of vessels is based on *manoeuvrability*.¹⁶¹ The rule provides seven types of circumstances (i.e. vessel engaged in fishing) or characteristics of the vessel (i.e. seaplane) in which a vessel’s manoeuvrability is ranked.¹⁶² For example, a powerboat is higher in the hierarchy than a seaplane, so the seaplane gives way.¹⁶³ COLREGS Rule 17(ii) illustrates that even if vessel A is to stand-on, if it becomes apparent that vessel B is not giving way, vessel A must take CA action.¹⁶⁴ This rule requires vessels to remain vigilant, especially around vessels that are larger and less manoeuvrable.

¹⁵³ Article 103(1) designates that the CASSP assists in conjunction with two manoeuvrable spacecraft. Therefore, the analysis herein does not consider one object lacking CAM capabilities altogether.

¹⁵⁴ COLREGS Rule 3; Rule 18.

¹⁵⁵ European Space Policy Institute (January 2020). *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*, at 12.

¹⁵⁶ *Comprehensive Overview of Satellite Propulsion Systems* (24 February 2026). The Lee Co. <https://www.theleeco.com/insights/comprehensive-overview-of-satellite-propulsion-systems/>.

¹⁵⁷ NASA (26 December 2012). *Ion Thruster Sets World Record*, <https://www.nasa.gov/image-article/ion-thruster-sets-world-record/>.

¹⁵⁸ NASA (17 March 2024). *State-of-the-Art of Small Spacecraft Technology*, https://www.nasa.gov/smallsat-institute/sst-soa/in-space_propulsion/, “While xenon is generally a superior propellant, krypton-fed Hall thrusters will likely become more common in the future, especially for large constellations.”

¹⁵⁹ NASA, (26 December 2012), *Ion Thruster Sets World Record*, <https://www.nasa.gov/image-article/ion-thruster-sets-world-record/>.

¹⁶⁰ *Cf.* COLREGS Rule 8(b). Rule 8(b) requires CAMs to be “large enough to be readily apparent to another vessel.” If the thruster systems on mega- and giga-constellations are tiny firings over a comparatively longer period of time, will it be sufficiently apparent to other actors that the constellations are taking CA action?

¹⁶¹ COLREGS Rule 18. Note, COLREGS is not based on crewed status.

¹⁶² *Ibid.*

¹⁶³ Note the relation between the landing and lift-off of a seaplane and the launch and re-entry of a space object. Rule 18 of COLREGS mandates a seaplane to give-way to actors already in the water, like the rule mandating launching space objects should give way to objects in-orbit.

¹⁶⁴ COLREGS Rule 17(ii).

By adopting this framework into the postulated hypothetical above, the mega-constellation must give way to the satellite, but the satellite’s operators must stay cautious. If it appears that the mega-constellation is unable to perform the manoeuvre, the satellite must take CA action.¹⁶⁵

For the hypothetical question to even manifest, both actors need to know what propulsion system the other is using. This can be accomplished through the shared access of operational capabilities in the EU-SST Portal. A critique of sharing operational capabilities in the EU-SST Portal is that it will incentivize propulsion systems with inferior capabilities.¹⁶⁶ Bad actors will incorporate cheaper propulsion systems to take advantage of the ROW. Ultimately, the need for operational data sharing is echoed in the AIAA’s report, which calls onto operators to update their information when CAM functions are hindered. Therefore, when such information is updated and shared, other operators “will recognize that they will bear the mitigation responsibility for any conjunctions with your satellite.”¹⁶⁷ In other words, operators must remain cautious, especially until additional clarity is provided with regards to the term “operational capacity.”

4.6. *Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation*

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the smaller constellation is responsible for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

In Article 103(3)(b), the phrase “spacecraft that *is part of* a constellation” is partially ambiguous. By referencing spacecraft that constitute the constellation, rather than referencing the constellation itself, this factor alludes to other phases of a spacecraft’s life cycle, like launching.¹⁶⁸ During launches, a satellite is not connected to the constellation but rather just “part” of it. Aircraft formations support this interpretation, as their formations include “periods of transition when aircraft are manoeuvring.”¹⁶⁹ Therefore, just as satellites comprise a constellation, aircrafts comprise flight formations.

During both the launch-planning and the launch and early orbit phases (LEOP), a constellation must give-way to objects in-orbit to the extent practicable.¹⁷⁰ This rule is consistent with the approach for other launching vehicles. Specifically, Annex VI 2.2(d)(i) in the Space Act supports this rule, which mandates operators of mega- and giga-constellations to prove a limited PoC when transferring from injection to final orbit.¹⁷¹ In other terms, this means a mega- or giga-constellation cannot move into a different orbit

¹⁶⁵ This notion of operators remaining vigilant when the other has the duty to conduct a CAM is supported by all proposed rules herein, especially in the following section: 4.6 Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation. The purpose of drawing this comparison with maritime law is to “fill the gap” presented by the lack of clarity in determining what “operational capacity” refers to, as explored in the hypothetical.

¹⁶⁶ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 17, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

¹⁶⁷ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-1: Create and Expediently Publish Your Strategy to Transport Yourself to Your Final Orbit, at 8.

¹⁶⁸ For example, had this factor been shortened to “involvement of a constellation,” launching satellites would not be included because the satellites aren’t *attached* to the constellation. This interpretation is supported by Article 88(3) stating: “prior to launch, or in the case of *satellites part of a constellation*, prior to the launch of the first batch of satellites” (emphasis added). Article 88(3) shows that when satellites “part of a constellation” are involved, it includes the full life cycle of satellites, not only when the satellites are attached to the constellation. EU Space Act, Article 88(3), pg. 95. The textual analysis utilized here is referred to as syntactic analysis and *expression unius* (negative implication).

¹⁶⁹ ICAO Annex 2 (3.1.8), at 3-2.

¹⁷⁰ See *supra* section 4.4 Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.

¹⁷¹ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex VI, Point 2.2(d), at 20, COM(2025) 335 Final,

without proving the plan has a low risk of collision. By requiring a launching plan, especially in the case of large constellations, operators must comply with registration practices, which is “a key factor in the safety and the long-term sustainability of space activities.”¹⁷²

Smaller constellations must conduct CAMs and give-way to larger constellations. This is most evident in point (66) of the EU Space Act Proposal, which states: “specific obligations should be imposed to constellations varying according to the *size* of a constellation.”¹⁷³ One example is the comparison starting with Article 73(2)(a)(iv), which mandates operators to take the expected number of CAMs during the lifetime of the mega- and giga-constellation into consideration when selecting an orbit.¹⁷⁴ Compare this to Article 69(1), which does not explicitly mandate that the number of CAMs be taken into consideration when selecting an orbit for spacecraft. Placing a higher burden on mega- and giga-constellations in selecting an orbit can disincentivize larger space objects from selecting LEO and thereby insulating smaller actors.

Additionally, a smaller constellation must give-way during a larger constellation’s ISOS.¹⁷⁵ During these services, the larger constellation might be unable to conduct CAMs, regardless of whether the constellation’s CAM system is manual or automated. In this case, the smaller object has to give way. It is important to monitor for actors who take advantage of this exception by routinely sourcing ISOS or improperly claiming ISOS services to avoid conducting CAMs.

To apply the rule, operators need to know the size of another’s spacecraft, which can be shared through the EU-SST Portal. Using the EU-SST Portal, the size of a constellation can be appraised, but additional thought is required in determining whether satellites of *comparable* size are nonetheless deemed “larger” or “smaller” than the other based on a strict interpretation of definitions.¹⁷⁶ When two equally sized constellations are in a conjunction event, the CASSP must continue the Article 103(3) analysis.

Larger constellations utilize autonomous CAM systems because the scale of a single constellation is too much for operators to manage on their own.¹⁷⁷ Though an automated CAM is a relatively new piece of technology, its premise – the ability to self-manage CAM – has been accepted at face-value.¹⁷⁸ The EU

https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf

¹⁷² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) (2021). *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space*, Guideline A.5: Enhance the Practice of Registering Space Objects, at 14. Registration requirements help States act in accordance with the OST Article VIII and the Registration Convention.

¹⁷³ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Point 66 at 24, (emphasis added).

¹⁷⁴ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 73(2)(a)(iv) at 85.

¹⁷⁵ See European Commission, (10 July 2024), *In Space Operations and Services – A Strategic Ability for the Future*, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/space-operations-and-services-strategic-ability-future_en.

¹⁷⁶ See European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article V (Definitions).

¹⁷⁷ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf, at 4.

¹⁷⁸ The analysis of intra-constellation collisions is not included in the scope of this paper because it has been widely accepted as effective and generally involves only one O/O, therefore it does not fall within Article 103(3). See Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (“It is assumed that constellations are able to self-manage their own collision avoidance . . .”).

Space Act mandates these automated systems for CA in mega- and giga-constellations.¹⁷⁹ In a scenario where a satellite or constellation is in a conjunction event with a mega- or giga-constellation, the sharing of information and planned manoeuvres will be imperative.¹⁸⁰ This is because the constellation's automated CAM system will be planning a manoeuvre and will not be able to consider what the smaller constellation or satellite might do without the requisite transfer of information.

A similar incident can appear in a conjunction event with two constellations, both equipped with automated systems. Because neither system will know the other is preparing for a CAM, it can lead to catastrophic results. Potential remedies include constant manual oversight and a common, automated system.

4.7. Age of the Spacecraft

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft that can conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre and end-of-life operations must conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

Generally, comparing the ages of two spacecrafts is unnecessary.¹⁸¹ It is also outside the scope of this paper to consider “older” spacecraft that were built without thrusters, as this falls outside the parameters of Article 103(1).¹⁸² This factor bears relevance in considering end-of-life (EOL) operations.¹⁸³

As stated in the EU Space Act, operators must have an EOL mission disposal plan and, in the case of mission extension, a renewed EOL plan.¹⁸⁴ These requirements ensure that spacecrafts have the necessary propellant for EOL manoeuvres.¹⁸⁵ This oversight limits the likelihood of a spacecraft running low on propellant before or during the disposal phase.¹⁸⁶ Therefore, older spacecrafts can continue to conduct CAM manoeuvres, because – all else being equal – there is a sufficient amount of propellant to continue operations. If a spacecraft needs their remaining amount of propellant for EOL operations, and is

¹⁷⁹ While satellites can have automated CAM systems, the EU Space Act only explicitly mandates larger constellations to be equipped with these functions. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex VI, Point 1.2(a) at 20, COM(2025) 335 Final,

https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf.

¹⁸⁰ European Space Agency (22 October 2019). *Automating Collision Avoidance*, Space Safety, https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/Automating_collision_avoidance.

¹⁸¹ For instance, a spacecraft in orbit for two weeks does not have “seniority” over a spacecraft in orbit for eleven days. Forgoing the “seniority” system can benefit later entrants by not asymmetrically imposing the burden to manoeuvre.

¹⁸² See Tech Briefs (1 January 2021). *Water-Powered Engines Offer Satellite Mobility*, <https://www.techbriefs.com/component/content/article/38352-water-powered-engines-offer-satellite-mobility#:~:text=At%20the%20time%2C%20CubeSats%20didn't%20have%20propulsion,about%20allowing%20pressurized%20propulsion%20systems%20onboard%20launches> (Previously, “CubeSats didn’t have propulsion systems”).

¹⁸³ EOL is defined as the “instant when a spacecraft or a launch vehicles orbital stage is permanently turned off, nominally as it completes its disposal phase, re-enters the Earth’s atmosphere, or can no longer be controlled by a space operator.” Removing space objects at EOL avoids contributing to the proliferation of space debris and is necessary for the sustainability of space orbits. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 5, point 42 at 42, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁸⁴ See generally European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex II.

¹⁸⁵ See European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V (3.1.5)(a).

¹⁸⁶ See *supra* note 34 (The Liability Convention incentivizes States to monitor spacecraft registrations, mission extensions, and mandate EOL plans to prove there is sufficient propellant to conduct disposal manoeuvres.) See also *supra* section 4.5 Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres (discussing the EU Space Act’s requirement for orbit-selection plans and operators put on “notice”).

therefore unable to conduct a CAM and the EOL operation, the CASSP should propose a CAM that complies with the removal methods provided in EU Space Act Annex V (3.3) (a-f):

- a) Performing a controlled re-entry with a well-defined impact footprint on the surface of the Earth, to limit the casualty risk;
- b) Performing a semi-controlled re-entry after the end of the mission, in case the design complies with the casualty risk;
- c) Performing an immediate uncontrolled re-entry after the end of the mission, in case the design complies with the casualty risk;
- d) Allowing its orbit to decay naturally, in accordance with the limit of cumulative accidental collision probability, maximum orbital lifetime, and the limit for casualty risk;
- e) In exceptionally justified cases, for Very High LEO, disposal can take place in an orbit not interfering with protected regions and valuable orbits;
- f) Removal by ISOS.¹⁸⁷

When assessing the means in (a-f), factors like the Union Space Safety Labels and “design for demise” parameters will incentivize operators to engage in more responsible EOL operations.¹⁸⁸ Lastly, mission extension applications that have been rejected should be reported in the EU-SST and considered by the CASSP when delineating ROW responsibilities.¹⁸⁹

5. RIGHT-OF-WAY (ROW) DECISION MATRIX

The Decision Matrix is a visual aid that combines the rule statements for each Article 103(3) factor. The Decision Matrix is purposed for a CASSP’s use when deciding a manoeuvre strategy between two operators in a HIE.

¹⁸⁷ European Commission, (2025), *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V (3.3)(a-f). Note that these means only apply to spacecraft in LEO. The spacecraft with limited propellant—for one reason or another—may be required to conduct a CAM, resulting in a loss of propellant. In such a scenario, this spacecraft will still be compliant with removal regulations given (f): “Removal by ISOS.”

¹⁸⁸ The Union Space Safety Labels will encourage adherence to high standards in safe sustainability (like an “eco-label”). See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 112 at 112, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (“Award and use of a Union Space Label”); European Commission, (15 February 2022), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 11, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>. Factors like company branding or public opinion can also incentivize operators to engage in sustainable removal practices. See also EU Space Act, Annex V (3.5.1) (“For spacecraft being disposed . . . Union spacecraft operators shall consider *design for demise* as one of the steps to minimise the casualty risk.”) (emphasis added).

¹⁸⁹ A spacecraft with a rejected mission extension is still eligible for several removal means in the EU Space Act, Annex V, (3.3) (a-f). For operators to be aware of the spacecraft’s true status, the acceptance or denial of mission extensions should be published, enabling them to meaningfully participate in negotiations. European Commission, (2025), *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V, (3.3) (a-f).

6. PROPOSALS AND LIMITATIONS

This paper concludes that Article 103(3) does not support a sequential hierarchy. The seven factors, however, can be rearranged to support an implied sequential hierarchy.

The following illustration provides a side-by-side look at the order of the factors within Article 103(3)(a)-(g) and the hierarchy proposed herein. The order of the factors under “PROPOSAL” is aligned with the Decision Matrix. The illustration gives a visual aid to better understand the differences between the two sequential orders. Each factor is given a respective colour to juxtapose the differences.

6.1. Comparative Illustration: Article 103(3) vs. Proposal

ARTICLE 103(3)	PROPOSAL
(a) Protection of crew vehicle	(a) Protection of crew vehicle
(b) Involvement of a spacecraft that is part of a constellation	(b) The state of the spacecraft
(c) The operational capacity for CA manoeuvres	(c) The eccentricity of the spacecraft’s orbits
(d) The state of the spacecraft	(d) The phase and type of the respective space mission
(e) The eccentricity of the spacecraft’s orbits	(e) The operational capacity for CA manoeuvres
(f) The age of the spacecraft	(f) Involvement of a spacecraft that is part of a constellation
(g) The phase and type of the respective space mission	(g) The age of the spacecraft

6.2. Proposals

The European Commission should provide greater clarity on the interpretation of Article 103(3) and relevant considerations within each factor, specifically with regard to the existence of an implied hierarchy. The sequential hierarchy is shown in the Decision Matrix above, but providing CASSPs with more resources would define the scope of each factor so that decisions are made with consistency and finality. Maritime and aviation analogies provide a helpful framework, but the applicability is limited given the inherent differences in the respective environments.

The ESA’s Space Safety Programme created the Collision Risk Estimation and Automated Mitigation (CREAM) project. CREAM is an automated risk assessment and manoeuvre-planning tool. It can be used to generate manoeuvre plans and support the decision-making process, facilitate negotiation between operators, and, in cases of disagreement with a proposed strategy, “refer the issue to a mediation service.”¹⁹⁰ The ESA stated: “The problem with establishing any kind of ‘rules of the road’ depends not only on the need to find consensus on such rules, but also on the availability of the technologies to make them a reality.”¹⁹¹

CREAM can be revolutionary in the STM field; however, if the EU looks to gain global dependence on Article 103(3) standards, automated technology must take these elements into consideration. Otherwise, if

¹⁹⁰ European Space Agency (12 August 2025). *CREAM: Avoiding Collisions in Space Through Automation*, https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/CREAM_avoiding_collisions_in_space_through_automation.

¹⁹¹ *Ibid.*

CREAM conflicts with Article 103(3) standards, it will lead to confusion among operators and CASSPs and poison the effectiveness of creating CIL.

Fostering the use of the EU-SST Portal will be imperative to achieving EU sovereignty and the implementation of ROW rules. In dealing with conjunction events, the most recent and factual understanding of the orbital environment must be provided to CASSPs. The EU-SST Portal should ensure users are reporting information with bearings on Article 103(3) analysis, such as: crewed status, automated CAM capabilities, unresponsive vehicles, mission extensions, manoeuvrability capabilities, etc.¹⁹² This paper, along with the applicability of the EU Space Act, did not include military or government assets.

Requiring CASSPs to document their decision-making process will reduce the likelihood of exploitation and help gather understandings of best practice.¹⁹³ The implementation of ROW rules might be subject to exploitation or inefficiency, especially with new technology such as ISOS and automated CAM. An audit system can expose these deficiencies.¹⁹⁴ On the operator level, Article 91(1) of the EU Space Act requires an “incident management process” for incident detection and reporting. As Member States integrate Article 91(1) in their domestic systems, Member States should be transparent with one another in their practices and discovery.

To achieve regulatory hegemony within the EU and ultimately, global sovereignty, the EU should continue working with non-EU partners and entities of the United Nations, like COPUOUS, for the adoption of a ROW framework. The EU can decide what behaviours to incentivize among space participants in allocating ROW benefits. With UN support, this framework can grow beyond the EU into global adoption. The clarity and functionality of ROW rules will be critical for global support.

Operators and CASSPs should be responsible for maintaining a record of their methodology in determining a manoeuvre strategy for each CAM. This would enable post-manoeuve accountability. Having a record of one’s decision-making process can enable an auditing agency to review the documentation for any errors or insights into “grey areas” of the policy. This recommendation should be limited in practice, as flooding operators and CASSPs with administrative forms will be too high of a burden.

6.3. *Limitations*

The strongest limitation on formulating a ROW framework and supporting its adoption on a global scale is the availability of Space Situational Awareness (SSA) data.¹⁹⁵ The foundation of regulating who gets to maintain the ROW and who must conduct a CAM is knowing where objects are in space. Without this knowledge, operators and CASSPs would rely on data that is false or incomplete. This can cause false positives for HIE alerts, or a complete lack of alerting, especially when certain data is regarded as “proprietary.” By accurately tracking space objects and maintaining the EU-SST Portal, a ROW framework can be put to the test.

The relevant technical implications of the proposed Article 103(3) hierarchy undoubtedly go beyond the scope of this paper. While this paper tries to incorporate practical considerations, such as eccentricity required for mission-type, there are mechanical limits of space travel that cannot be adjusted to policy. The proposed Article 103(3) hierarchy attempts to strike this balance between hopeful policy and realistic

¹⁹² See European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex IV (2.4) at 10; European Commission, (2025), *Space Act*, Article 64 at 81.

¹⁹³ See European Commission (2025). *Space Act, Reporting of Significant Incidents*, Article 63 at 97.

¹⁹⁴ See European Commission (2025). *Space Act*, Article 94 at 99, (establishing the Union Space Resilience Network (EUSRN) for “support coordination and exchanges between the Agency and the competent authorities”); *Ibid.* at Article 102 (a “competent authority” can seek annual reports or compliance with specific investigations).

¹⁹⁵ See *supra* note 63.

technology, but feedback from the space community is warranted to determine the actual practicality of this ROW framework.

Within the space law community, there have been arguments against the urgency in creating a STM system, based upon a finding that the Earth's orbit is not crowded. To put such an argument in black-and-white, these contentions reject the Kessler Syndrome thesis.¹⁹⁶ To address this argument is outside the scope of this paper, as formulating ROW rules is independent of orbital congestion. Whether the Kessler Syndrome realizes is a separate inquiry.

7. CONCLUSION

A clear understanding of the rules is critical to orbital safety, so that each operator behaves in accordance with the rules and trusts that the *other* actor knows the rules and will also comply.¹⁹⁷ The factors considered in this paper are not exhaustive, as Article 103(3) makes clear,¹⁹⁸ but the analysis provides a starting framework for a ROW structure. Additionally, when evaluating these factors, impacts on neighbouring specialties like cybersecurity and satellite tracking services are noted.

This mutual confidence underpins the effectiveness of any ROW regime and strengthens the likelihood of its emergence as customary international law (CIL). As Hjalte Osborn Frandsen notes, “Any decision about right-of-way in orbit is therefore also a decision about who should bear the cost of manoeuvring.”¹⁹⁹ Article 103(3) of the EU Space Act represents a foundational opportunity to address this question precisely by establishing the world's first operational ROW framework for space.

If implemented, these provisions could harmonise EU Member States under a shared framework that preserves EU sovereignty. By adopting relevant policies seen in maritime and aviation law, the EU can set a precedent for global space-traffic governance, promoting safety, accountability, and international cooperation.

Future progress depends on transdisciplinary collaboration to critically appraise both the technical and regulatory feasibility of such a regime. Though the EU Space Act remains in the Commission for negotiations, its implementation by 2030 would mark a decisive step toward an enforceable, interoperable system of orbital conduct.

¹⁹⁶ Bhakare, N. (20–23 April 2021). *The Need for Evolving Legal Framework for Regulation of Space Debris Caused by Satellite Constellations* [Conference Presentation], Section 3: Kessler Syndrome and Space Debris, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (Kessler Syndrome: In 1978, Kessler and Cour-Palais published their theory that “the more debris there is in orbit, the more collisions will occur,” thereby setting off a chain reaction. They predicted a “slow yet continuous growth in collision fragments that will not stop until the intact population is reduced in number”).

¹⁹⁷ Frandsen, H. O. (2021, Oct. 25-29). *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 2, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854>.

¹⁹⁸ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3) at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (“based on *at least* the following elements”) (emphasis added).

¹⁹⁹ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 303, <https://doi.org/10.54648/ajla2023042>.

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NAVIGATING SUPERPOWER DOMINANCE: THE ROLE OF MID-SIZED NATIONS IN GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE, WITH THE UNITED KINGDOM AS A CASE STUDY

SAFEEYA RIPPINGALE¹

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the evolving nature of international space governance by analysing both the power dynamics between leading spacefaring nations, namely the United States (US), China, Russia and India, and whether mid-sized states hold influence over the progression of space activity, using the United Kingdom (UK) as a case study.

Whilst space superpowers maintain leadership through technological, military and economic superiority, the increasing commercialisation of outer space has challenged traditional state-dominated space activity. This paper assesses the dynamics between state and commercial actors, and whether commercialisation has widened the capability gap between spacefaring nations.

Heightened political rivalries, exacerbated by lunar ambitions, have increased the risk of space militarisation. This paper investigates whether mid-size nations can act as moderating players in geopolitical tension through diplomacy, policy leadership and sustainable practices. The UK's approach, seen in initiatives like the Astra Carta, participation in the Artemis Accords, and active role within the United Nations, illustrates how strategic diplomacy allows states with limited military and launch capacity to influence global space policy.

The paper is structured in three parts. First, it assesses the ambitions and strategies of dominant spacefaring nations. Second, it considers the risks of disproportionate governance and the strategies implemented by mid-sized powers to assert influence through regulatory frameworks, multilateral diplomacy and technological specialisation. Finally, it evaluates future trends for global space governance in light of growing commercial activity, the prospect of an international regulatory regime, and the challenge of equitable multi-state participation.

KEY WORDS: Space Governance, Space Superpowers, Mid-sized Nations, Militarisation, Commercialisation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Space governance emerged from competitive space exploration during the Cold War, and continues to be dominated by Russia, formerly the USSR, the United States, and more recently, China and India. Whether the individual ambitions of these superpowers, as seen in the return to the Moon through the Artemis Accords, the International Lunar Research Station (ILRS) and China's Chang'e project, overshadow the collective interests and participation of less powerful nations is critical to understanding the dynamics of contemporary space governance.

Space power refers to a state's ability to independently develop, deploy and operate space assets in support of its political, diplomatic, military, economic and social objectives. This includes the legal and economic conditions that enable private participation.² This paper categorises the United States, Russia, China and India as space superpowers due to their robust national space framework and political power.

In this paper, mid-sized powers are states with significant space capabilities such as satellite manufacturing ability, launch partnerships and an active role in international space governance through participation at the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UN COPUOS), but do not have a comprehensive, independent space industry characteristic of a space superpower. For example, the UK relies on foreign launch providers for satellite orbit success³, despite spaceport developments in areas such as Cornwall (England) and Unst (Scotland).⁴ Further, mid-sized powers' national space budget is unequal to that of the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) or the China National Space Administration (CNSA). In 2024-25, the UK Space Agency (UKSA) had a total budget of £618 million⁵ compared to NASA's of \$25 billion⁶.

Contemporary space activity holds significant governance challenges. Increased activity from private and state actors has led to Low Earth Orbit (LEO) congestion and greater competition for space resources such as orbital location and radio frequencies. New dual-use technologies, like in-orbit servicing, have increased international pressure to prevent space conflict through working groups like the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space (PAROS).⁷

Yet, despite wider participation, the global governance structure continues to be influenced by the aspirations of a few dominant states, leaving smaller powers to survive in a complex environment between dependence and autonomy. This imbalance poses a crucial question: how do mid-sized nations with established space industries like the United Kingdom, Australia and Japan adapt and influence the future of space governance, whilst also bridging the power gap between themselves and superpowers? This paper will discuss how mid-sized nations contribute to international diplomacy, ethical and

² D'Urso, G., & Giosafatto, G. (2025). Space power governance, war and diplomacy: The new challenge for states. *Media, War & Conflict*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/17506352251344041>.

³ Sarah Jane Fox. (2023). The U.K.'s 'Appetite' for Space: An Increased Craving! *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 88(4), 733-774. <https://doi.org/10.25172/jalc.88.4.2> at 767.

⁴ UK Space Agency, Department for Transport and Civil Aviation Authority. (2023). Brochure: A guide to UK spaceports. GOV.UK. <https://www.ukspace.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/LaunchUK-A-guide-to-the-UKs-commercial-spaceports.pdf>.

⁵ UK Space Agency. (2025). *UK Space Agency Annual Report 2024-2025*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-annual-report-and-accounts-2024-2025/uk-space-agency-annual-report-2024-2025>.

⁶ NASA. (2024, April 15). *FY 2025 Budget Request - NASA*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/fy-2025-budget-request/>.

⁷ United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. (2025). *Open-ended Working Group on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space*. United Nations. <https://meetings.unoda.org/open-ended-working-group-on-prevention-of-an-arms-race-in-outer-space-2025>.

sustainable space governance and regulatory achievements, despite possessing reliance on other actors for space access.

2. POWER AND CAPABILITY IN GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE

2.1. *The Dominance of Major Spacefaring Nations*

Major spacefaring nations maintain dominance in international governance through advanced technological and scientific capabilities, diplomatic presence and a monopoly on space access. This supremacy operates through three interconnected forms of power: structural power, knowledge inequality and military capability.

The United States exercises structural power most visibly through export control regimes. In licensing restrictions, technological distribution and funding tied to membership of US-led frameworks such as the Missile Technology Control Regime⁸, the US effectively manages foreign state operations through its domestic initiatives. US export rules further divide the political landscape, excluding major powers like China from cooperating with certain US allies, including Canada.⁹ This dynamic illustrates Susan Strange's concept of structural power, 'the ability to shape frameworks within which states relate to each other'¹⁰, showing how dominance can be exercised through control of operating conditions.

The knowledge structure functions as an equally significant tool of power.¹¹ As Santiago Rementeria observes, by monopolising the scientific research and experimentation results generated through space activity, dominant powers are able to limit the technological independence of what he terms 'third parties'.¹² Rementeria's use of 'third parties' aptly describes states and actors that lack control or ownership of advanced space technology; namely, mid-sized powers, emerging space nations and private entities that depend on regulatory approval or space infrastructure provided by dominant powers, as particularly seen in satellite imaging technology.¹³

This structural inequality has longstanding historical origins. As early as 1960, Air Force Lieutenant General Donald L. Putt warned the US Congress that 'the Moon appears to be of such significance that we should not let another nation establish a military capability there ahead of us.'¹⁴ During the 1960s, the US monopolised launch capabilities, creating a system in which weaker states could only reach orbit through superpower collaboration.¹⁵ As one early account of rocket development noted, 'the richest and most powerful states now have means through high altitude rockets to control more or less effectively the "airspace" over their surface territories,'¹⁶ a logic that extended into orbit with the development of space technology. Whilst contemporary public-private partnerships and emerging national programmes have

⁸ Morin, J-F., & Tepper, E. (2023). The Empire Strikes Back: Comparing US and China's Structural Power in Outer Space, *Global Studies Quarterly*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksad067> at 10.

⁹ Ibid., 11.

¹⁰ Strange, S. (1988). *States and Markets*. Bloomsbury Publishing, at 25.

¹¹ Rementeria, S. (2022). Power Dynamics in the Age of Space Commercialisation. *Space Policy*, 60, 101472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2021.101472> at 3.

¹² Ibid., 3.

¹³ Ibid., 8.

¹⁴ Moltz J.C. (2019). *The politics of space security: strategic restraint and the pursuit of national interests*. Stanford University Press. at 96.

¹⁵ Huntley, W. L. (2007). Smaller State Perspectives on the Future of Space Governance. *Astropolitics*, 5(3), 237–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777620701615145>.

¹⁶ Cooper, J.C. (1956) Legal Problems of Upper Space. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 23(3). <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol23/iss3/4> at 313.

diversified access to space, structural inequalities persist. For instance, Singapore's first satellite was launched with Indian assistance,¹⁷ reflecting the continued reliance of smaller states on established space powers.

The capacity to shape international norms is a decisive characteristic of space powers, particularly apparent in areas of lunar governance. The United States strongly opposed the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Treaty)¹⁸ which contributed to its limited influence,¹⁹ despite the agreement reinforcing key principles of the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty),²⁰ such as the prohibition of sovereignty claims and the placement of nuclear weapons in space. In its place, the US-led *Artemis Accords*, now bearing 61 signatories,²¹ have established a Western commercial standard of lunar exploration that endorses private sector participation²² and resource exploitation.²³ These principles impose a strategic choice on other nations: to align with the Accords and gain access to lunar resources or oppose them and risk exclusion from their benefits. As stated in the Artemis programme documents, NASA intends to 'utilise commercial participation to enhance U.S. leadership,'²⁴ demonstrating how the US uses both political influence and commercial innovation to shape the future of lunar activity.

China's lunar ambitions create a significant challenge to the US-proposed frameworks. Through the Chang'e programme, China has sought to orbit, land and return samples from the Moon, successfully becoming the third lunar landing state and directly threatening US leadership.²⁵ The new successes in lunar exploration contribute to achieving political stability and promoting social harmony, restoring China's greatness and international standing.²⁶ The International Lunar Research Station (ILRS), developed jointly with Russia, extends China's ambition by offering an alternative to the Artemis framework. Analysts describe it as a 'clear manifestation of China's policy shift of enabling closer connections and relations with other nations.'²⁷ China's lunar programme serves two objectives, domestically as a technological achievement restoring national standing, and internationally to offer smaller nations an alternative to US-led initiatives.

Space dominance is further sustained through military capability. Space power directly interlinks to ground operations, with 'space power (guaranteeing) the security of satellites in return for services that

¹⁷ Moltz, J.C. (2014). *Crowded Orbits: Conflict and Cooperation in Space*. Columbia University Press.

¹⁸ United Nations. (1979). Agreement governing the activities of States on the Moon and other celestial bodies. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_34_68E.pdf.

¹⁹ de Zwart, M., Henderson, S., & Neumann, M. (2023). Space resource activities and the evolution of international space law. *Acta Astronautica*, 211, 155–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.06.009> at 157.

²⁰ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of States in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies*. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_21_2222E.pdf.

²¹ National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2026). *Artemis Accords*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/artemis-accords/>.

²² Melamed, A., Rao, A.I., de Rohan Willner, O., & Kreps, S. (2024). Going to outer space with new space: The rise and consequences of evolving public-private partnerships. *Space Policy*, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101626>.

²³ Wu, X. (2023). The International Lunar Research Station: China's New Era of Space Cooperation and Its New Role in the Space Legal Order. *Space Policy*, 65, 101537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101537> at 6.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, 8.

²⁵ Remus-Delgado, D. (2025). China's Apollo Program: Chang'e Lunar Missions and Regime Legitimacy. *Astropolitics*, 23(1), 73–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2025.2511173> at 74-79.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 82.

²⁷ Wu, *supra* note 23.

enable the armed forces to operate more efficiently and effectively on the ground.²⁸ Anti-satellite (ASAT) weapons are held by the United States, Russia, China, and India, a small group sitting at the upper tier of space power, aiming to limit an adversary's power of resistance. China's 2007 ASAT test demonstrated both technological innovation and the dangers of unchecked ambition, significantly worsening the orbital debris environment and underscoring the need for effective international institutions to regulate space power competition. Major space powers consistently resist constraints on their freedom of strategic action, as further evidenced by the United States 2001 withdrawal from the 1972 *Treaty Between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the Limitation of Anti-Ballistic Missile Systems* (Anti-Ballistic Missile Treaty).²⁹ This lack of self-restraint extends to commercial operators, whose deployment of mega-constellations creates challenges to the stability of space.³⁰

The rivalry between the United States and China continues to influence global alliances and challenges: space security, stability and sustainability, threatening the future of space operations.³¹ In response, both powers have pursued distinct partnership strategies that reflect their broader geopolitical objectives. China's partnerships are mostly bilateral, strategic and aim to reduce dependency on Western powers. China's 1992 Asia-Pacific Multilateral Cooperation in Space Technology and Applications (AP-MCSTA) initiative sought to expand influence among less developed countries, and the 2008 Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organisation further demonstrates cooperative behavior.³² China also actively cooperates with other international partners, including the European Space Agency in Telemetry, Tracking and Command (TT&C),³³ leveraging partnerships to extend soft power diplomacy and demonstrate technological legitimacy.

In contrast, the United States favours multilateral agreements like the Artemis Accords, COSPAS-SARSAT agreement of 1988,³⁴ the 1963 *Treaty Banning Nuclear Weapon Tests in the Atmosphere, in Outer Space and Under Water* (Partial Nuclear Test Ban Treaty)³⁵ and the 1998 *Agreement Among the Government of the United States of America, the Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of Canada, and the Government of the Russian Federation Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station* (Intergovernmental Agreement on the International Space Station)³⁶ involving fifteen other nations, to reinforce leadership and accelerate US interests within its alliance network.³⁷ Beyond formal agreements,

²⁸ D'Urso, *supra* note 2 at 9.

²⁹ United States & Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. (1972). *Treaty between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the limitation of anti-ballistic missile systems*. <https://2009-2017.state.gov/t/avc/trty/101888.htm>.

³⁰ Pekkanen, S.M., & Blount, P.J. (2023). *The Oxford Handbook of Space Security*. Oxford University Press, USA. at 638.

³¹ *Ibid.*, at 641.

³² Moltz, *supra* note 17.

³³ United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2019). China deep space TT&C and international cooperation. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/2019/copuos2019tech45E.pdf>.

³⁴ International Cospas-Sarsat Programme. (1988). *The international Cospas-Sarsat agreement*. NOAA Repository. <https://repository.library.noaa.gov/view/noaa/13374>.

³⁵ United States, United Kingdom, & Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. (1963). *Treaty banning nuclear weapon tests in the atmosphere, in outer space and under water*. <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Partial-Nuclear-Test-Ban-Treaty.pdf>.

³⁶ United States, Member States of the European Space Agency, Japan, Canada, & Russian Federation. (1998). *Agreement among the Government of the United States of America, the Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of Canada, and the Government of the Russian Federation concerning cooperation on the civil International Space Station*. <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/98-1291.pdf>.

³⁷ Melamed, *supra* note 22.

the US has established national safety standards, space traffic management initiatives and institutions such as the International Space Safety Foundation of 2008, demonstrating unilateral leadership that shapes safety practices instead of a binding international consensus. The US Space Situational Awareness data-sharing increases transparency and is fundamental for the safety of both commercial and governmental space operations.³⁸

Both approaches, China's bilateral agreements and America's multilateral frameworks, reflect the same logic, that leadership in space governance directly translates into geopolitical influence.

It has been argued that US-aligned states are unable to exercise meaningful power over the international-law-making process due to their dependence on the superpower.³⁹ Whilst dependent allies are tethered to US objectives, alignment remains a strategic choice rather than a forced condition. Smaller allies gain material advantages with access to technology, intelligence and launch infrastructure. The more significant constraint on international space law is not allied dependence, but the unwillingness of major spacefaring powers to accept binding restrictions on their conduct. The obligations of international law do not sufficiently restrict major spacefaring powers,⁴⁰ and the US space policy's promotion of private property claims, resource exploitation and commercial developments reflects this clearly.⁴¹ Through coherent national space strategies that align technology, strategy and diplomacy, dominant powers are able to shape international norms to reflect their own ambitions and support their continued leadership.

2.2. The Role of Private Companies in Governance Gaps

The commercialisation of outer space has challenged traditional state-centric space governance by introducing competing interests which are not adequately addressed in existing frameworks.⁴² Companies such as SpaceX and Blue Origin illustrate this change. SpaceX's ambition to 'facilitate the colonisation of Mars' and Blue Origin's objective of creating a 'future in space that millions of people call their office and home,'⁴³ highlight commercial motivations that operate independently of national policy objectives. The traditional role of states is challenged by private companies that, in some cases, hold greater financial resources than mid-sized national space agencies, as seen in SpaceX's \$16 billion revenue in 2025⁴⁴ exceeding the UKSA's £618 million budget⁴⁵, and commercial ambition raises liability, sustainability and sovereignty issues.

The legitimacy of commercial actors has been consolidated with state institution partnerships. The European Space Agency (ESA) relies on Arianespace launch services, SpaceX and NASA have

³⁸ Verspieren, Q. (2020). The United States Department of Defense space situational awareness sharing program: Origins, development and drive towards transparency. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2020.10.001>.

³⁹ Steer, C. (2020). Who Has the Power? A Critical Perspective on Space Governance and New Entrants to the Space Sector. *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law* 48(3), 751. <https://digitalcommons.law.uga.edu/gjicl/vol48/iss3/10> at 758.

⁴⁰ Huntley, *supra* note 15.

⁴¹ Billings, L. (2006). How shall we live in space? Culture, law and ethics in spacefaring society. *Space Policy*, 22(4), 249–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2006.08.001> at 251.

⁴² Rementeria, *supra* note 11 at 10.

⁴³ Melamed, *supra* note 22 at 12.

⁴⁴ Wang, E., Vinn, M., & Roulette, J. (2026, January 30). Exclusive: SpaceX generated about \$8 billion in profit last year ahead of IPO, sources say. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/finance/spacex-generated-about-8-billion-profit-last-year-ahead-ipo-sources-say-2026-01-30/>.

⁴⁵ UK Space Agency, *supra* note 4.

collaborated since 2008,⁴⁶ and New Space India Limited (NSIL) serves both domestic and international markets.⁴⁷ Beyond partnerships, policy frameworks like the Artemis Accords have encouraged the international acceptance of commercial participation in outer space activities.⁴⁸ Following the end of the Space Shuttle Program in 2011, NASA's reliance on Russian launch vehicles proved the strategic need for private providers, a need further emphasised by geopolitical tensions such as Russia's invasion of Crimea. India, despite formidable space capabilities including the successful lunar landing from the Chandrayaan-3 mission,⁴⁹ chose to use SpaceX's Falcon 9 for satellite deployment.⁵⁰ That even the most capable spacefaring nations defer to commercial providers indicates how mid-sized nations must also engage with the private sector to remain competitive in space activity. As Wichita Teerantabodee notes, 'many spacefaring countries, especially small and middle powers, rely on foreign space companies; their regulatory frameworks should also consider Private-Public Partnerships (PPPs) with enterprises that are not entirely under their jurisdiction.'⁵¹ PPPs provide financial solutions and technological innovation in space transportation,⁵² expanding launch capabilities and global commercial reach,⁵³ which becomes critical for spacefaring nations with limited capabilities.

Public-private partnerships nonetheless introduce significant governance risks. Transnational partnerships offer smaller nations space sector opportunities but create national security vulnerabilities through external dependence. Divergent motivations between state agencies and profit-driven firms create policy misalignment, which in turn destabilises the regulatory environment and can increase the risk of dual-use technology misuse, as demonstrated by the 2020 SpaceX-NASA Crew Dragon collaboration.⁵⁴ As private authority becomes progressively disconnected from public accountability,⁵⁵ commercial actors face fewer consequences for conduct that conflicts with broader public interests, emphasising the need for clearer regulation.

The U.S Spurring Private Aerospace Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship Act of 2015 indicates the lack of proper distinction between public and private authority in space, granting ownership rights over celestial objects to the entities that obtained them.⁵⁶ This overrides international agreements, particularly Article II of the Outer Space Treaty's (OST) non-appropriation principle, showing the lack of authority that international law has over the incentives of space superpowers. As SpaceX and Blue Origin dominate the commercial sector under American jurisdiction, the US holds authoritative power over these companies and, by extension, over much of the space market. National laws supervise and authorise non-state actors through licensing regimes that regulate international liability,⁵⁷ meaning non-state actors are at risk of answering to the state from which they operate. The US, therefore, shapes the private sector

⁴⁶ Melamed, *supra* note 22 at 3.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, 14.

⁴⁸ NASA, *supra* note 21.

⁴⁹ European Space Agency. (2023, August 23). *India's Chandrayaan-3 successfully lands on the Moon*. ESA https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Operations/India_s_Chandrayaan-3_successfully_lands_on_the_Moon.

⁵⁰ Teeratanabodee, W. (2025). *Public-Private Partnerships in Outer Space: Implications for the Defence and Security Sector* (RSIS Working Paper No. 344). S. Rajaratnam School of International Studies. <https://rsis.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/WP344.pdf> at 19.

⁵¹ *Ibid*, 26.

⁵² *Ibid*, 6.

⁵³ Moltz, *supra* note 17 at 93.

⁵⁴ Teerantabodee, *supra* note 50 at 10.

⁵⁵ Newlove-Eriksson, L., & Eriksson, J. (2013). Governance Beyond the Global: Who Controls the Extraterrestrial? *Globalizations*, 10(2), 277–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2013.786250> at 280.

⁵⁶ Aggarwal, J. (2024). Space Policy Imperative: The Urgency for a New International Space Governance System. *Astropolitics*, 22(1-2), 102–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2024.2379089>.

⁵⁷ Dempsey, P.S. (2016). National laws governing commercial space activities: legislation, regulation, & enforcement. *Northwestern Journal of International Law & Business*, 36(1), 1-44 at 5.

through domestic law whilst benefiting from commercial dominance and consequently increasing the structural inequalities of space governance identified in section one.

The governance of mega-constellations remains unclear and raises questions about the applicability of international law to private entities. As Pranav Kaginele argues, large networks of privately owned satellites occupying Low Earth Orbit for economic gain may violate the OST's foundational principles.⁵⁸ Although Article VI of the OST⁵⁹ declares that states bear international responsibility for the national activities of private entities in space, enforcement remains weak and national licensing frameworks inadequately address global challenges such as space debris, conflict resolution or cyber attacks. Under Article VIII of the OST, the state of registry bears responsibility for launched objects, but the low attribution threshold may hold states accountable for private activities beyond their control or knowledge, potentially including foreign armed conflicts.⁶⁰ This accountability gap is consequential for mid-sized nations, which must rely on effective national regulation and licensing to manage commercial dependence in the absence of independent financial capacity.

The 2017 *Luxembourg Law on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources* requires ministerial authorisation for space activities, as well as offering tax incentives to attract commercial actors.⁶¹ This demonstrates that responsible private investment is possible with appropriate regulation. Luxembourg's model is apt in showing how mid-sized nations can actively shape the conditions under which commercial activity operates within their jurisdiction. As Cassandra Seer notes: 'today's space race is equal parts commercial and political, and commercial players have a unique ability to disrupt the status quo.'⁶² Hence, it must be observed that states cannot maintain influence in space governance without commercial sector engagement.

3. MID-SIZED POWERS IN A DISPROPORTIONATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM

3.1. Strategies of Influence- Collaboration, Specialisation and Domestic Frameworks

In a hierarchical governance system dominated by a few space superpowers, mid-sized powers are disadvantaged. The risk of disproportionate governance, whether that is superpower or commercial dominance, creates inequality amongst nations, particularly in access to the benefits of satellite technology in communications and environmental monitoring. Without strategic engagement, mid-sized powers risk having their interests overlooked in space governance forums that decide the direction of outer space. This section examines how, despite these constraints, mid-sized nations assert influence through foreign collaboration, regional organisation, technological specialisation and domestic legislation.

Smaller nations turn to foreign collaboration to promote development whilst removing singular dependability on any one superpower. Joint missions, bilateral agreements and multilateral initiatives not only expand scientific achievements but also create alliances and cross-border objectives. As Wade L.Huntley observes in his article on smaller state perspectives on the future of space governance, 'smaller

⁵⁸ Kaginele, P. (2023). Megaconstellations: Analyzing Potential Risks of Gaps in Space Law. *JHU Law Review*. <https://jhlur.org/2023/01/27/megaconstellations-analyzing-potential-risks-of-gaps-in-space-law/>.

⁵⁹ OST, *supra* note 20.

⁶⁰ Wang, G., & Hu, Y. (2025). Allocation and Attribution of Commercial Space Activities in Armed Conflict. *Air and Space Law*, 50(1). at 11.

⁶¹ Loi du 20 juillet 2017 sur l'exploration et l'utilisation des ressources de l'espace [Law of July 20th 2017 on the Exploration and Use of Space Resources], Journal officiel du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg, (2017). <https://legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2017/07/20/a674/jo/en>.

⁶² Steer, *supra* note 39 at 751.

states aim to influence larger powers; otherwise, their personal interests will be ignored out of ignorance or apathy.⁶³ Collaboration provides a dual purpose for mid-sized nations, advancing scientific and technological capability whilst participating in governance discussions that would otherwise be shaped without them. The 2021 Quad Space Cooperation Working Group, in which Australia and Japan collaborated with the United States and India to share satellite data and consult on norms for sustainable space use,⁶⁴ demonstrates how mid-sized powers utilise collaboration to advance their own space capabilities whilst contributing to the broader preservation of the space domain. In doing so, mid-sized nations position themselves as responsible moderators keeping superpower behaviour aligned with the benefit of all spacefaring nations by promoting long-term sustainability.

Regional organisations such as the ESA and the African Space Agency (AfSA) illustrate the ambitions of smaller nations to contribute collectively. The political nature of ESA enables scientists and industrial lobbies to have more influence, forming scientific diplomacy that gives a voice to smaller member states. Through ESA, states such as the United Kingdom are able to shape international standards on space sustainability, debris mitigation and responsible private behaviour,⁶⁵ areas of development that exceed what any individual member state could achieve through national policy alone. This collective representation is shown by ESA's role in the 1998 Intergovernmental Agreement on the International Space Station,⁶⁶ in which ESA acted as a single space agency representing eleven of its member states and internally handling the jurisdiction over intellectual property rights.⁶⁷ Regional organisations are critical for mid-sized nations, as smaller states can act at a level of authority beyond their individual capabilities.

Mid-sized powers often specialise in niche technological and scientific fields to attract partnerships and establish a distinct role in the space sector that does not depend on military or economic dominance. For example, the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) innovatively uses robotics to reduce space debris⁶⁸ and focuses on environmental monitoring to '(maintain) its role as one of the leading countries in studying greenhouse gases and climate change, which it sees as an important part of its unique scientific mission in space.'⁶⁹ Similarly, the United Kingdom focuses on small satellite manufacturing and orbital sustainability. Through specialisation, mid-sized states become indispensable, proving that influence can derive from capability rather than military or economic power.

International law alone provides insufficient protection for mid-sized powers, as it lacks the enforcement mechanisms to fully constrain superpower behaviour. Consequently, domestic legislation becomes a more effective source of influence. By translating international principles into national law, such as the *United*

⁶³ Huntley, *supra note* 15 at 254.

⁶⁴ Office of Space Commerce (2021, September 24). Quad Leaders Announce Space Cooperation Working Group. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://space.commerce.gov/quad-leaders-announce-space-cooperation-working-group/>.

⁶⁵ European Space Agency. (2023). *The Zero Debris Charter*. https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Clean_Space/The_Zero_Debris_Charter.

⁶⁶ Agreement Among the Government of Canada, Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of the Russian Federation, and the Government of the United States of America Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station. (1998, Jan 29). <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/oijr-nasa-canadian-space-agency-agreement-january1998.pdf?emrc=aa2c30>.

⁶⁷ Von der Dunk, F. & Fabio Tronchetti. (2017). *Handbook of space law*. Cheltenham, UK Edward Elgar Publishing at 115.

⁶⁸ Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency. *Space Debris Removal Project Underway*. <https://global.jaxa.jp/activity/pr/jaxas/no092/03.html>.

⁶⁹ Moltz, *supra note* 17 at 75.

Kingdom's Outer Space Act 1986,⁷⁰ Japan's Space Activities Act 2016,⁷¹ and Australia's Space Activities Act 1998,⁷² mid-sized powers establish normative behaviour that contributes to consistent global standards. The United Kingdom's resolution on 'reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behavior led directly to the establishment of the Open-Ended Working Group on identifying and tackling threats through responsible behaviour,⁷³ showing how domestic policy can directly affect broader initiatives. In the handbook of space law, Von der Dunk describes the fourth phase of space activities in which the coherence of international law is diminished as space activity moves away from its traditional Cold -War, government-focused origins.⁷⁴ This shift provides a unique opportunity for mid-sized nations, as weakened binding frameworks create space for alternative forms of governance influence. Normative leadership through domestic legislation and responsible behavior positions mid-sized powers as a stabilising force, shaping global standards across state, commercial and academic spheres whilst reducing space threats.⁷⁵

3.2. Case Study- the United Kingdom

The United Kingdom, with its significant space capabilities and active role in international governance, yet without the military and economic resources or independent launch capabilities of a space superpower, exemplifies the mid-sized nation position examined throughout this paper. The UK's approach to space governance is defined by normative standards and regulatory leadership, aiming to promote responsible, sustainable behaviour rather than technological strength.⁷⁶ Crucially, the UK has maintained an influential position in space governance, and its space development offers a model for other mid-sized powers.

Possessing a coherent national legal framework built on the Outer Space Act (1986) and the Space Industry Act (2018),⁷⁷ alongside subsequent statutory instruments, the UK has established one of the most comprehensive national regulatory frameworks for space activities. Governance is coordinated across multiple institutions, including the UKSA and the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA).

⁷⁰ United Kingdom. (1986). *Outer Space Act 1986*. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1986/38>.

⁷¹ Japan. (2016). *Act on Launching of Spacecraft, etc. and Control of Spacecraft (Space Activities Act)* (Act No. 76 of 2016). https://www.jaxa.jp/library/space_law/chapter_4/4-1-2-1_e.html.

⁷² Australia. (1998). *Space Activities Act 1998*. <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2019C00074>.

⁷³ Office, D. (2021, November). UN General Assembly's First Committee approves UK push to tackle threatening space behaviour. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/un-general-assemblys-first-committee-approves-uk-push-to-tackle-threatening-space-behaviour>.

⁷⁴ Von der Dunk & Fabio Tronchetti, *supra* note 67 at 106.

⁷⁵ Pavesi, G., & Wouters, J. (2023). The final frontier? The European Union and the governance of outer space. *Revue d'Intégration Européenne*, 45(8), 1199–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2023.2274885>.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ United Kingdom (2018). *Space Industry Act 2018*. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/5/contents>.

Through the National Space Strategy (2021),⁷⁸ the National Space Strategy in Action (2023)⁷⁹ and the UK Space Agency Corporate Plan (2022-2025),⁸⁰ the UK has successfully integrated space policy within defence, industry and environmental domains. This policy coherence has translated into diplomatic impact, with the passing of the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 75/36⁸¹ establishing its international position as an advocate for space security.

The UK positions itself as a forward-thinking sustainable space nation, aiming to ‘lead the global effort to make space more sustainable by funding demonstrator missions for debris removal.’⁸² By specialising in small satellite manufacturing, in orbit servicing and in-space assembly and manufacturing (ISAM),⁸³ the UK establishes a sustainability-focused identity. The Astra Carta⁸⁴ aims to minimise biological and chemical contamination in space whilst investing in green-energy space technology. The UK contributes to ESA’s Vigil Mission,⁸⁵ which monitors space weather and adheres to the IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines⁸⁶ in alignment with its strong stance on orbital sustainability. The cross-parliamentary All-Party Parliamentary Group for Dark Skies, established in 2020, aims to preserve the night sky from light pollution, showing a commitment extending beyond orbital sustainability to atmospheric and environmental protection as a whole. Through specialisation in sustainability-oriented technology and policy, the UK occupies a critical governance space that is overshadowed by states and commercial actors driven by economic objectives, yet indispensable to the international community’s long-term space goals.

The UK is actively involved with the private sector, reflecting its approach to sustainable governance through public-private partnerships. The Space Innovation and Growth Strategy promotes dual-use technology and commercial ambition, and as an investor in Eutelsat OneWeb, the UK utilises commercial infrastructure to secure influence in global communications. According to BryceTech’s Start-Up Space 2025 report, the UK accounted for 9% of space start-up first investments in 2024, second only to the United States and showing Britain’s influence in the commercial space market.⁸⁷ With strong domestic commercial ties, the UK reduces its dependence on foreign providers and strategically reinforces its

⁷⁸ UK Space Agency, Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, Ministry of Defence & Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy. (2021). National space strategy (27 Sept. 2021). GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-space-strategy/national-space-strategy>.

⁷⁹ Department for Science, Innovation and Technology & Ministry of Defence. (2023, July 19). National space strategy in action. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-space-strategy-in-action/national-space-strategy-in-action>.

⁸⁰ UK Space Agency. (2022). UK Space Agency corporate plan 2022–25. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2022-25/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2022-25>.

⁸¹ United Nations General Assembly. (2020). *Reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behavior* (A/RES/75/36). United Nations <https://docs.un.org/en/a/res/75/36>.

⁸² Teerantabodee, *supra note* 50 at 13.

⁸³ UK Space Agency. (2025, September 30). *UK Space Agency Corporate Plan 2025-26*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2025-26/uk-space-agency-corporate-plan-2025-26>.

⁸⁴ *Astra Carta: To care for the infinite wonders of the universe*. Sustainable Markets Initiative. https://www.sustainable-markets.org/AstraCarta_charter.pdf.

⁸⁵ UK Space Agency. (2024, August). *ESA Vigil*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/case-studies/esa-vigil>.

⁸⁶ Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee. (2025). *IADC space debris mitigation guidelines*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_12025crp/aac_105c_12025crp_9_0_html/AC1_05_C1_2025_CRP09E.pdf.

⁸⁷ BryceTech. (2025). *Start-Up Space 2025: Private sector space investment activity in 2024*. https://brycetek.com/reports/report-documents/start_up_space_2025/.

standing in space governance, reflecting the commercial engagement strategy that is essential for mid-sized nations.

As an active member of ESA, the UK specialises in maritime communications satellites⁸⁸ and invests in ESA-led debris mitigation, life extension missions and collision avoidance projects.⁸⁹ Beyond Europe, the UK International Bilateral Fund of £20 million supports partnerships with other space powers, including Australia and Japan, on projects such as InRange with Jaxa and Aqua-Watch-AUK with ASA, reflecting the broad diplomatic reach of the mid-sized nation. The UK also chooses to align with the US through projects like the Civilian Exchange Program for Space Collaboration (2025),⁹⁰ a display of trust and cooperation that reflects the mutually beneficial dynamic between superpowers and their allies. Collectively, these partnerships are indicative of how the UK uses multilateral and bilateral relationships to achieve wide-reaching influence and reduce singular dependence on one space power. The UK's governance role is consolidated through participation in global institutions. Its membership of UN COPUOS, participation in the Artemis Accords and signatory to treaties such as the Partial Test Ban Treaty leave a global impression of cooperative space activity.

However, the UK's influence is constrained by limited launch capability, budget allocation and reliance on U.S. space infrastructure, as it does not possess Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) capability or sovereign access to Positioning, Navigation, and Timing (PNT) systems.⁹¹ This dependency defines its position as a mid-sized power, yet simultaneously creates diplomatic flexibility, broadening its access to superpower multilateral and bilateral engagement as tools of influence. As a case study, the United Kingdom demonstrates that where binding international law is weakening, and commercial activity is expanding, the states that are shaping space regulation are not necessarily those with the greatest military and economic resources, but those with the clearest policy vision and diplomatic capacity to shape global norms and behaviours in space.

4. FUTURE TRENDS FOR GLOBAL SPACE GOVERNANCE

4.1. Space Security and the Moderating Role of Mid-Sized Nations

The militarisation of space poses a substantial threat to the peaceful and sustainable use of outer space. The US has strong military ambitions to achieve space dominance, as signified in the Air Force 2025 Study, which proposes plans for the development of advanced military technology, including orbital maneuvering vehicles, orbital combat vehicles, satellite bodyguards designed to destroy global threats and space-based kinetic weapons. The US withdrawal from the ABM Treaty in 2001 signals a shift from cooperative security frameworks toward assertive national policy in space. Furthermore, plans for the Golden Dome, a proposed missile defense system with space-based sensors and interceptors, risk military

⁸⁸ Moltz, *supra* note 17 at 75.

⁸⁹ UK Space Agency. (2025, April). *UK engagement with space: Written evidence* (SPA0024). UK Parliament. <https://committees.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/140363/pdf/> at 5.

⁹⁰ Space Systems Command & UK Space Command. (2025, April 15). Space Systems Command and U.K. Space Command foster international collaboration with first-ever civilian exchange program space position [Press release]. U.S. Space Force. <https://www.ssc.spaceforce.mil/Newsroom/Article-Display/Article/4154567/space-systems-command-and-uk-space-command-foster-international-collaboration-w>.

⁹¹ Elefteriu, G. (2024, November.) *Better space. Consolidating Britain's national space enterprise* (Policy Paper No. 2024/36). Council on Geostrategy. https://www.geostrategy.org.uk/app/uploads/2024/11/No.2024_36-Better-space-consolidating-the-UK-national-space-enterprise1.pdf at 11.

escalation, instability in Europe-Atlantic relations and the development of space-based weapons.⁹² The possible military escalation between space superpowers, with Russia and China heavily opposing the Golden Dome, calls other players of the space community into action to act as moderators.

The proposition for data-sharing, transparency and formal limits as a ground for future arms control agreement has been identified as a potential solution,⁹³ yet the individual power ambitions of space superpowers make progress unlikely without diplomatic intervention from mid-sized nations. Japan's co-drafting of the 2024 UN Security Council resolution on preventing nuclear weapons in outer space, which attracted 65 country co-sponsors before being vetoed by Russia, is a clear example of the leading role mid-sized nations play in moderating space superpower conduct.⁹⁴

Currently, military radio installations operate outside standard ITU regulations⁹⁵ and most UN treaties do not address the dual-use nature of space technology. Systems such as the European Galileo programme serve a civil-military purpose, and international law permits conventional weapons in orbit under the Outer Space Treaty.⁹⁶ India's demonstration of anti-satellite (ASAT) capability in 2019⁹⁷ further shows the continuing militarisation of space and the absence of international enforcement against it. Although the UN conference on the Prevention of an Arms Race in Outer Space (PAROS) revealed strong objections from countries to the weaponisation of space, without proper regulation, these objections remain symbolic.

Canada strongly opposes the weaponisation of space⁹⁸ and effectively demonstrates the role mid-sized nations take in mitigating governance challenges. Canada mirrors the UK's approach, viewing responsible behaviour as a way to increase space security and stability through increasing transparency,⁹⁹ and is similarly a supporter of the UN Resolution 75/36 on reducing space threats and responsible behaviours.¹⁰⁰ Where mid-sized nations align in policy approach, their collective influence can shape UN resolutions without risk of being overshadowed by superpower dominance.

The ongoing debris problem poses one of the most serious threats to orbital sustainability, with around 140 million fragments between 1mm and 1cm and an estimated 1.2 million objects between 1cm and 10cm orbiting Earth.¹⁰¹ This accumulation, alongside the increase of mega-constellations, triggers the

⁹² Vaddi, P. R., & Warden, J. K. (2025). *Golden Dome and arms control: Impediment or opportunity?* *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 81(4), 296–304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2025.2518872>.

⁹³ *Ibid.*, 302.

⁹⁴ United Nations. (2024, April 24). Security Council Fails to Adopt First-Ever Resolution on Arms Race in Outer Space, Due to Negative Vote by the Russian Federation. <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15678.doc.htm>.

⁹⁵ International Telecommunication Union. (1994). *Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union* (Article 48). <https://www.itu.int/en/council/Documents/basic-texts/Constitution-E.pdf>.

⁹⁶ UNOOSA. (1967). *Outer Space Treaty*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

⁹⁷ İnan-Şimşek, A., & Atvur, S. (2025). Sustainable space governance as a key to protect future generations' rights. *European Journal of Futures Research*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-025-00254-8>.

⁹⁸ Huntley, *supra* note 15 at 257.

⁹⁹ Goody, A., & Shapiro, A. (2022). The growing complexity of space: Implications for security and stability. <https://lop.parl.ca/staticfiles/PublicWebsite/Home/ResearchPublications/HillStudies/PDF/2022-10-E.pdf> at 11-12.

¹⁰⁰ United Nations General Assembly. (2020). Reducing space threats through norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviours (Res. A/RES/75/36). <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n20/354/39/pdf/n2035439.pdf>.

¹⁰¹ European Space Agency. (2023, September 12). *Space debris by the numbers*. https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/Space_debris_by_the_numbers.

potential onset of the Kessler Syndrome,¹⁰² which could make orbital planes unusable and permanently reduce future access to space. Despite private company attempts at self-regulation, with SpaceX introducing reflective satellite coatings to reduce orbital light pollution¹⁰³ and the Space Safety Coalition's Best Practices for Sustainable Space Activities,¹⁰⁴ these efforts are voluntary and inconsistent. The reliance on voluntary self-regulation by profit-driven commercial actors reveals governance limitations in managing commercial expansion. The *New Zealand's Outer Space and High-altitude Activities Act 2017*¹⁰⁵ developed in response to foreign commercial operations, introducing licensing requirements and technology export controls to manage their dependence on commercial companies whilst aligning them with national policy objectives.¹⁰⁶

The 'tragedy of the commons'¹⁰⁷ aptly describes the risk of a self-interested space race for control and profit, leading to overcrowding, debris challenges and environmental deterioration. Without effective global management, space could descend into a competitive, destructive domain rather than a shared area for scientific innovation and human advancement. The 2024 UN Summit of the Future in Action 27 calls for reform of global governance, where emerging technological risks are addressed.¹⁰⁸ Future governance forums must prioritise equitable access to space resources, debris mitigation and sustainable exploration.¹⁰⁹ In this, UN COPUOS will play a crucial role in advancing international cooperation. Strengthening UN COPUOS as a supervising authority, through the inclusion of private actors and clearer objectives, would provide the structure to maintain order and responsible behaviour in space. Mid-sized nations, as consistent advocates for responsible space conduct and equitable governance, are well-positioned to lead this reform and can manage the dynamic of superpower unilateralism in the best interests of all spacefaring nations.

4.2. Regulatory Fragmentation Risks Without a Unified Governance Regime

Currently, international standards of space exploration are set by powerful states with advanced capabilities and political influence. There is no single body of governance, whether that be an external organisation or coalition of space nations, responsible for monitoring or enforcing these standards.¹¹⁰ In the absence of unified global governance, space activity remains subject to superpower dominance within a skewed power dynamic. Will space superpowers continue to dominate and set international standards on space governance, or can mid-sized powers hold them accountable?

¹⁰² For All Humanity – The Future of Outer Space Governance. (2023). *UN Executive Office of the Secretary-General (EOSG) Policy Briefs and Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.18356/27082245-30>.

¹⁰³ Akshaya, S., & Hitoishi, S. (2022). Regulation of Corporate Activity in the Space Sector. *Santa Clara Law Review*, 62(2), 375-421 <https://digitalcommons.law.scu.edu/lawreview/vol62/iss2/4> at 407.

¹⁰⁴ Space Safety Coalition. *Best Practices for the Sustainability of Space Operations*. (2019). NASA. https://s3vi.ndc.nasa.gov/ssri-kb/static/resources/Endorsement-of-Best-Practices-for-Sustainability_v42.pdf.

¹⁰⁵ New Zealand Parliament. (2017). *Outer Space and High-altitude Activities Act 2019*. <https://www.legislation.govt.nz/act/public/2017/29/en/latest/#DLM6966275>.

¹⁰⁶ Akshaya & Hitoishi, *supra* note 103 at 404.

¹⁰⁷ Aggarwal, *supra* note 56.

¹⁰⁸ United Nations General Assembly. (2024). Pact for the Future (Res. A/RES/79/1). United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/summit-of-the-future/pact-for-the-future>.

¹⁰⁹ Akshaya, *supra* note 103.

¹¹⁰ United Nations. (2023) *Our Common Agenda Policy Brief 7*. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2023/a77/a77crp_1add_6_0_html/our-common-agenda-policy-brief-outer-space-en.pdf at 3.

Political pressures within major spacefaring nations shape governance outcomes. As Aggarwal observes, ‘public opinion strongly translates to policy,’¹¹¹ meaning that during periods of international tension, major powers like the United States may enact space policies that reflect internal political pressures rather than neutral international norms, limiting the possibility of cohesive governance. Should the United States prevail in the current space hierarchy, future activity is likely to prioritise commercial expansion and resource mining as seen in the Artemis Accords and Trump’s 2025 Executive Order.¹¹² Although the UK remains a close ally of the US, its policy emphasis on sustainability and responsible space behaviour introduces regulatory tension, and balancing commercial expansion with space sustainability is a key governance challenge for the future.

The rise of private actors complicates the future trend of governance. Commercial space entities operate with limited accountability,¹¹³ pursuing goals of commercial, civil and military objectives. The lack of transparency around commercial objectives raises issues of regulation, liability and adherence to international law. As the role of public-private partnerships grows, mid-sized nations must navigate commercial dependency carefully; otherwise, the future of space governance risks the self-regulation of commercial actors. The UK’s Civil Aviation Authority is responsible for licensing sub-orbital activities under the Space Industry Act 2018, which emerged in response to commercial growth and positioned the UK as a responsible and reliable spacefaring state holding high international standards.¹¹⁴

The absence of a centralised international governance regime produces inconsistent standards across key areas of space activity, creating overlap and weak enforcement that undermines space stability and security. The UN COPUOS Subcommittee on national legislation was created to address these inconsistencies,¹¹⁵ but national legislation still remains fragmented. Fragmented space policy affects transparency and cooperation, which challenges the ability of mid-sized nations to influence governance outcomes and ensure superpower adherence to responsible practices. To address these challenges, scholars advocate for an intergovernmental forum that is tasked with protecting the rights and interests of future generations and establishing common goals and norms for space activity.¹¹⁶ As Colonel Patrick Frakes observes, such a body would require the technical expertise and committed membership to ‘optimize current and planned space activities with the goal of sustaining the environment for future generations.’¹¹⁷ Without this coordination, space could become inaccessible and unsafe for all actors. Mid-sized nations have positioned themselves as responsible advocates of space activity, and their political advocacy in such forums is well-suited to reflect the interests of all spacefaring states.

5. CONCLUSION

The governance of outer space is shaped by the ambitions of space superpowers, private entities and smaller actors aligned through regional networks. The disparity of influence has created regulatory inconsistencies and intensified competition, with space superpowers employing financial and technological tools to assert leadership. Ambitious lunar projects have increased tensions between

¹¹¹ Aggarwal, *supra* note 56 at 108.

¹¹² Executive Office of the President. (2025, December 18). *Ensuring American space superiority* [Executive order]. The White House. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/12/ensuring-american-space-superiority/>.

¹¹³ Newlove-Eriksson, *supra* note 55 at 280.

¹¹⁴ Newman, C. J. (2019). The Space Industry Act 2018: Unlocking the UK Space Economy. *Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law*, 62, 273-284. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?handle=hein.space/pinins10062&id=321>.

¹¹⁵ Fabio Tronchetti. (2013). *Fundamentals of Space Law and Policy*. New York, Ny Springer at 92.

¹¹⁶ İnan-Şimşek & Atvur, *supra* note 97.

¹¹⁷ Moltz, *supra* note 17 at 167.

superpowers and complicated the political alignment of smaller powers. Space sustainability and security are challenged not only through geopolitics but by intensified military capability in space powers, ultimately overshadowing the collective interests of all spacefaring nations. Commercial actors also operate outside collective interests and national policies, driven by financial profit. The private sector is not only independent but is also used as a tool for superpower dynamics, making regulation difficult given the sensitive nature of data-sharing and dual-use capabilities.

It is in this landscape that mid-sized nations have demonstrated their most meaningful contribution. Through regulatory developments, diplomatic engagement and scientific specialisation, they have influenced governance trends and promoted responsible space practice. The United Kingdom is a meaningful case study as its cohesive policy on licensing, leadership in sustainability initiatives, and partnership with superpowers and other mid-sized powers have earned it an internationally recognised standing in addressing major governance challenges like space debris.

Nonetheless, to secure a sustainable, equitable future in space, a cohesive international governance regime must be established. Without it, challenges of debris management, commercial competition and accountability will persist. Mid-sized nations are best positioned to provide this change, as they act without the power-driven objectives of superpower dominance, or the profit-focused motives of commercial actors, and advocate for policy that benefits the continued use of outer space for all.

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